

D31.1

Formal Specification of a Generic Separation Kernel

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Keywords:	separation kernel with control, formal model, instantiation, IPC, events, Isabelle/HOL

A previous version (1.0) of this document was *not* self-contained, because it referred to “A New Theory of Intransitive Noninterference for Separation Kernels with Control” that was not available.

To address this, this (1.1) version of the document now consists of two parts:

- the first part is the formal specification of a generic separation kernel itself, this part is identical to version 1.0 of this document
- the second part is “A New Theory of Intransitive Noninterference for Separation Kernels with Control”. This document is referenced in the first part.

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Executive Summary

We introduce a theory of intransitive non-interference for separation kernels with control. We show that it can be instantiated for a simple API consisting of IPC and events.

Contents

1	Introduction	3
1.1	Binders for the option type	3
1.2	Theorems on lists	3
2	A generic model for separation kernels	6
2.1	K (Kernel)	6
2.1.1	Execution semantics	7
2.2	SK (Separation Kernel)	8
2.2.1	Security for non-interfering domains	10
2.2.2	Security for indirectly interfering domains	21
2.3	ISK (Interruptible Separation Kernel)	34
2.4	CISK (Controlled Interruptible Separation Kernel)	48
2.4.1	Execution semantics	49
2.4.2	Formulations of security	50
2.4.3	Proofs	50
3	Instantiation by a separation kernel with concrete actions	57
3.1	Model of a separation kernel configuration	57
3.1.1	Type definitions	57
3.1.2	Configuration	58
3.2	Formulation of a subject-subject communication policy and an information flow policy, and showing both can be derived from subject-object configuration data	58
3.2.1	Specification	58
3.2.2	Derivation	59
3.3	Separation kernel state and atomic step function	60
3.3.1	Interrupt points	60
3.3.2	System state	60
3.3.3	Atomic step	61
3.4	Preconditions and invariants for the atomic step	63
3.4.1	Atomic steps of SK_IPC preserve invariants	63
3.4.2	Summary theorems on atomic step invariants	65
3.5	The view-partitioning equivalence relation	66
3.5.1	Elementary properties	67
3.6	Atomic step locally respects the information flow policy	67
3.6.1	Locally respects of atomic step functions	67
3.6.2	Summary theorems on view-partitioning locally respects	70
3.7	Weak step consistency	70
3.7.1	Weak step consistency of auxiliary functions	70
3.7.2	Weak step consistency of atomic step functions	72
3.7.3	Summary theorems on view-partitioning weak step consistency	74
3.8	Separation kernel model	75
3.8.1	Initial state of separation kernel model	75
3.8.2	Types for instantiation of the generic model	76
3.8.3	Possible action sequences	77
3.8.4	Control	77
3.8.5	Discharging the proof obligations	78
3.9	Link implementation to CISK: the specific separation kernel is an interpretation of the generic model.	87

4 Conclusion

90

1 Introduction

In Section 2 we introduce a theory of intransitive non-interference for separation kernels with control, based on [3]. We show that it can be instantiated for a simple API consisting of IPC and events (Section 3). The rest of *this* section gives some auxiliary theories used for Section 2.

1.1 Binders for the option type

```
theory Option-Binders
  imports Option
begin
```

The following functions are used as binders in the theorems that are proven. At all times, when a result is `None`, the theorem becomes vacuously true. The expression “ $m \rightarrow \alpha$ ” means “First compute m , if it is `None` then return `True`, otherwise pass the result to α ”. `B2` is a short hand for sequentially doing two independent computations. The following syntax is associated to `B2`: “ $m_1 || m_2 \rightarrow \alpha$ ” represents “First compute m_1 and m_2 , if one of them is `None` then return `True`, otherwise pass the result to α ”.

```
definition B :: 'a option => ('a => bool) => bool (infixl -> 65)
where B m α ≡ case m of None => True | (Some a) => α a
```

```
definition B2 :: 'a option => 'a option => ('a => 'a => bool) => bool
where B2 m1 m2 α ≡ m1 -> (λ a . m2 -> (λ b . α a b))
```

```
syntax B2 :: ['a option, 'a option, ('a => 'a => bool)] => bool ((- || - -> -) [0, 0, 10] 10)
```

Some rewriting rules for the binders

```
lemma rewrite-B2-to-cases[simp]:
  shows B2 s t f = (case s of None => True | (Some s1) => (case t of None => True | (Some t1) => f s1 t1))
using assms unfolding B2-def B-def by(cases s,cases t,simp+)
lemma rewrite-B-None[simp]:
  shows None -> α = True
unfolding B-def by(auto)
lemma rewrite-B-m-True[simp]:
  shows m -> (λ a . True) = True
unfolding B-def by(cases m,simp+)
lemma rewrite-B2-cases:
  shows (case a of None => True | (Some s) => (case b of None => True | (Some t) => f s t))
    = (∀ s t . a = (Some s) ∧ b = (Some t) -> f s t)
by(cases a,simp,cases b,simp+)

definition strict-equal :: 'a option => 'a => bool
where strict-equal m a ≡ case m of None => False | (Some a') => a' = a

end
```

1.2 Theorems on lists

```
theory List-Theorems
  imports List
begin
```

```
definition lastn :: nat => 'a list => 'a list
where lastn n x = drop ((length x) - n) x
```

definition *is-sub-seq* :: 'a ⇒ 'a ⇒ 'a list ⇒ bool
where *is-sub-seq* a b x ≡ ∃ n . Suc n < length x ∧ x!n = a ∧ x!(Suc n) = b

definition *prefixes* :: 'a list set ⇒ 'a list set
where *prefixes* s ≡ {x . ∃ n y . n > 0 ∧ y ∈ s ∧ take n y = x}

lemma *drop-one*[*simp*]:

shows *drop* (Suc 0) x = tl x **by** (*induct* x,*auto*)

lemma *length-ge-one*:

shows x ≠ [] → length x ≥ 1 **by** (*induct* x,*auto*)

lemma *take-but-one*[*simp*]:

shows x ≠ [] → lastn ((length x) - 1) x = tl x **unfolding** *lastn-def*

using *length-ge-one* [**where** x=x] **by** *auto*

lemma *Suc-m-minus-n*[*simp*]:

shows m ≥ n → Suc m - n = Suc (m - n) **by** *auto*

lemma *lastn-one-less*:

shows n > 0 ∧ n ≤ length x ∧ lastn n x = (a#y) → lastn (n - 1) x = y **unfolding** *lastn-def*

using *drop-Suc* [**where** n=length x - n **and** xs=x] *drop-tl* [**where** n=length x - n **and** xs=x]

by (*auto*)

lemma *list-sub-implies-member*:

shows ∀ a x . set (a#x) ⊆ Z → a ∈ Z **by** *auto*

lemma *subset-smaller-list*:

shows ∀ a x . set (a#x) ⊆ Z → set x ⊆ Z **by** *auto*

lemma *second-elt-is-hd-tl*:

shows tl x = (a # x') → a = x ! 1

by (*cases* x,*auto*)

lemma *length-ge-2-implies-tl-not-empty*:

shows length x ≥ 2 → tl x ≠ []

by (*cases* x,*auto*)

lemma *length-lt-2-implies-tl-empty*:

shows length x < 2 → tl x = []

by (*cases* x,*auto*)

lemma *first-second-is-sub-seq*:

shows length x ≥ 2 ⇒ *is-sub-seq* (hd x) (x!1) x

proof–

assume length x ≥ 2

hence 1: (Suc 0) < length x **by** *auto*

hence x!0 = hd x **by** (*cases* x,*auto*)

from this 1 **show** *is-sub-seq* (hd x) (x!1) x **unfolding** *is-sub-seq-def* **by** *auto*

qed

lemma *hd-drop-is-nth*:

shows n < length x ⇒ hd (drop n x) = x!n

proof (*induct* x *arbitrary*: n)

case Nil

thus ?*case* **by** *simp*

next

case (Cons a x)

{

have hd (drop n (a # x)) = (a # x) ! n

proof (*cases* n)

case 0

thus ?*thesis* **by** *simp*

next

case (Suc m)

from Suc Cons **show** ?*thesis* **by** *auto*

qed

}

thus ?case by auto
qed

lemma def-of-hd:

shows $y = a \# x \longrightarrow \text{hd } y = a$ **by simp**

lemma def-of-tl:

shows $y = a \# x \longrightarrow \text{tl } y = x$ **by simp**

lemma drop-yields-results-implies-nbound:

shows $\text{drop } n \ x \neq [] \longrightarrow n < \text{length } x$

by (induct x, auto)

lemma hd-take[simp]:

shows $n > 0 \implies \text{hd } (\text{take } n \ x) = \text{hd } x$

by (cases x, simp, cases n, auto)

lemma consecutive-is-sub-seq:

shows $a \# (b \# x) = \text{lastn } n \ y \implies \text{is-sub-seq } a \ b \ y$

proof-

assume $I: a \# (b \# x) = \text{lastn } n \ y$

from I **drop-Suc** [where $n = (\text{length } y) - n$ and $xs = y$]

drop-tl [where $n = (\text{length } y) - n$ and $xs = y$]

def-of-tl [where $y = \text{lastn } n \ y$ and $a = a$ and $x = b \# x$]

drop-yields-results-implies-nbound [where $n = \text{Suc } (\text{length } y - n)$ and $x = y$]

have $3: \text{Suc } (\text{length } y - n) < \text{length } y$ **unfolding lastn-def by auto**

from 3 I **hd-drop-is-nth** [where $n = (\text{length } y) - n$ and $x = y$] **def-of-hd** [where $y = \text{drop } (\text{length } y - n) \ y$ and $x = b \# x$ and $a = a$]

have $4: y!(\text{length } y - n) = a$ **unfolding lastn-def by auto**

from 3 I **hd-drop-is-nth** [where $n = \text{Suc } ((\text{length } y) - n)$ and $x = y$] **def-of-hd** [where $y = \text{drop } (\text{Suc } (\text{length } y - n))$ and $x = x$ and $a = b$]

drop-Suc [where $n = (\text{length } y) - n$ and $xs = y$]

drop-tl [where $n = (\text{length } y) - n$ and $xs = y$]

def-of-tl [where $y = \text{lastn } n \ y$ and $a = a$ and $x = b \# x$]

have $5: y! \text{Suc } (\text{length } y - n) = b$ **unfolding lastn-def by auto**

from 3 4 5 **show** ?thesis

unfolding is-sub-seq-def by auto

qed

lemma sub-seq-in-prefixes:

assumes $\exists y \in \text{prefixes } X. \text{is-sub-seq } a \ a' \ y$

shows $\exists y \in X. \text{is-sub-seq } a \ a' \ y$

proof-

from *assms* **obtain** y **where** $y: y \in \text{prefixes } X \wedge \text{is-sub-seq } a \ a' \ y$ **by auto**

then obtain $n \ x$ **where** $x: n > 0 \wedge x \in X \wedge \text{take } n \ x = y$

unfolding prefixes-def by auto

from y **obtain** i **where** $\text{sub-seq-index}: \text{Suc } i < \text{length } y \wedge y! i = a \wedge y! \text{Suc } i = a'$

unfolding is-sub-seq-def by auto

from $\text{sub-seq-index } x$ **have** $\text{is-sub-seq } a \ a' \ x$

unfolding is-sub-seq-def using nth-take by auto

from $\text{this } x$ **show** ?thesis **by metis**

qed

lemma set-tl-is-subset:

shows $\text{set } (\text{tl } x) \subseteq \text{set } x$ **by** (induct x, auto)

lemma x-is-hd-snd-tl:

shows $\text{length } x \geq 2 \longrightarrow x = (\text{hd } x) \# x!1 \# \text{tl } (\text{tl } x)$

proof (induct x)

case Nil

show ?case **by auto**

```

case (Cons a xs)
  show ?case by(induct xs,auto)
qed

lemma tl-x-not-x:
shows  $x \neq [] \longrightarrow tl\ x \neq x$  by(induct x,auto)
lemma tl-hd-x-not-tl-x:
shows  $x \neq [] \wedge hd\ x \neq [] \longrightarrow tl\ (hd\ x) \neq x$  using tl-x-not-x by(induct x,simp,auto)

end

```

2 A generic model for separation kernels

This section defines a detailed generic model of separation kernels called CISK (Controlled Interruptible Separation Kernel). It contains a generic functional model of the behaviour of a separation kernel as a transition system, definitions of the security property and proofs that the functional model satisfies security properties. It is based on Rushby’s approach [2] for noninterference. For an explanation of the model, its structure and an overview of the proofs, we refer to the document entitled “A New Theory of Intransitive Noninterference for Separation Kernels with Control” [3].

The structure of the model is based on locales and refinement:

- locale “Kernel” defines a highly generic model for a kernel, with execution semantics. It defines a state transition system with some extensions to the one used in [2]. The transition system defined here stores the currently active domain in the state, and has transitions for explicit context switches and interrupts and provides a notion of control. As each operation of the system will be split into atomic actions in our model, only certain sequences of actions will correspond to a run on a real system. Therefore, the function *run*, which applies an execution on a state and computes the resulting new state, is partial and defined for realistic traces only. Later, but not in this locale, we will define a predicate to distinguish realistic traces from other traces. Security properties are also not part of this locale, but will be introduced in the locales to be described next.
- locale “Separation_Kernel” extends “Kernel” with constraints concerning non-interference. The theorem is only sensible for realistic traces; for unrealistic trace it will hold vacuously.
- locale “Interruptible_Separation_Kernel” refines “Separation_Kernel” with interruptible action sequences. It defines function “realistic_trace” based on these action sequences. Therefore, we can formulate a total run function.
- locale “Controlled_Interruptible_Separation_Kernel” refines “Interruptible_Separation_Kernel” with abortable action sequences. It refines function “control” which now uses a generic predicate “aborting” and a generic function “set_error_code” to manage aborting of action sequences.

2.1 K (Kernel)

```

theory K
imports Main List Set Transitive-Closure List-Theorems Option-Binders
begin

```

The model makes use of the following types:

'state.t A state contains information about the resources of the system, as well as which domain is currently active. We decided that a state does *not* need to include a program stack, as in this model the actions that are executed are modelled separately.

'dom.t A domain is an entity executing actions and making calls to the kernel. This type represents the names of all domains. Later on, we define security policies in terms of domains.

'action.t Actions of type 'action.t represent atomic instructions that are executed by the kernel. As kernel actions are assumed to be atomic, we assume that after each kernel action an interrupt point can occur.

'action.t execution An execution of some domain is the code or the program that is executed by the domain. One call from a domain to the kernel will typically trigger a succession of one or more kernel actions. Therefore, an execution is represented as a list of *sequences* of kernel actions. Non-kernel actions are not take into account.

'output.t Given the current state and an action an output can be computed deterministically.

time.t Time is modelled using natural numbers. Each atomic kernel action can be executed within one time unit.

type-synonym ('action-t) execution = 'action-t list list

type-synonym time-t = nat

Function *kstep* (for kernel step) computes the next state based on the current state *s* and a given action *a*. It may assume that it makes sense to perform this action, i.e., that any precondition that is necessary for execution of action *a* in state *s* is met. If not, it may return any result. This precondition is represented by generic predicate *kprecondition* (for kernel precondition). Only realistic traces are considered. Predicate *realistic_execution* decides whether a given execution is realistic.

Function *current* returns given the state the domain that is currently executing actions. The model assumes a single-core setting, i.e., at all times only one domain is active. Interrupt behavior is modelled using functions *interrupt* and *cswitch* (for context switch) that dictate respectively when interrupts occur and how interrupts occur. Interrupts are solely time-based, meaning that there is an at beforehand fixed schedule dictating which domain is active at which time.

Finally, we add function *control*. This function represents control of the kernel over the execution as performed by the domains. Given the current state *s*, the currently active domain *d* and the execution α of that domain, it returns three objects. First, it returns the next action that domain *d* will perform. Commonly, this is the next action in execution α . It may also return None, indicating that no action is done. Secondly, it returns the updated execution. When executing action *a*, typically, this action will be removed from the current execution (i.e., updating the program stack). Thirdly, it can update the state to set, e.g., error codes.

locale Kernel =

```

fixes kstep :: 'state-t  $\Rightarrow$  'action-t  $\Rightarrow$  'state-t
and output-f :: 'state-t  $\Rightarrow$  'action-t  $\Rightarrow$  'output-t
and s0 :: 'state-t
and current :: 'state-t  $\Rightarrow$  'dom-t
and cswitch :: time-t  $\Rightarrow$  'state-t  $\Rightarrow$  'state-t
and interrupt :: time-t  $\Rightarrow$  bool
and kprecondition :: 'state-t  $\Rightarrow$  'action-t  $\Rightarrow$  bool
and realistic-execution :: 'action-t execution  $\Rightarrow$  bool
and control :: 'state-t  $\Rightarrow$  'dom-t  $\Rightarrow$  'action-t execution  $\Rightarrow$ 
    (('action-t option)  $\times$  'action-t execution  $\times$  'state-t)
and kinvolved :: 'action-t  $\Rightarrow$  'dom-t set

```

begin

2.1.1 Execution semantics

Short hand notations for using function control.

definition next-action::'state-t \Rightarrow ('dom-t \Rightarrow 'action-t execution) \Rightarrow 'action-t option

where next-action s execs = fst (control s (current s) (execs (current s)))

definition next-exec::'state-t \Rightarrow ('dom-t \Rightarrow 'action-t execution) \Rightarrow ('dom-t \Rightarrow 'action-t execution)

where $next\text{-execs } s \text{ execs} = (fun\text{-upd } execs (current\ s) (fst (snd (control\ s (current\ s) (execs (current\ s))))))$
definition $next\text{-state}::'state\text{-}t \Rightarrow ('dom\text{-}t \Rightarrow 'action\text{-}t \text{ execution}) \Rightarrow 'state\text{-}t$
where $next\text{-state } s \text{ execs} = snd (snd (control\ s (current\ s) (execs (current\ s))))$

A thread is empty iff either it has no further action sequences to execute, or when the current action sequence is finished and there are no further action sequences to execute.

abbreviation $thread\text{-}empty::'action\text{-}t \text{ execution} \Rightarrow bool$
where $thread\text{-}empty\ exec \equiv exec = [] \vee exec = [[]]$

Wrappers for function `kstep` and `kprecondition` that deal with the case where the given action is `None`.

definition $step\ \mathbf{where}\ step\ s\ oa \equiv case\ oa\ of\ None \Rightarrow s \mid (Some\ a) \Rightarrow kstep\ s\ a$

definition $precondition::'state\text{-}t \Rightarrow 'action\text{-}t \text{ option} \Rightarrow bool$

where $precondition\ s\ a \equiv a \rightarrow kprecondition\ s$

definition $involved$

where $involved\ oa \equiv case\ oa\ of\ None \Rightarrow \{\} \mid (Some\ a) \Rightarrow kinvolved\ a$

Execution semantics are defined as follows: a run consists of consecutively running sequences of actions. These sequences are interruptable. Run first checks whether an interrupt occurs. When this happens, function `cswitch` may switch the context. Otherwise, function `control` is used to determine the next action a , which also yields a new state s' . Action a is executed by executing $(step\ s' a)$. The current execution of the current domain is updated.

Note that `run` is a partial function, i.e., it computes results only when at all times the preconditions hold. Such runs are the realistic ones. For other runs, we do not need to – and cannot – prove security. All the theorems are formulated in such a way that they hold vacuously for unrealistic runs.

function $run::time\text{-}t \Rightarrow 'state\text{-}t \text{ option} \Rightarrow ('dom\text{-}t \Rightarrow 'action\text{-}t \text{ execution}) \Rightarrow 'state\text{-}t \text{ option}$

where $run\ 0\ s \text{ execs} = s$

$| run\ (Suc\ n)\ None \text{ execs} = None$

$| interrupt\ (Suc\ n) \Longrightarrow run\ (Suc\ n)\ (Some\ s) \text{ execs} = run\ n\ (Some\ (cswitch\ (Suc\ n)\ s)) \text{ execs}$

$| \neg interrupt\ (Suc\ n) \Longrightarrow thread\text{-}empty(execs\ (current\ s)) \Longrightarrow run\ (Suc\ n)\ (Some\ s) \text{ execs} = run\ n\ (Some\ s) \text{ execs}$

$| \neg interrupt\ (Suc\ n) \Longrightarrow \neg thread\text{-}empty(execs\ (current\ s)) \Longrightarrow \neg precondition\ (next\text{-state } s \text{ execs})\ (next\text{-action } s \text{ execs}) \Longrightarrow run\ (Suc\ n)\ (Some\ s) \text{ execs} = None$

$| \neg interrupt\ (Suc\ n) \Longrightarrow \neg thread\text{-}empty(execs\ (current\ s)) \Longrightarrow precondition\ (next\text{-state } s \text{ execs})\ (next\text{-action } s \text{ execs}) \Longrightarrow$

$run\ (Suc\ n)\ (Some\ s) \text{ execs} = run\ n\ (Some\ (step\ (next\text{-state } s \text{ execs})\ (next\text{-action } s \text{ execs)))\ (next\text{-execs } s \text{ execs})$

using $not0\text{-implies}\text{-}Suc$ **by** $(metis\ option.\text{exhaust}\ prod\text{-cases}3,\text{auto})$

termination by lexicographic-order

end

end

2.2 SK (Separation Kernel)

theory SK

imports K

begin

Locale Kernel is now refined to a generic model of a separation kernel. The security policy is represented using function ia . Function $vpeq$ is adopted from Rushby and is an equivalence relation representing whether two states are equivalent from the point of view of the given domain.

We assume constraints similar to Rushby, i.e., weak step consistency, locally respects, and output consistency. Additional assumptions are:

Step Atomicity Each atomic kernel step can be executed within one time slot. Therefore, the domain that is currently active does not change by executing one action.

Time-based Interrupts As interrupts occur according to a prefixed time-based schedule, the domain that is active after a call of `switch` depends on the currently active domain only (`cswitch_consistency`). Also, `cswitch` can *only* change which domain is currently active (`cswitch_consistency`).

Control Consistency States that are equivalent yield the same control. That is, the next action and the updated execution depend on the currently active domain only (`next_action_consistent`, `next_execs_consistent`), the state as updated by the control function remains in `vpeq` (`next_state_consistent`, `locally_respects_next_state`). Finally, function `control` cannot change which domain is active (`current_next_state`).

definition *actions-in-execution* :: 'action-t execution \Rightarrow 'action-t set
where *actions-in-execution exec* $\equiv \{ a . \exists aseq \in set\ exec . a \in set\ aseq \}$

locale *Separation-Kernel* = *Kernel kstep output-f s0 current cswitch interrupt kprecondition realistic-execution control kinvolved*

for *kstep* :: 'state-t \Rightarrow 'action-t \Rightarrow 'state-t
and *output-f* :: 'state-t \Rightarrow 'action-t \Rightarrow 'output-t
and *s0* :: 'state-t
and *current* :: 'state-t \Rightarrow 'dom-t — Returns the currently active domain
and *cswitch* :: time-t \Rightarrow 'state-t \Rightarrow 'state-t — Switches the current domain
and *interrupt* :: time-t \Rightarrow bool — Returns t iff an interrupt occurs in the given state at the given time
and *kprecondition* :: 'state-t \Rightarrow 'action-t \Rightarrow bool — Returns t if an precondition holds that relates the current action to the state
and *realistic-execution* :: 'action-t execution \Rightarrow bool — In this locale, this function is completely unconstrained.
and *control* :: 'state-t \Rightarrow 'dom-t \Rightarrow 'action-t execution \Rightarrow (('action-t option) \times 'action-t execution \times 'state-t)
and *kinvolved* :: 'action-t \Rightarrow 'dom-t set
+
fixes *ifp* :: 'dom-t \Rightarrow 'dom-t \Rightarrow bool
and *vpeq* :: 'dom-t \Rightarrow 'state-t \Rightarrow 'state-t \Rightarrow bool
assumes *vpeq-transitive*: $\forall a b c u . (vpeq\ u\ a\ b \wedge vpeq\ u\ b\ c) \longrightarrow vpeq\ u\ a\ c$
and *vpeq-symmetric*: $\forall a b u . vpeq\ u\ a\ b \longrightarrow vpeq\ u\ b\ a$
and *vpeq-reflexive*: $\forall a u . vpeq\ u\ a\ a$
and *ifp-reflexive*: $\forall u . ifp\ u\ u$
and *weakly-step-consistent*: $\forall s t u a . vpeq\ u\ s\ t \wedge vpeq\ (current\ s)\ s\ t \wedge kprecondition\ s\ a \wedge kprecondition\ t\ a$
 $\wedge current\ s = current\ t \longrightarrow vpeq\ u\ (kstep\ s\ a)\ (kstep\ t\ a)$
and *locally-respects*: $\forall a s u . \neg ifp\ (current\ s)\ u \wedge kprecondition\ s\ a \longrightarrow vpeq\ u\ s\ (kstep\ s\ a)$
and *output-consistent*: $\forall a s t . vpeq\ (current\ s)\ s\ t \wedge current\ s = current\ t \longrightarrow (output-f\ s\ a) = (output-f\ t\ a)$
and *step-atomicity*: $\forall s a . current\ (kstep\ s\ a) = current\ s$
and *cswitch-independent-of-state*: $\forall n s t . current\ s = current\ t \longrightarrow current\ (cswitch\ n\ s) = current\ (cswitch\ n\ t)$
and *cswitch-consistency*: $\forall u s t n . vpeq\ u\ s\ t \longrightarrow vpeq\ u\ (cswitch\ n\ s)\ (cswitch\ n\ t)$
and *next-action-consistent*: $\forall s t execs . vpeq\ (current\ s)\ s\ t \wedge (\forall d \in involved\ (next-action\ s\ execs) . vpeq\ d\ s\ t) \wedge current\ s = current\ t \longrightarrow next-action\ s\ execs = next-action\ t\ execs$
and *next-exec-consistent*: $\forall s t execs . vpeq\ (current\ s)\ s\ t \wedge (\forall d \in involved\ (next-action\ s\ execs) . vpeq\ d\ s\ t) \wedge current\ s = current\ t \longrightarrow fst\ (snd\ (control\ s\ (current\ s)\ (execs\ (current\ s)))) = fst\ (snd\ (control\ t\ (current\ s)\ (execs\ (current\ s))))$
and *next-state-consistent*: $\forall s t u execs . vpeq\ (current\ s)\ s\ t \wedge vpeq\ u\ s\ t \wedge current\ s = current\ t \longrightarrow vpeq\ u\ (next-state\ s\ execs)\ (next-state\ t\ execs)$
and *current-next-state*: $\forall s execs . current\ (next-state\ s\ execs) = current\ s$
and *locally-respects-next-state*: $\forall s u execs . \neg ifp\ (current\ s)\ u \longrightarrow vpeq\ u\ s\ (next-state\ s\ execs)$
and *involved-ifp*: $\forall s a . \forall d \in (involved\ a) . kprecondition\ s\ (the\ a) \longrightarrow ifp\ d\ (current\ s)$
and *next-action-from-exec*: $\forall s execs . next-action\ s\ execs \rightarrow (\lambda a . a \in actions-in-execution\ (execs\ (current\ s)))$
and *next-exec-subset*: $\forall s execs u . actions-in-execution\ (next-exec\ s\ execs\ u) \subseteq actions-in-execution\ (execs\ u)$
begin

Note that there are no proof obligations on function “interrupt”. Its typing enforces the assumptions

that switching is based on time and not on state. This assumption is sufficient for these proofs, i.e., no further assumptions are required.

2.2.1 Security for non-interfering domains

We define security for domains that are completely non-interfering. That is, for all domains u and v such that v may not interfere in any way with domain u , we prove that the behavior of domain u is independent of the actions performed by v . In other words, the output of domain u in some run is at all times equivalent to the output of domain u when the actions of domain v are replaced by some other set actions.

A domain is unrelated to u if and only if the security policy dictates that there is no path from the domain to u .

abbreviation $unrelated :: 'dom-t \Rightarrow 'dom-t \Rightarrow bool$
where $unrelated\ d\ u \equiv \neg ifp^{**}\ d\ u$

To formulate the new theorem to prove, we redefine purging: all domains that may not influence domain u are replaced by arbitrary action sequences.

definition $purge :: ('dom-t \Rightarrow 'action-t\ execution) \Rightarrow 'dom-t \Rightarrow ('dom-t \Rightarrow 'action-t\ execution)$
where $purge\ execs\ u \equiv \lambda\ d . (if\ unrelated\ d\ u\ then\ (SOME\ alpha . realistic-execution\ alpha)\ else\ execs\ d)$

A normal run from initial state s_0 ending in state s_f is equivalent to a run purged for domain $(currents_f)$.

definition $NI-unrelated\ where\ NI-unrelated$
 $\equiv \forall\ execs\ a\ n . run\ n\ (Some\ s_0)\ execs \rightarrow (\lambda\ s_f . run\ n\ (Some\ s_0)\ (purge\ execs\ (current\ s_f))) \rightarrow (\lambda\ s_f2 . output-f\ s_f\ a = output-f\ s_f2\ a \wedge current\ s_f = current\ s_f2))$

The following properties are proven inductive over states s and t :

1. Invariably, states s and t are equivalent for any domain v that may influence the purged domain u . This is more general than proving that “ $vpeq\ u\ s\ t$ ” is inductive. The reason we need to prove equivalence over all domains v is so that we can use *weak* step consistency.
2. Invariably, states s and t have the same active domain.

abbreviation $equivalent-states :: 'state-t\ option \Rightarrow 'state-t\ option \Rightarrow 'dom-t \Rightarrow bool$
where $equivalent-states\ s\ t\ u \equiv s\ \parallel\ t \rightarrow (\lambda\ s\ t . (\forall\ v . ifp^{**}\ v\ u \rightarrow vpeq\ v\ s\ t) \wedge current\ s = current\ t)$

Rushby’s view partitioning is redefined. Two states that are initially u -equivalent are u -equivalent after performing respectively a realistic run and a realistic purged run.

definition $view-partitioned :: bool\ where\ view-partitioned$
 $\equiv \forall\ execs\ ms\ mt\ n\ u . equivalent-states\ ms\ mt\ u \rightarrow (run\ n\ ms\ execs\ \parallel\ run\ n\ mt\ (purge\ execs\ u) \rightarrow (\lambda\ rs\ rt . vpeq\ u\ rs\ rt \wedge current\ rs = current\ rt))$

We formulate a version of predicate $view_partitioned$ that is on one hand more general, but on the other hand easier to prove inductive over function run . Instead of reasoning over $execs$ and $(purge\ execs\ u)$, we reason over any two executions $execs1$ and $execs2$ for which the following relation holds:

definition $purged-relation :: 'dom-t \Rightarrow ('dom-t \Rightarrow 'action-t\ execution) \Rightarrow ('dom-t \Rightarrow 'action-t\ execution) \Rightarrow bool$
where $purged-relation\ u\ execs1\ execs2 \equiv \forall\ d . ifp^{**}\ d\ u \rightarrow execs1\ d = execs2\ d$

The inductive version of view partitioning says that runs on two states that are u -equivalent and on two executions that are purged_related yield u -equivalent states.

definition *view-partitioned-ind::bool* **where** *view-partitioned-ind*

$\equiv \forall \text{execs1 } \text{execs2 } s \ t \ n \ u . \text{equivalent-states } s \ t \ u \wedge \text{purged-relation } u \ \text{execs1 } \text{execs2} \longrightarrow \text{equivalent-states } (\text{run } n \ s \ \text{execs1}) \ (\text{run } n \ t \ \text{execs2}) \ u$

A proof that when state t performs a step but state s not, the states remain equivalent for any domain v that may interfere with u .

lemma *vpeq-s-nt*:

assumes *prec-t*: *precondition* (*next-state* t *execs2*) (*next-action* t *execs2*)

assumes *not-ifp-curr-u*: $\neg \text{ifp}^{**} (\text{current } t) \ u$

assumes *vpeq-s-t*: $\forall v . \text{ifp}^{**} v \ u \longrightarrow \text{vpeq } v \ s \ t$

shows ($\forall v . \text{ifp}^{**} v \ u \longrightarrow \text{vpeq } v \ s \ (\text{step } (\text{next-state } t \ \text{execs2}) \ (\text{next-action } t \ \text{execs2}))$)

proof-

{

fix v

assume *ifp-v-u*: $\text{ifp}^{**} v \ u$

from *ifp-v-u* **and** *not-ifp-curr-u* **have** *unrelated*: $\neg \text{ifp}^{**} (\text{current } t) \ v$ **using** *rtranclp-trans* **by** *metis*

from *this* *current-next-state*[*THEN spec*,*THEN spec*,**where** $x1=t$]

locally-respects[*THEN spec*,*THEN spec*,*THEN spec*,**where** $x1=\text{next-state } t \ \text{execs2}$] *vpeq-reflexive*

prec-t **have** *vpeq* $v \ (\text{next-state } t \ \text{execs2}) \ (\text{step } (\text{next-state } t \ \text{execs2}) \ (\text{next-action } t \ \text{execs2}))$

unfolding *step-def precondition-def B-def*

by (*cases next-action* $t \ \text{execs2}$,*auto*)

from *unrelated* *this* *locally-respects-next-state* *vpeq-transitive* **have** *vpeq* $v \ t \ (\text{step } (\text{next-state } t \ \text{execs2}) \ (\text{next-action } t \ \text{execs2}))$ **by** *blast*

from *this* **and** *ifp-v-u* **and** *vpeq-s-t* **and** *vpeq-symmetric* **and** *vpeq-transitive* **have** *vpeq* $v \ s \ (\text{step } (\text{next-state } t \ \text{execs2}) \ (\text{next-action } t \ \text{execs2}))$ **by** *metis*

}

thus *?thesis* **by** *auto*

qed

A proof that when state s performs a step but state t not, the states remain equivalent for any domain v that may interfere with u .

lemma *vpeq-ns-t*:

assumes *prec-s*: *precondition* (*next-state* s *execs*) (*next-action* s *execs*)

assumes *not-ifp-curr-u*: $\neg \text{ifp}^{**} (\text{current } s) \ u$

assumes *vpeq-s-t*: $\forall v . \text{ifp}^{**} v \ u \longrightarrow \text{vpeq } v \ s \ t$

shows $\forall v . \text{ifp}^{**} v \ u \longrightarrow \text{vpeq } v \ t \ (\text{step } (\text{next-state } s \ \text{execs}) \ (\text{next-action } s \ \text{execs}))$

proof-

{

fix v

assume *ifp-v-u*: $\text{ifp}^{**} v \ u$

from *ifp-v-u* **and** *not-ifp-curr-u* **have** *unrelated*: $\neg \text{ifp}^{**} (\text{current } s) \ v$ **using** *rtranclp-trans* **by** *metis*

from *this* *current-next-state*[*THEN spec*,*THEN spec*,**where** $x1=s$] *vpeq-reflexive*

unrelated *locally-respects*[*THEN spec*,*THEN spec*,*THEN spec*,**where** $x1=\text{next-state } s \ \text{execs}$ **and** $x=v$ **and** $x2=\text{the } (\text{next-action } s \ \text{execs})$] *prec-s*

have *vpeq* $v \ (\text{next-state } s \ \text{execs}) \ (\text{step } (\text{next-state } s \ \text{execs}) \ (\text{next-action } s \ \text{execs}))$

unfolding *step-def precondition-def B-def*

by (*cases next-action* $s \ \text{execs}$,*auto*)

from *unrelated* *this* *locally-respects-next-state* *vpeq-transitive* **have** *vpeq* $v \ s \ (\text{step } (\text{next-state } s \ \text{execs}) \ (\text{next-action } s \ \text{execs}))$ **by** *blast*

from *this* **and** *ifp-v-u* **and** *vpeq-s-t* **and** *vpeq-symmetric* **and** *vpeq-transitive* **have** *vpeq* $v \ t \ (\text{step } (\text{next-state } s \ \text{execs}) \ (\text{next-action } s \ \text{execs}))$ **by** *metis*

}

thus *?thesis* **by** *auto*

qed

A proof that when both states s and t perform a step, the states remain equivalent for any domain v that may interfere with u . It assumes that the current domain *can* interact with u (the domain for which is purged).

lemma *vpeq-ns-nt-ifp-u*:**assumes** *vpeq-s-t*: $\forall v . \text{ifp}^{**} v u \longrightarrow \text{vpeq } v s t'$ **and** *current-s-t*: $\text{current } s = \text{current } t'$ **shows** *precondition* (*next-state* s *execs*) $a \wedge \text{precondition}$ (*next-state* t' *execs*) $a \implies (\text{ifp}^{**} (\text{current } s) u \implies (\forall v . \text{ifp}^{**} v u \longrightarrow \text{vpeq } v (\text{step } (\text{next-state } s \text{ execs}) a) (\text{step } (\text{next-state } t' \text{ execs}) a)))$ **proof**–**fix** a **assume** *prec-s*: *precondition* (*next-state* s *execs*) $a \wedge \text{precondition}$ (*next-state* t' *execs*) a **assume** *ifp-curr*: $\text{ifp}^{**} (\text{current } s) u$ **from** *vpeq-s-t* **have** *vpeq-curr-s-t*: $\text{ifp}^{**} (\text{current } s) u \longrightarrow \text{vpeq } (\text{current } s) s t'$ **by** *auto***from** *ifp-curr* *prec-s*

$$\text{next-state-consistent}[\text{THEN } \text{spec}, \text{THEN } \text{spec}, \text{where } x1=s \text{ and } x=t'] \text{vpeq-curr-s-t } \text{vpeq-s-t}$$

$$\text{current-next-state } \text{current-s-t } \text{weakly-step-consistent}[\text{THEN } \text{spec}, \text{THEN } \text{spec}, \text{THEN } \text{spec}, \text{THEN } \text{spec}, \text{where } x3=\text{next-state } s \text{ execs and } x2=\text{next-state } t' \text{ execs and } x=\text{the } a]$$
show $\forall v . \text{ifp}^{**} v u \longrightarrow \text{vpeq } v (\text{step } (\text{next-state } s \text{ execs}) a) (\text{step } (\text{next-state } t' \text{ execs}) a)$ **unfolding** *step-def precondition-def B-def***by** (*cases a, auto*)**qed**

A proof that when both states s and t perform a step, the states remain equivalent for any domain v that may interfere with u . It assumes that the current domain *cannot* interact with u (the domain for which is purged).

lemma *vpeq-ns-nt-not-ifp-u*:**assumes** *purged-a-a2*: *purged-relation* u *execs* *execs2***and** *prec-s*: *precondition* (*next-state* s *execs*) (*next-action* s *execs*)**and** *current-s-t*: $\text{current } s = \text{current } t'$ **and** *vpeq-s-t*: $\forall v . \text{ifp}^{**} v u \longrightarrow \text{vpeq } v s t'$ **shows** $\neg \text{ifp}^{**} (\text{current } s) u \wedge \text{precondition}$ (*next-state* t' *execs2*) (*next-action* t' *execs2*) $\longrightarrow (\forall v . \text{ifp}^{**} v u \longrightarrow \text{vpeq } v (\text{step } (\text{next-state } s \text{ execs}) (\text{next-action } s \text{ execs})) (\text{step } (\text{next-state } t' \text{ execs2}) (\text{next-action } t' \text{ execs2})))$ **proof**–

{

assume *not-ifp*: $\neg \text{ifp}^{**} (\text{current } s) u$ **assume** *prec-t*: *precondition* (*next-state* t' *execs2*) (*next-action* t' *execs2*)**fix** $a' v$ **assume** *ifp-v-u*: $\text{ifp}^{**} v u$ **from** *not-ifp* **and** *purged-a-a2* **have** $\neg \text{ifp}^{**} (\text{current } s) u$ **unfolding** *purged-relation-def* **by** *auto***from** *this* **and** *ifp-v-u* **have** *not-ifp-curr-v*: $\neg \text{ifp}^{**} (\text{current } s) v$ **using** *rtranclp-trans* **by** *metis***from** *this* *current-next-state*[*THEN spec, THEN spec, where* $x1=s$ **and** $x=\text{execs}$] *prec-s* *vpeq-reflexive*

$$\text{locally-respects}[\text{THEN } \text{spec}, \text{THEN } \text{spec}, \text{THEN } \text{spec}, \text{where } x1=\text{next-state } s \text{ execs and } x2=\text{the } (\text{next-action } s \text{ execs}) \text{ and } x=v]$$
have $\text{vpeq } v (\text{next-state } s \text{ execs}) (\text{step } (\text{next-state } s \text{ execs}) (\text{next-action } s \text{ execs}))$ **unfolding** *step-def precondition-def B-def***by** (*cases next-action s execs, auto*)**from** *not-ifp-curr-v* *this* *locally-respects-next-state* *vpeq-transitive***have** *vpeq-s-ns*: $\text{vpeq } v s (\text{step } (\text{next-state } s \text{ execs}) (\text{next-action } s \text{ execs}))$ **by** *blast***from** *not-ifp-curr-v* *current-s-t* *current-next-state*[*THEN spec, THEN spec, where* $x1=t'$ **and** $x=\text{execs2}$] *prec-t**locally-respects*[*THEN spec, THEN spec, where* $x=\text{next-state } t' \text{ execs2}$] *vpeq-reflexive***have** 0 : $\text{vpeq } v (\text{next-state } t' \text{ execs2}) (\text{step } (\text{next-state } t' \text{ execs2}) (\text{next-action } t' \text{ execs2}))$ **unfolding** *step-def precondition-def B-def***by** (*cases next-action t' execs2, auto*)**from** *not-ifp-curr-v* *current-s-t* *current-next-state* **have** 1 : $\neg \text{ifp}^{**} (\text{current } t') v$

```

using rtranclp-trans by auto
from 0 1 locally-respects-next-state vpeq-transitive
  have vpeq-t-nt: vpeq v t' (step (next-state t' execs2) (next-action t' execs2))
  by blast
from vpeq-s-ns and vpeq-t-nt and vpeq-s-t and ifp-v-u and vpeq-symmetric and vpeq-transitive
  have vpeq-ns-nt: vpeq v (step (next-state s execs) (next-action s execs)) (step (next-state t' execs2) (next-action
t' execs2))
  by blast
}
thus ?thesis by auto
qed

```

A run with a purged list of actions appears identical to a run without purging, when starting from two states that appear identical.

lemma *unwinding-implies-view-partitioned-ind*:

shows *view-partitioned-ind*

proof–

```

{
  fix execs execs2 s t n u
  have equivalent-states s t u  $\wedge$  purged-relation u execs execs2  $\longrightarrow$  equivalent-states (run n s execs) (run n t
execs2) u
  proof (induct n s execs arbitrary: t u execs2 rule: run.induct)
  case (1 s execs t u execs2)
    show ?case by auto
  next
  case (2 n execs t u execs2)
    show ?case by simp
  next
  case (3 n s execs t u execs2)
  assume interrupt-s: interrupt (Suc n)
  assume IH: ( $\wedge$  t u execs2.
    equivalent-states (Some (cswitch (Suc n) s)) t u  $\wedge$  purged-relation u execs execs2  $\longrightarrow$ 
    equivalent-states (run n (Some (cswitch (Suc n) s)) execs) (run n t execs2) u)
  {
    fix t'
    assume t = Some t'
    fix rs
    assume rs: run (Suc n) (Some s) execs = Some rs
    fix rt
    assume rt: run (Suc n) (Some t') execs2 = Some rt

    assume vpeq-s-t:  $\forall v . \text{ifp}^{**} v u \longrightarrow \text{vpeq } v s t'$ 
    assume current-s-t: current s = current t'
    assume purged-a-a2: purged-relation u execs execs2

```

— The following terminology is used: states rs and rt (for: run-s and run-t) are the states after a run. States ns and nt (for: next-s and next-t) are the states after one step.

— We prove two properties: the states rs and rt have equal active domains (current-rs-rt) and are vpeq for all domains v that may influence u (vpeq-rs-rt). Both are proven using the IH. To use the IH, we have to prove that the properties hold for the next step (in this case, a context switch). Statement current-ns-nt states that after one step states ns and nt have the same active domain. Statement vpeq-ns-nt states that after one step states ns and nt are vpeq for all domains v that may influence u (vpeq-rs-rt).

```

from current-s-t cswitch-independent-of-state
  have current-ns-nt: current (cswitch (Suc n) s) = current (cswitch (Suc n) t') by blast
from cswitch-consistency vpeq-s-t
  have vpeq-ns-nt:  $\forall v . \text{ifp}^{**} v u \longrightarrow \text{vpeq } v (\text{cswitch } (Suc n) s) (\text{cswitch } (Suc n) t')$  by auto
from current-ns-nt vpeq-ns-nt interrupt-s vpeq-reflexive purged-a-a2 current-s-t IH[where u=u and t=Some
(cswitch (Suc n) t') and ?execs2.0=execs2]

```

```

have current-rs-rt: current rs = current rt using rs rt by(auto)
{
  fix v
  assume ia: ifp*** v u
  from current-ns-nt vpeq-ns-nt ia interrupt-s vpeq-reflexive purged-a-a2 IH[where u=u and t=Some (cswitch
(Suc n) t') and ?execs2.0=execs2]
  have vpeq-rs-rt: vpeq v rs rt using rs rt by(auto)
}
from current-rs-rt and this have equivalent-states (Some rs) (Some rt) u by auto
}
thus ?case by(simp add:option.splits,cases t,simp+)
next
case (4 n execs s t u execs2)
assume not-interrupt: ¬interrupt (Suc n)
assume thread-empty-s: thread-empty(execs (current s))
assume IH: ( $\wedge t u \text{ execs2. equivalent-states (Some s) t u \wedge \text{purged-relation } u \text{ execs execs2} \longrightarrow \text{equivalent-states}$ 
(run n (Some s) execs) (run n t execs2) u)
{
  fix t'
  assume t: t = Some t'
  fix rs
  assume rs: run (Suc n) (Some s) execs = Some rs
  fix rt
  assume rt: run (Suc n) (Some t') execs2 = Some rt

  assume vpeq-s-t:  $\forall v. \text{ifp}^{\text{***}} v u \longrightarrow \text{vpeq } v s t'$ 
  assume current-s-t: current s = current t'
  assume purged-a-a2: purged-relation u execs execs2

```

— The following terminology is used: states *rs* and *rt* (for: run-s and run-t) are the states after a run. States *ns* and *nt* (for: next-s and next-t) are the states after one step.

— We prove two properties: the states *rs* and *rt* have equal active domains (*current-rs-rt*) and are *vpeq* for all domains *v* that may influence *u* (*vpeq-rs-rt*). Both are proven using the *IH*. To use the *IH*, we have to prove that the properties hold for the next step (in this case, nothing happens in *s* as the thread is empty). Statement *current-ns-nt* states that after one step states *ns* and *nt* have the same active domain. Statement *vpeq_ns_nt* states that after one step states *ns* and *nt* are *vpeq* for all domains *v* that may influence *u* (*vpeq-rs-rt*).

```

from ifp-reflexive and vpeq-s-t have vpeq-s-t-u: vpeq u s t' by auto
  from thread-empty-s and purged-a-a2 and current-s-t have purged-a-na2: ¬ifp*** (current t') u  $\longrightarrow$ 
purged-relation u execs (next-exec t' execs2)
  by(unfold next-exec-def,unfold purged-relation-def,auto)
  from step-atomicity current-next-state current-s-t have current-s-nt: current s = current (step (next-state t'
execs2) (next-action t' execs2))
  unfolding step-def
  by (cases next-action t' execs2,auto)

```

— The proof is by case distinction. If the current thread is empty in state *t* as well (case *t-empty*), then nothing happens and the proof is trivial. Otherwise (case *t-not-empty*), since the current thread has different executions in states *s* and *t*, we now show that it cannot influence *u* (statement *not-ifp-curr-t*). If in state *t* the precondition holds (case *t-prec*), locally respects shows that the states remain *vpeq*. Otherwise, (case *t-not-prec*), everything holds vacuously.

```

have current-rs-rt: current rs = current rt
proof (cases thread-empty(execs2 (current t')) rule :case-split[case-names t-empty t-not-empty])
case t-empty
  from purged-a-a2 and vpeq-s-t and current-s-t IH[where t=Some t' and u=u and ?execs2.0=execs2]
  have equivalent-states (run n (Some s) execs) (run n (Some t') execs2) u using rs rt by(auto)
  from this not-interrupt t-empty thread-empty-s

```

```

    show ?thesis using rs rt by(auto)
next
case t-not-empty
from t-not-empty current-next-state and vpeq-s-t-u and thread-empty-s and purged-a-a2 and current-s-t
have not-ifp-curr-t:  $\neg \text{ifp}^{**} (\text{current} (\text{next-state } t' \text{ execs2})) u$  unfolding purged-relation-def by auto
show ?thesis
proof (cases precondition (next-state t' execs2) (next-action t' execs2) rule :case-split[case-names t-prec
t-not-prec])
case t-prec
from locally-respects-next-state current-next-state t-prec not-ifp-curr-t vpeq-s-t locally-respects vpeq-s-nt
have vpeq-s-nt:  $(\forall v . \text{ifp}^{**} v u \longrightarrow \text{vpeq } v \text{ s } (\text{step} (\text{next-state } t' \text{ execs2}) (\text{next-action } t' \text{ execs2})))$  by auto
from vpeq-s-nt purged-a-na2 this current-s-nt not-ifp-curr-t current-next-state
IH[where t=Some (step (next-state t' execs2) (next-action t' execs2)) and u=u and ?execs2.0=next-exec
t' execs2]
have equivalent-states (run n (Some s) execs) (run n (Some (step (next-state t' execs2) (next-action t'
execs2)))) (next-exec t' execs2)) u
using rs rt by auto
from t-not-empty t-prec vpeq-s-nt this thread-empty-s not-interrupt
show ?thesis using rs rt by auto
next
case t-not-prec
thus ?thesis using rt t-not-empty not-interrupt by(auto)
qed
qed
{
fix v
assume ia:  $\text{ifp}^{**} v u$ 
have vpeq v rs rt
proof (cases thread-empty(execs2 (current t')) rule :case-split[case-names t-empty t-not-empty])
case t-empty
from purged-a-a2 and vpeq-s-t and current-s-t IH[where t=Some t' and u=u and ?execs2.0=execs2]
have equivalent-states (run n (Some s) execs) (run n (Some t') execs2) u using rs rt by(auto)
from ia this not-interrupt t-empty thread-empty-s
show ?thesis using rs rt by(auto)
next
case t-not-empty
show ?thesis
proof (cases precondition (next-state t' execs2) (next-action t' execs2) rule :case-split[case-names t-prec
t-not-prec])
case t-prec
from t-not-empty current-next-state and vpeq-s-t-u and thread-empty-s and purged-a-a2 and current-s-t
have not-ifp-curr-t:  $\neg \text{ifp}^{**} (\text{current} (\text{next-state } t' \text{ execs2})) u$  unfolding purged-relation-def
by auto
from t-prec current-next-state locally-respects-next-state this and vpeq-s-t and locally-respects and
vpeq-s-nt
have vpeq-s-nt:  $(\forall v . \text{ifp}^{**} v u \longrightarrow \text{vpeq } v \text{ s } (\text{step} (\text{next-state } t' \text{ execs2}) (\text{next-action } t' \text{ execs2})))$  by
auto
from purged-a-na2 this current-s-nt not-ifp-curr-t current-next-state
IH[where t=Some (step (next-state t' execs2) (next-action t' execs2)) and u=u and ?execs2.0=next-exec
t' execs2]
have equivalent-states (run n (Some s) execs) (run n (Some (step (next-state t' execs2) (next-action t'
execs2)))) (next-exec t' execs2)) u
using rs rt by(auto)
from ia t-not-empty t-prec vpeq-s-nt this thread-empty-s not-interrupt
show ?thesis using rs rt by auto
next
case t-not-prec

```

```

    thus ?thesis using rt t-not-empty not-interrupt by(auto)
  qed
}
}
from current-rs-rt and this have equivalent-states (Some rs) (Some rt) u by auto
}
thus ?case by(simp add:option.splits,cases t,simp+)
next
case (5 n execs s t u execs2)
assume not-interrupt:  $\neg$ interrupt (Suc n)
assume thread-not-empty-s:  $\neg$ thread-empty(execs (current s))
assume not-prec-s:  $\neg$ precondition (next-state s execs) (next-action s execs)
— Whenever the precondition does not hold, the entire theorem flattens to True and everything holds vacuously.

```

```

hence run (Suc n) (Some s) execs = None using not-interrupt thread-not-empty-s by simp
thus ?case by(simp add:option.splits)
next
case (6 n execs s t u execs2)
assume not-interrupt:  $\neg$ interrupt (Suc n)
assume thread-not-empty-s:  $\neg$ thread-empty(execs (current s))
assume prec-s: precondition (next-state s execs) (next-action s execs)
assume IH:  $(\bigwedge t u \text{ execs2.}$ 
  equivalent-states (Some (step (next-state s execs) (next-action s execs))) t u  $\wedge$ 
  purged-relation u (next-exec s execs) execs2  $\longrightarrow$ 
  equivalent-states
  (run n (Some (step (next-state s execs) (next-action s execs))) (next-exec s execs))
  (run n t execs2) u)
{
  fix t'
  assume t: t = Some t'
  fix rs
  assume rs: run (Suc n) (Some s) execs = Some rs
  fix rt
  assume rt: run (Suc n) (Some t') execs2 = Some rt

  assume vpeq-s-t:  $\forall v . \text{ifp}^{**} v u \longrightarrow \text{vpeq } v s t'$ 
  assume current-s-t: current s = current t'
  assume purged-a-a2: purged-relation u execs execs2

```

— The following terminology is used: states rs and rt (for: run-s and run-t) are the states after a run. States ns and nt (for: next-s and next-t) are the states after one step.

— We prove two properties: the states rs and rt have equal active domains (current-rs-rt) and are vpeq for all domains v that may influence u (vpeq-rs-rt). Both are proven using the IH. To use the IH, we have to prove that the properties hold for the next step (in this case, state s executes an action). Statement current-ns-nt states that after one step states ns and nt have the same active domain. Statement vpeq-ns-nt states that after one step states ns and nt are vpeq for all domains v that may influence u (vpeq-rs-rt).

— Some lemma's used in the remainder of this case.

```

from ifp-reflexive and vpeq-s-t have vpeq-s-t-u: vpeq u s t' by auto
from step-atomicity and current-s-t current-next-state
  have current-ns-nt: current (step (next-state s execs) (next-action s execs)) = current (step (next-state t'
  execs2) (next-action t' execs2))
  unfolding step-def
  by (cases next-action s execs,cases next-action t' execs2,simp,simp,cases next-action t' execs2,simp,simp)
from vpeq-s-t have vpeq-curr-s-t:  $\text{ifp}^{**} (\text{current } s) u \longrightarrow \text{vpeq } (\text{current } s) s t'$  by auto
from prec-s involved-ifp[THEN spec,THEN spec,where x1=next-state s execs and x=next-action s execs]
  vpeq-s-t have vpeq-involved:  $\text{ifp}^{**} (\text{current } s) u \longrightarrow (\forall d \in \text{involved } (\text{next-action } s \text{ execs}) . \text{vpeq } d s t')$ 

```

```

using current-next-state
unfolding involved-def precondition-def B-def
by(cases next-action s execs,simp,auto,metis converse-rtranclp-into-rtranclp)
from current-s-t next-execs-consistent vpeq-curr-s-t vpeq-involved
have next-execs-t: ifp*** (current s) u  $\longrightarrow$  next-execs t' execs = next-execs s execs
unfolding next-execs-def
by(auto)
from current-s-t purged-a-a2 thread-not-empty-s next-action-consistent[THEN spec,THEN spec,where x1=s
and x=t'] vpeq-curr-s-t vpeq-involved
have next-action-s-t: ifp*** (current s) u  $\longrightarrow$  next-action t' execs2 = next-action s execs
by(unfold next-action-def,unfold purged-relation-def,auto)
from purged-a-a2 current-s-t next-execs-consistent[THEN spec,THEN spec,THEN spec,where x2=s and x1=t'
and x=execs]
  vpeq-curr-s-t vpeq-involved
have purged-na-na2: purged-relation u (next-execs s execs) (next-execs t' execs2)
unfolding next-execs-def purged-relation-def
by(auto)
from purged-a-a2 and purged-relation-def and thread-not-empty-s and current-s-t have thread-not-empty-t:
ifp*** (current s) u  $\longrightarrow$   $\neg$ thread-empty(execs2 (current t')) by auto
from step-atomicity current-s-t current-next-state have current-ns-t: current (step (next-state s execs) (next-action
s execs)) = current t'
unfolding step-def
by (cases next-action s execs,auto)
from step-atomicity and current-s-t have current-s-nt: current s = current (step t' (next-action t' execs2))
unfolding step-def
by (cases next-action t' execs2,auto)
from purged-a-a2 have purged-na-a:  $\neg$ ifp*** (current s) u  $\longrightarrow$  purged-relation u (next-execs s execs) execs2
by(unfold next-execs-def,unfold purged-relation-def,auto)

```

— The proof is by case distinction. If the current domain can interact with u (case curr-ifp-u), then either in state t the precondition holds (case t-prec) or not. If it holds, then lemma vpeq-ns-nt-ifp-u applies. Otherwise, the proof is trivial as the theorem holds vacuously. If the domain cannot interact with u , (case curr-not-ifp-u), then lemma $\text{vpeq-ns-nt-not-ifp-u}$ applies.

```

have current-rs-rt: current rs = current rt
proof (cases ifp*** (current s) u rule :case-split[case-names curr-ifp-u curr-not-ifp-u])
case curr-ifp-u
show ?thesis
proof (cases precondition (next-state t' execs2) (next-action t' execs2) rule :case-split[case-names prec-t
prec-not-t])
case prec-t
have thread-not-empty-t:  $\neg$ thread-empty(execs2 (current t')) using thread-not-empty-t curr-ifp-u by auto
from
  current-ns-nt next-execs-t next-action-s-t purged-a-a2
  curr-ifp-u prec-t prec-s vpeq-ns-nt-ifp-u[where a=(next-action s execs)] vpeq-s-t current-s-t
have equivalent-states (Some (step (next-state s execs) (next-action s execs))) (Some (step (next-state t'
execs2) (next-action t' execs2))) u
unfolding purged-relation-def next-state-def
by auto
from this
  IH[where u=u and ?execs2.0=(next-execs t' execs2) and t=Some (step (next-state t' execs2) (next-action
t' execs2))]
  current-ns-nt purged-na-na2
have equivalent-states (run n (Some (step (next-state s execs) (next-action s execs))) (next-execs s execs))
  (run n (Some (step (next-state t' execs2) (next-action t' execs2))) (next-execs t' execs2)) u
by auto
from prec-t thread-not-empty-t prec-s and this and not-interrupt and thread-not-empty-s and next-action-s-t
show ?thesis using rs rt by auto

```

```

next
case prec-not-t
  from curr-ifp-u prec-not-t thread-not-empty-t not-interrupt show ?thesis using rt by simp
qed
next
case curr-not-ifp-u
  show ?thesis
  proof (cases thread-empty(execs2 (current t'))) rule :case-split[case-names t-empty t-not-empty]
  case t-not-empty
    show ?thesis
    proof (cases precondition (next-state t' execs2) (next-action t' execs2) rule :case-split[case-names t-prec
t-not-prec])
      case t-prec
        from curr-not-ifp-u t-prec IH[where u=u and ?execs2.0=(next-execs t' execs2) and t=Some (step
(next-state t' execs2) (next-action t' execs2))]
          current-ns-nt next-execs-t purged-na-na2 vpeq-ns-nt-not-ifp-u current-s-t vpeq-s-t prec-s purged-a-a2
          have equivalent-states (run n (Some (step (next-state s execs) (next-action s execs))) (next-execs s
execs))
            (run n (Some (step (next-state t' execs2) (next-action t' execs2))) (next-execs t' execs2))
u by auto
  from this t-prec curr-not-ifp-u t-not-empty prec-s not-interrupt thread-not-empty-s show ?thesis using rs
rt by auto
  next
  case t-not-prec
    from t-not-prec t-not-empty not-interrupt show ?thesis using rt by simp
  qed
next
case t-empty
  from curr-not-ifp-u and prec-s and vpeq-s-t and locally-respects and vpeq-ns-t current-next-state
locally-respects-next-state
  have vpeq-ns-t: ( $\forall v . \text{ifp}^{**} v u \longrightarrow \text{vpeq } v (\text{step } (\text{next-state } s \text{ execs}) (\text{next-action } s \text{ execs})) t'$ )
  by blast
  from curr-not-ifp-u IH[where t=Some t' and u=u and ?execs2.0=execs2] and current-ns-t and next-execs-t
and purged-na-a and vpeq-ns-t and this
  have equivalent-states (run n (Some (step (next-state s execs) (next-action s execs))) (next-execs s execs))
    (run n (Some t') execs2) u by auto
  from this not-interrupt thread-not-empty-s t-empty prec-s show ?thesis using rs rt by auto
qed
qed
{
  fix v
  assume ia:  $\text{ifp}^{**} v u$ 

  have vpeq v rs rt
  proof (cases  $\text{ifp}^{**} (\text{current } s) u$  rule :case-split[case-names curr-ifp-u curr-not-ifp-u])
  case curr-ifp-u
  show ?thesis
  proof (cases precondition (next-state t' execs2) (next-action t' execs2) rule :case-split[case-names t-prec
t-not-prec])
  case t-prec
    have thread-not-empty-t:  $\neg \text{thread-empty}(\text{execs2 } (\text{current } t'))$  using thread-not-empty-t curr-ifp-u by auto
    from
      current-ns-nt next-execs-t next-action-s-t purged-a-a2
      curr-ifp-u t-prec prec-s vpeq-ns-nt-not-ifp-u[where a=(next-action s execs)] vpeq-s-t current-s-t
    have equivalent-states (Some (step (next-state s execs) (next-action s execs))) (Some (step (next-state t'
execs2) (next-action t' execs2))) u

```

```

unfolding purged-relation-def next-state-def
by auto
from this
  IH[where  $u=u$  and  $?execs2.0=(next-exec\ t' execs2)$  and  $t=Some\ (step\ (next-state\ t' execs2)\ (next-action\ t' execs2))$ ]]
  current-ns-nt purged-na-na2
  have equivalent-states ( $run\ n\ (Some\ (step\ (next-state\ s\ execs)\ (next-action\ s\ execs)))\ (next-exec\ s\ execs)$ )
    ( $run\ n\ (Some\ (step\ (next-state\ t' execs2)\ (next-action\ t' execs2)))\ (next-exec\ t' execs2)$ )  $u$ 
  by auto
  from ia curr-ifp-u t-prec thread-not-empty-t prec-s and this and not-interrupt and thread-not-empty-s
and next-action-s-t
  show ?thesis using rs rt by auto
  next
  case t-not-prec
  from curr-ifp-u t-not-prec thread-not-empty-t not-interrupt show ?thesis using rt by simp
  qed
  next
  case curr-not-ifp-u
  show ?thesis
  proof (cases thread-empty(execs2 (current t')) rule :case-split[case-names t-empty t-not-empty])
  case t-not-empty
  show ?thesis
  proof (cases precondition (next-state t' execs2) (next-action t' execs2) rule :case-split[case-names t-prec t-not-prec])
  case t-prec
  from curr-not-ifp-u t-prec IH[where u=u and ?execs2.0=(next-exec\ t' execs2) and t=Some (step (next-state t' execs2) (next-action t' execs2))]
  current-ns-nt next-exec\ t purged-na-na2 vpeq-ns-nt-not-ifp-u current-s-t vpeq-s-t prec-s purged-a-a2
  have equivalent-states ( $run\ n\ (Some\ (step\ (next-state\ s\ execs)\ (next-action\ s\ execs)))\ (next-exec\ s\ execs)$ )
    ( $run\ n\ (Some\ (step\ (next-state\ t' execs2)\ (next-action\ t' execs2)))\ (next-exec\ t' execs2)$ )
   $u$  by auto
  from ia this t-prec curr-not-ifp-u t-not-empty prec-s not-interrupt thread-not-empty-s show ?thesis using
  rs rt by auto
  next
  case t-not-prec
  from t-not-prec t-not-empty not-interrupt show ?thesis using rt by simp
  qed
  next
  case t-empty
  from curr-not-ifp-u prec-s and vpeq-s-t and locally-respects and vpeq-ns-t current-next-state locally-respects-next-state
  have  $vpeq-ns-t: (\forall v. ifp^{**}\ v\ u \longrightarrow vpeq\ v\ (step\ (next-state\ s\ execs)\ (next-action\ s\ execs))\ t')$ 
  by blast
  from curr-not-ifp-u IH[where t=Some t' and u=u and ?execs2.0=execs2] and current-ns-t and next-exec\ t
and purged-na-a and vpeq-ns-t and this
  have equivalent-states ( $run\ n\ (Some\ (step\ (next-state\ s\ execs)\ (next-action\ s\ execs)))\ (next-exec\ s\ execs)$ )
    ( $run\ n\ (Some\ t'\ execs2)\ u$ ) by auto
  from ia this not-interrupt thread-not-empty-s t-empty prec-s show ?thesis using rs rt by auto
  qed
  qed
}
from current-rs-rt and this have equivalent-states (Some rs) (Some rt) u by auto
}
thus ?case by (simp add:option.splits,cases t,simp+)
qed

```

```

}
thus ?thesis
  unfolding view-partitioned-ind-def by auto
qed

```

From the previous lemma, we can prove that the system is view partitioned. The previous lemma was inductive, this lemma just instantiates the previous lemma replacing s and t by the initial state.

```

lemma unwinding-implies-view-partitioned:
shows view-partitioned
proof-
from assms unwinding-implies-view-partitioned-ind have view-partitioned-inductive: view-partitioned-ind
  by blast
have purged-relation:  $\forall u \text{ execs } . \text{purged-relation } u \text{ execs } (\text{purge } \text{execs } u)$ 
  by(unfold purged-relation-def, unfold purge-def, auto)
{
  fix execs s t n u
  assume I: equivalent-states s t u
  from this view-partitioned-inductive purged-relation
  have equivalent-states (run n s execs) (run n t (purge execs u)) u
  unfolding view-partitioned-ind-def by auto
  from this ifp-reflexive
  have run n s execs  $\parallel$  run n t (purge execs u)  $\rightarrow$  ( $\lambda rs \text{ rt. vpeq } u \text{ rs } \text{rt} \wedge \text{current } \text{rs} = \text{current } \text{rt}$ )
  using r-into-rtranclp unfolding B-def
  by(cases run n s execs,simp,cases run n t (purge execs u),simp,auto)
}
thus ?thesis unfolding view-partitioned-def Let-def by auto
qed

```

Domains that many not interfere with each other, do not interfere with each other.

```

theorem unwinding-implies-NI-unrelated:
shows NI-unrelated
proof-
{
  fix execs a n
  from assms unwinding-implies-view-partitioned
  have vp: view-partitioned by blast
  from vp and vpeq-reflexive
  have I:  $\forall u . (\text{run } n \text{ (Some } s0) \text{ execs}$ 
     $\parallel$  run n (Some } s0) (purge execs u)
     $\rightarrow$  ( $\lambda rs \text{ rt. vpeq } u \text{ rs } \text{rt} \wedge \text{current } \text{rs} = \text{current } \text{rt}$ ))
  unfolding view-partitioned-def by auto
  have run n (Some } s0) execs  $\rightarrow$  ( $\lambda s\text{-f. run } n \text{ (Some } s0) (\text{purge } \text{execs } (\text{current } s\text{-f}))$ )  $\rightarrow$  ( $\lambda s\text{-f2. output-f } s\text{-f } a =$ 
output-f } s\text{-f2 } a \wedge \text{current } s\text{-f} = \text{current } s\text{-f2})
  proof(cases run n (Some } s0) execs)
  case None
  thus ?thesis unfolding B-def by simp
  next
  case (Some rs)
  thus ?thesis
  proof(cases run n (Some } s0) (purge execs (current rs)))
  case None
  from Some this show ?thesis unfolding B-def by simp
  next
  case (Some rt)
  from (run n (Some } s0) execs = Some rs) Some I[THEN spec,where x=current rs]
  have vpeq: vpeq (current rs) rs rt  $\wedge$  current rs = current rt
  unfolding B-def by auto
  from this output-consistent have output-f rs a = output-f rt a

```

```

    by auto
  from this vpeq (run n (Some s0) execs = Some rs) Some
  show ?thesis unfolding B-def by auto
qed
qed
}
thus ?thesis unfolding NI-unrelated-def by auto
qed

```

2.2.2 Security for indirectly interfering domains

Consider the following security policy over three domains A , B and C : $A \rightsquigarrow B \rightsquigarrow C$, but $A \not\rightsquigarrow C$. The semantics of this policy is that A may communicate with C , but *only* via B . No direct communication from A to C is allowed. We formalize these semantics as follows: without intermediate domain B , domain A cannot flow information to C . In other words, from the point of view of domain C the run where domain B is inactive must be equivalent to the run where domain B is inactive and domain A is replaced by an attacker. Domain C must be independent of domain A , when domain B is inactive.

The aim of this subsection is to formalize the semantics where A can write to C via B *only*. We define to two ipurge functions. The first purges all domains d that are *intermediary* for some other domain v . An intermediary for u is defined as a domain d for which there exists an information flow from some domain v to u via d , but no direct information flow from v to u is allowed.

definition *intermediary* :: 'dom-t ⇒ 'dom-t ⇒ bool
where *intermediary* $d\ u \equiv \exists v . \text{ifp}^{**} v\ d \wedge \text{ifp}\ d\ u \wedge \neg \text{ifp}\ v\ u \wedge d \neq u$
primrec *remove-gateway-communications* :: 'dom-t ⇒ 'action-t execution ⇒ 'action-t execution
where *remove-gateway-communications* $u\ [] = []$
 $| \text{remove-gateway-communications}\ u\ (\text{aseq}\#\text{exec}) = (\text{if}\ \exists a \in \text{set}\ \text{aseq} . \exists v . \text{intermediary}\ v\ u \wedge v \in \text{involved}\ (\text{Some}\ a)\ \text{then}\ []\ \text{else}\ \text{aseq})\#\text{(remove-gateway-communications}\ u\ \text{exec})$

definition *ipurge-l* ::
('dom-t ⇒ 'action-t execution) ⇒ 'dom-t ⇒ ('dom-t ⇒ 'action-t execution) **where**
ipurge-l $\text{execs}\ u \equiv \lambda d . \text{if}\ \text{intermediary}\ d\ u\ \text{then}$
 $\quad []$
 $\quad \text{else if}\ d = u\ \text{then}$
 $\quad \quad \text{remove-gateway-communications}\ u\ (\text{execs}\ u)$
 $\quad \text{else}\ \text{execs}\ d$

The second ipurge removes both the intermediaries and the *indirect sources*. An indirect source for u is defined as a domain that may indirectly flow information to u , but not directly.

abbreviation *ind-source* :: 'dom-t ⇒ 'dom-t ⇒ bool
where *ind-source* $d\ u \equiv \text{ifp}^{**} d\ u \wedge \neg \text{ifp}\ d\ u$
definition *ipurge-r* ::
('dom-t ⇒ 'action-t execution) ⇒ 'dom-t ⇒ ('dom-t ⇒ 'action-t execution) **where**
ipurge-r $\text{execs}\ u \equiv \lambda d . \text{if}\ \text{intermediary}\ d\ u\ \text{then}$
 $\quad []$
 $\quad \text{else if}\ \text{ind-source}\ d\ u\ \text{then}$
 $\quad \quad \text{SOME}\ \alpha . \text{realistic-execution}\ \alpha$
 $\quad \text{else if}\ d = u\ \text{then}$
 $\quad \quad \text{remove-gateway-communications}\ u\ (\text{execs}\ u)$
 $\quad \text{else}$
 $\quad \quad \text{execs}\ d$

For a system with an intransitive policy to be called secure for domain u any indirect source may not flow information towards u when the intermediaries are purged out. This definition of security allows the information flow $A \rightsquigarrow B \rightsquigarrow C$, but prohibits $A \rightsquigarrow C$.

definition *NI-indirect-sources* :: bool

where *NI-indirect-sources*

$$\equiv \forall \text{ execs } a \ n. \text{ run } n \ (\text{Some } s0) \ \text{execs} \rightarrow$$

$$(\lambda \ s\ f. (\text{run } n \ (\text{Some } s0) \ (\text{ipurge-l } \text{execs} \ (\text{current } s\ f))) \parallel$$

$$\text{run } n \ (\text{Some } s0) \ (\text{ipurge-r } \text{execs} \ (\text{current } s\ f)) \rightarrow$$

$$(\lambda \ s\ l \ s\ r. \text{output-f } s\ l \ a = \text{output-f } s\ r \ a))$$

This definition concerns indirect sources only. It does not enforce that an *unrelated* domain may not flow information to *u*. This is expressed by “secure”.

This allows us to define security over intransitive policies.

definition *isecure::bool*

where *isecure* \equiv *NI-indirect-sources* \wedge *NI-unrelated*

abbreviation *iequivalent-states* $::$ *'state-t option* \Rightarrow *'state-t option* \Rightarrow *'dom-t* \Rightarrow *bool*

where *iequivalent-states* *s t u* \equiv *s* \parallel *t* \rightarrow $(\lambda \ s \ t. (\forall \ v. \text{ifp } v \ u \wedge \neg \text{intermediary } v \ u \rightarrow \text{vpeq } v \ s \ t) \wedge \text{current } s = \text{current } t)$

definition *does-not-communicate-with-gateway*

where *does-not-communicate-with-gateway* *u execs* \equiv $\forall \ a. a \in \text{actions-in-execution } (\text{execs } u) \rightarrow (\forall \ v. \text{intermediary } v \ u \rightarrow v \notin \text{involved } (\text{Some } a))$

definition *iview-partitioned::bool* **where** *iview-partitioned*

$$\equiv \forall \ \text{execs } ms \ mt \ n \ u. \ \text{iequivalent-states } ms \ mt \ u \rightarrow$$

$$(\text{run } n \ ms \ (\text{ipurge-l } \text{execs } u) \parallel$$

$$\text{run } n \ mt \ (\text{ipurge-r } \text{execs } u) \rightarrow$$

$$(\lambda \ rs \ rt. \text{vpeq } u \ rs \ rt \wedge \text{current } rs = \text{current } rt))$$

definition *ipurged-relation1* $::$ *'dom-t* \Rightarrow $(\text{'dom-t} \Rightarrow \text{'action-t execution}) \Rightarrow (\text{'dom-t} \Rightarrow \text{'action-t execution}) \Rightarrow$ *bool*

where *ipurged-relation1* *u execs1 execs2* \equiv $\forall \ d. (\text{ifp } d \ u \rightarrow \text{execs1 } d = \text{execs2 } d) \wedge (\text{intermediary } d \ u \rightarrow \text{execs1 } d = [])$

Proof that if the current is not an intermediary for *u*, then all domains involved in the next action are *vpeq*.

lemma *vpeq-involved-domains*:

assumes *ifp-curr*: *ifp* *(current s) u*

and *not-intermediary-curr*: $\neg \text{intermediary } (\text{current } s) \ u$

and *no-gateway-comm*: *does-not-communicate-with-gateway* *u execs*

and *vpeq-s-t*: $\forall \ v. \text{ifp } v \ u \wedge \neg \text{intermediary } v \ u \rightarrow \text{vpeq } v \ s \ t'$

and *prec-s*: *precondition* *(next-state s execs) (next-action s execs)*

shows $\forall \ d \in \text{involved } (\text{next-action } s \ \text{execs}). \ \text{vpeq } d \ s \ t'$

proof-

{

fix *v*

assume *involved*: *v* \in *involved* *(next-action s execs)*

from *this prec-s involved-ifp* [*THEN spec, THEN spec, where* *x1=next-state s execs* **and** *x=next-action s execs*]

have *ifp-v-curr*: *ifp* *v (current s)*

using *current-next-state*

unfolding *involved-def precondition-def B-def*

by *(cases next-action s execs, auto)*

have *vpeq v s t'*

proof-

{

assume *ifp v u* \wedge $\neg \text{intermediary } v \ u$

from *this vpeq-s-t*

have *vpeq v s t'* **by** *(auto)*

}

moreover

```

{
  assume not-intermediary-v: intermediary v u
  from ifp-curr not-intermediary-curr ifp-v-curr not-intermediary-v have curr-is-u: current s = u
  using rtranclp-trans r-into-rtranclp
  by (metis intermediary-def)
  from curr-is-u next-action-from-execs [THEN spec, THEN spec, where x=execs and x1=s] not-intermediary-v
  involved
  no-gateway-comm [unfolded does-not-communicate-with-gateway-def, THEN spec, where x=the (next-action
  s execs)]
  have False
  unfolding involved-def B-def
  by (cases next-action s execs, auto)
  hence vpeq v s t' by auto
}
moreover
{
  assume intermediary-v: ¬ ifp v u
  from ifp-curr not-intermediary-curr ifp-v-curr intermediary-v
  have False unfolding intermediary-def by auto
  hence vpeq v s t' by auto
}
ultimately
show vpeq v s t' unfolding intermediary-def by auto
qed
}
thus ?thesis by auto
qed

```

Proof that purging removes communications of the gateway to domain u .

lemma *ipurge-l-removes-gateway-communications*:

shows *does-not-communicate-with-gateway u (ipurge-l execs u)*

proof–

```

{
  fix aseq u execs a v
  assume 1: aseq ∈ set (remove-gateway-communications u (execs u))
  assume 2: a ∈ set aseq
  assume 3: intermediary v u
  have 4: v ∉ involved (Some a)
  proof–
  {
    fix a::'action-t
    fix aseq u exec v
    have aseq ∈ set (remove-gateway-communications u exec) ∧ a ∈ set aseq ∧ intermediary v u  $\longrightarrow$  v ∉ involved
    (Some a)
    by (induct exec, auto)
  }
  from 1 2 3 this show ?thesis by metis
  qed
}
from this
show ?thesis
unfolding does-not-communicate-with-gateway-def ipurge-l-def actions-in-execution-def
by auto
qed

```

Proof of view partitioning. The lemma is structured exactly as lemma `unwinding_implies_view_partitioned_ind` and uses the same convention for naming.

lemma *iunwinding-implies-view-partitioned1*:

shows *iview-partitioned*

proof–

```

{
  fix u execs execs2 s t n
  have does-not-communicate-with-gateway u execs  $\wedge$  iequivalent-states s t u  $\wedge$  ipurged-relation1 u execs execs2
 $\longrightarrow$  iequivalent-states (run n s execs) (run n t execs2) u
  proof (induct n s execs arbitrary: t u execs2 rule: run.induct)
  case (1 s execs t u execs2)
    show ?case by auto
  next
  case (2 n execs t u execs2)
    show ?case by simp
  next
  case (3 n s execs t u execs2)
    assume interrupt-s: interrupt (Suc n)
    assume IH: ( $\wedge t u execs2. \text{does-not-communicate-with-gateway } u \text{ execs} \wedge$ 
      iequivalent-states (Some (cswitch (Suc n) s)) t u  $\wedge$  ipurged-relation1 u execs execs2  $\longrightarrow$ 
      iequivalent-states (run n (Some (cswitch (Suc n) s)) execs) (run n t execs2) u)
    {
      fix t' :: 'state-t
      assume t = Some t'
      fix rs
      assume rs: run (Suc n) (Some s) execs = Some rs
      fix rt
      assume rt: run (Suc n) (Some t') execs2 = Some rt

      assume no-gateway-comm: does-not-communicate-with-gateway u execs
      assume vpeq-s-t:  $\forall v. \text{ifp } v \text{ u} \wedge \neg \text{intermediary } v \text{ u} \longrightarrow \text{vpeq } v \text{ s } t'$ 
      assume current-s-t: current s = current t'
      assume purged-a-a2: ipurged-relation1 u execs execs2

      from current-s-t cswitch-independent-of-state
      have current-ns-nt: current (cswitch (Suc n) s) = current (cswitch (Suc n) t')
      by blast
      from cswitch-consistency vpeq-s-t
      have vpeq-ns-nt:  $\forall v. \text{ifp } v \text{ u} \wedge \neg \text{intermediary } v \text{ u} \longrightarrow \text{vpeq } v \text{ (cswitch (Suc n) s) (cswitch (Suc n) t')}$ 
      by auto
      from no-gateway-comm current-ns-nt vpeq-ns-nt interrupt-s vpeq-reflexive current-s-t purged-a-a2 IH [where
u=u and t=Some (cswitch (Suc n) t') and ?execs2.0=execs2]
      have current-rs-rt: current rs = current rt using rs rt by(auto)
      {
        fix v
        assume ia: ifp v u  $\wedge$   $\neg$ intermediary v u
        from no-gateway-comm interrupt-s current-ns-nt vpeq-ns-nt vpeq-reflexive ia current-s-t purged-a-a2
IH [where u=u and t=Some (cswitch (Suc n) t') and ?execs2.0=execs2]
        have vpeq v rs rt using rs rt by(auto)
      }
      from current-rs-rt and this have iequivalent-states (Some rs) (Some rt) u by auto
    }
    thus ?case by(simp add:option.splits,cases t,simp+)
  next
  case (4 n execs s t u execs2)
    assume not-interrupt:  $\neg$ interrupt (Suc n)
    assume thread-empty-s: thread-empty(execs (current s))

    assume IH: ( $\wedge t u execs2. \text{does-not-communicate-with-gateway } u \text{ execs} \wedge \text{iequivalent-states (Some s) t u} \wedge$ 
      ipurged-relation1 u execs execs2  $\longrightarrow$  iequivalent-states (run n (Some s) execs) (run n t execs2) u)

```

```

{
  fix t'

  assume t: t = Some t'
  fix rs
  assume rs: run (Suc n) (Some s) execs = Some rs
  fix rt
  assume rt: run (Suc n) (Some t') execs2 = Some rt

  assume no-gateway-comm: does-not-communicate-with-gateway u execs
  assume vpeq-s-t:  $\forall v u . \text{ifp } v u \wedge \neg \text{intermediary } v u \longrightarrow \text{vpeq } v s t'$ 
  assume current-s-t: current s = current t'
  assume purged-a-a2: ipurged-relation1 u execs execs2

  from ifp-reflexive vpeq-s-t have vpeq-u-s-t: vpeq u s t' unfolding intermediary-def by auto
  from step-atomicity current-next-state current-s-t have current-s-nt: current s = current (step (next-state t'
execs2) (next-action t' execs2))
  unfolding step-def
  by (cases next-action s execs, cases next-action t' execs2, simp, simp, cases next-action t' execs2, simp, simp)
  from vpeq-s-t have vpeq-curr-s-t:  $\text{ifp } (\text{current } s) u \wedge \neg \text{intermediary } (\text{current } s) u \longrightarrow \text{vpeq } (\text{current } s) s t'$  by
auto
  have iequivalent-states (run (Suc n) (Some s) execs) (run (Suc n) (Some t') execs2) u
  proof(cases thread-empty(execs2 (current t')))
  case True
    from purged-a-a2 and vpeq-s-t and current-s-t IH[where t=Some t' and u=u and ?execs2.0=execs2]
no-gateway-comm
    have iequivalent-states (run n (Some s) execs) (run n (Some t') execs2) u using rs rt by(auto)
    from this not-interrupt True thread-empty-s
    show ?thesis using rs rt by(auto)
  next
  case False
  have prec-t: precondition (next-state t' execs2) (next-action t' execs2)
  proof-
  {
    assume not-prec-t:  $\neg \text{precondition } (\text{next-state } t' \text{ execs2}) (\text{next-action } t' \text{ execs2})$ 
    hence run (Suc n) (Some t') execs2 = None using not-interrupt False not-prec-t by (simp)
    from this have False using rt by(simp add:option.splits)
  }
  thus ?thesis by auto
  qed

  from False purged-a-a2 thread-empty-s current-s-t
  have l: ind-source (current t') u  $\vee$  unrelated (current t') u unfolding ipurged-relation1-def intermediary-def
by auto
  {
    fix v
    assume ifp-v:  $\text{ifp } v u$ 
    assume v-not-intermediary:  $\neg \text{intermediary } v u$ 

    from l ifp-v v-not-intermediary have not-ifp-curr-v:  $\neg \text{ifp } (\text{current } t') v$  unfolding intermediary-def by auto
    from not-ifp-curr-v prec-t locally-respects[THEN spec, THEN spec, THEN spec, where x1=next-state t'
execs2 and x=v and x2=the (next-action t' execs2)]
    current-next-state vpeq-reflexive
    have vpeq v (next-state t' execs2) (step (next-state t' execs2) (next-action t' execs2))
    unfolding step-def precondition-def B-def
    by (cases next-action t' execs2, auto)
    from this vpeq-transitive not-ifp-curr-v locally-respects-next-state

```

```

    have vpeq-t-nt: vpeq v t' (step (next-state t' execs2) (next-action t' execs2))
    by blast
  from vpeq-s-t ifp-v v-not-intermediary vpeq-t-nt vpeq-transitive vpeq-symmetric vpeq-reflexive
  have vpeq v s (step (next-state t' execs2) (next-action t' execs2))
  by (metis)
}
hence vpeq-ns-nt:  $\forall v . \text{ifp } v \ u \wedge \neg \text{intermediary } v \ u \longrightarrow \text{vpeq } v \ s \ (\text{step } (\text{next-state } t' \ \text{execs2}) \ (\text{next-action } t' \ \text{execs2}))$  by auto
from False purged-a-a2 current-s-t thread-empty-s have purged-a-na2: ipurged-relation1 u execs (next-exec
t' execs2)
  unfolding ipurged-relation1-def next-exec-def by(auto)
  from vpeq-ns-nt no-gateway-comm
  and IH[where t=Some (step (next-state t' execs2) (next-action t' execs2)) and ?execs2.0=(next-exec
execs2) and u=u]
  and current-s-nt purged-a-na2
  have eq-ns-nt: equivalent-states (run n (Some s) execs)
    (run n (Some (step (next-state t' execs2) (next-action t' execs2))) (next-exec
execs2)) u by auto
  from prec-t eq-ns-nt not-interrupt False thread-empty-s
  show ?thesis using t rs rt by(auto)
qed
}
thus ?case by(simp add:option.splits,cases t,simp+)
next
case (5 n execs s t u execs2)
  assume not-interrupt:  $\neg \text{interrupt } (\text{Suc } n)$ 
  assume thread-not-empty-s:  $\neg \text{thread-empty}(\text{execs } (\text{current } s))$ 
  assume not-prec-s:  $\neg \text{precondition } (\text{next-state } s \ \text{execs}) \ (\text{next-action } s \ \text{execs})$ 
  hence run (Suc n) (Some s) execs = None using not-interrupt thread-not-empty-s by simp
  thus ?case by(simp add:option.splits)
next
case (6 n execs s t u execs2)
  assume not-interrupt:  $\neg \text{interrupt } (\text{Suc } n)$ 
  assume thread-not-empty-s:  $\neg \text{thread-empty}(\text{execs } (\text{current } s))$ 
  assume prec-s: precondition (next-state s execs) (next-action s execs)
  assume IH:  $(\wedge t \ u \ \text{execs2} . \text{does-not-communicate-with-gateway } u \ (\text{next-exec } s \ \text{execs}) \wedge$ 
    equivalent-states (Some (step (next-state s execs) (next-action s execs))) t u  $\wedge$ 
    ipurged-relation1 u (next-exec s execs) execs2  $\longrightarrow$ 
    equivalent-states
    (run n (Some (step (next-state s execs) (next-action s execs))) (next-exec s execs))
    (run n t execs2) u)
  {
    fix t'
    assume t: t = Some t'
    fix rs
    assume rs: run (Suc n) (Some s) execs = Some rs
    fix rt
    assume rt: run (Suc n) (Some t') execs2 = Some rt

    assume no-gateway-comm: does-not-communicate-with-gateway u execs
    assume vpeq-s-t:  $\forall v . \text{ifp } v \ u \wedge \neg \text{intermediary } v \ u \longrightarrow \text{vpeq } v \ s \ t'$ 
    assume current-s-t: current s = current t'
    assume purged-a-a2: ipurged-relation1 u execs execs2

    from ifp-reflexive vpeq-s-t have vpeq-u-s-t: vpeq u s t' unfolding intermediary-def by auto
    from step-atomicity and current-s-t current-next-state
    have current-ns-nt: current (step (next-state s execs) (next-action s execs)) = current (step (next-state t'

```

```

execs2) (next-action t' execs2))
  unfolding step-def
  by (cases next-action s execs,cases next-action t' execs2,simp,simp,cases next-action t' execs2,simp,simp)

  from step-atomicity current-next-state current-s-t have current-ns-t: current (step (next-state s execs) (next-action
s execs)) = current t'
  unfolding step-def
  by (cases next-action s execs,auto)
  from vpeq-s-t have vpeq-curr-s-t: ifp (current s) u  $\wedge$   $\neg$ intermediary (current s) u  $\longrightarrow$  vpeq (current s) s t'
unfolding intermediary-def by auto
from current-s-t purged-a-a2
have eq-exec: ifp (current s) u  $\wedge$   $\neg$ intermediary (current s) u  $\longrightarrow$  execs (current s) = execs2 (current s)
by(auto simp add: ipurged-relation1-def)
from vpeq-involved-domains no-gateway-comm vpeq-s-t vpeq-involved-domains prec-s
have vpeq-involved: ifp (current s) u  $\wedge$   $\neg$ intermediary (current s) u  $\longrightarrow$  ( $\forall$  d  $\in$  involved (next-action s execs)
. vpeq d s t')
by blast
from current-s-t next-exec-consistent[THEN spec,THEN spec,THEN spec,where x2=s and x1=t' and x=execs]
vpeq-curr-s-t vpeq-involved
have next-exec-s-t: ifp (current s) u  $\wedge$   $\neg$ intermediary (current s) u  $\longrightarrow$  next-exec t' execs = next-exec s execs
by(auto simp add: next-exec-def)
from current-s-t and purged-a-a2 and thread-not-empty-s next-action-consistent[THEN spec,THEN spec,where
x1=s and x=t'] vpeq-curr-s-t vpeq-involved
have next-action-s-t: ifp (current s) u  $\wedge$   $\neg$ intermediary (current s) u  $\longrightarrow$  next-action t' execs2 = next-action s
execs
by(unfold next-action-def,unfold ipurged-relation1-def,auto)
from purged-a-a2 and thread-not-empty-s and current-s-t
have thread-not-empty-t: ifp (current s) u  $\wedge$   $\neg$ intermediary (current s) u  $\longrightarrow$   $\neg$ thread-empty(execs2 (current
t'))
unfolding ipurged-relation1-def by auto
have vpeq-ns-nt-1:  $\wedge$  a . precondition (next-state s execs) a  $\wedge$  precondition (next-state t' execs) a  $\implies$  ifp
(current s) u  $\wedge$   $\neg$ intermediary (current s) u  $\implies$  ( $\forall$  v . ifp v u  $\wedge$   $\neg$ intermediary v u  $\longrightarrow$  vpeq v (step (next-state s
execs) a) (step (next-state t' execs) a))
proof-
fix a
assume prec: precondition (next-state s execs) a  $\wedge$  precondition (next-state t' execs) a
assume ifp-curr: ifp (current s) u  $\wedge$   $\neg$ intermediary (current s) u
from ifp-curr prec
next-state-consistent[THEN spec,THEN spec,where x1=s and x=t'] vpeq-curr-s-t vpeq-s-t
current-next-state current-s-t weakly-step-consistent[THEN spec,THEN spec,THEN spec,THEN spec,where
x3=next-state s execs and x2=next-state t' execs and x=the a]
show  $\forall$  v . ifp v u  $\wedge$   $\neg$ intermediary v u  $\longrightarrow$  vpeq v (step (next-state s execs) a) (step (next-state t' execs) a)
unfolding step-def precondition-def B-def
by (cases a,auto)
qed
have no-gateway-comm-na: does-not-communicate-with-gateway u (next-exec s execs)
proof-
{
fix a
assume a  $\in$  actions-in-execution (next-exec s execs u)
from this no-gateway-comm[unfolded does-not-communicate-with-gateway-def,THEN spec,where x=a]
next-exec-subset[THEN spec,THEN spec,THEN spec,where x2=s and x1=execs and x0=u]
have  $\forall$  v . intermediary v u  $\longrightarrow$  v  $\notin$  involved (Some a)
unfolding actions-in-execution-def
by(auto)
}
thus ?thesis unfolding does-not-communicate-with-gateway-def by auto

```

```

qed
have iequivalent-states (run (Suc n) (Some s) execs) (run (Suc n) (Some t') execs2) u
proof (cases ifp (current s) u  $\wedge$   $\neg$ intermediary (current s) u rule :case-split[case-names T F])
case T
  show ?thesis
  proof (cases thread-empty(execs2 (current t')) rule :case-split[case-names T2 F2])
  case F2
    show ?thesis
    proof (cases precondition (next-state t' execs2) (next-action t' execs2) rule :case-split[case-names T3 F3])

    case T3
      from T purged-a-a2 current-s-t
        next-exec-consistent[THEN spec,THEN spec,where x1=s and x=t'] vpeq-curr-s-t vpeq-involved
        have purged-na-na2: ipurged-relation1 u (next-exec s execs) (next-exec t' execs2)
        unfolding ipurged-relation1-def next-exec-def
        by auto
        from IH[where t=Some (step (next-state t' execs2) (next-action t' execs2)) and ?execs2.0=next-exec t'
execs2 and u=u]
          purged-na-na2 current-ns-nt vpeq-ns-nt-1[where a=(next-action s execs)] T T3 prec-s
          next-action-s-t eq-exec current-s-t no-gateway-comm-na
          have eq-ns-nt: iequivalent-states (run n (Some (step (next-state s execs) (next-action s execs)))) (next-exec
s execs))
              (run n (Some (step (next-state t' execs2) (next-action t' execs2)))) (next-exec t'
execs2)) u
            unfolding next-state-def
            by (auto,metis)
            from this not-interrupt thread-not-empty-s prec-s F2 T3
            have current-rs-rt: current rs = current rt using rs rt by auto
            {
              fix v
              assume ia: ifp v u  $\wedge$   $\neg$ intermediary v u
              from this eq-ns-nt not-interrupt thread-not-empty-s prec-s F2 T3
              have vpeq v rs rt using rs rt by auto
            }
            from this and current-rs-rt show ?thesis using rs rt by auto
          next
          case F3
            from F3 F2 not-interrupt show ?thesis using rt by simp
          qed
        next
        case T2
          from T2 T purged-a-a2 thread-not-empty-s current-s-t prec-s next-action-s-t vpeq-u-s-t
          have ind-source: False unfolding ipurged-relation1-def by auto
          thus ?thesis by auto
        qed
      next
      case F
        hence 1: ind-source (current s) u  $\vee$  unrelated (current s) u  $\vee$  intermediary (current s) u
        unfolding intermediary-def
        by auto
        from purged-a-a2 and thread-not-empty-s
        have 2:  $\neg$ intermediary (current s) u unfolding ipurged-relation1-def by auto

        let ?nt = if thread-empty(execs2 (current t')) then t' else step (next-state t' execs2) (next-action t' execs2)
        let ?na2 = if thread-empty(execs2 (current t')) then execs2 else next-exec t' execs2

        have prec-t:  $\neg$ thread-empty(execs2 (current t'))  $\implies$  precondition (next-state t' execs2) (next-action t'

```

```

execs2)
  proof-
  assume thread-not-empty-t:  $\neg$ thread-empty(execs2 (current t'))
  {
    assume not-prec-t:  $\neg$ precondition (next-state t' execs2) (next-action t' execs2)
    hence run (Suc n) (Some t') execs2 = None using not-interrupt thread-not-empty-t not-prec-t by (simp)
    from this have False using rt by (simp add:option.splits)
  }
  thus ?thesis by auto
qed

show ?thesis
proof-
{
  fix v
  assume ifp-v: ifp v u
  assume v-not-intermediary:  $\neg$ intermediary v u

  have not-ifp-curr-v:  $\neg$ ifp (current s) v
  proof
    assume ifp-curr-v: ifp (current s) v
    thus False
  proof-
  {
    assume ind-source (current s) u
    from this ifp-curr-v ifp-v have intermediary v u unfolding intermediary-def by auto
    from this v-not-intermediary have False unfolding intermediary-def by auto
  }
  moreover
  {
    assume unrelated: unrelated (current s) u
    from this ifp-v ifp-curr-v have False using rtranclp-trans r-into-rtranclp by metis
  }
  ultimately show ?thesis using 1 2 by auto
}
qed
qed
from this current-next-state[THEN spec,THEN spec,where x1=s and x=execs] prec-s
  locally-respects[THEN spec,THEN spec,where x=next-state s execs] vpeq-reflexive
  have vpeq v (next-state s execs) (step (next-state s execs) (next-action s execs))
  unfolding step-def precondition-def B-def
  by (cases next-action s execs,auto)
from not-ifp-curr-v this locally-respects-next-state vpeq-transitive
  have vpeq-s-ns: vpeq v s (step (next-state s execs) (next-action s execs))
  by blast
from not-ifp-curr-v current-s-t current-next-state[THEN spec,THEN spec,where x1=t' and x=execs2] prec-t
  locally-respects[THEN spec,THEN spec,where x=next-state t' execs2]
  F vpeq-reflexive
  have 0:  $\neg$  thread-empty (execs2 (current t'))  $\longrightarrow$  vpeq v (next-state t' execs2) (step (next-state t' execs2)
(next-action t' execs2))
  unfolding step-def precondition-def B-def
  by (cases next-action t' execs2,auto)
  from 0 not-ifp-curr-v current-s-t locally-respects-next-state[THEN spec,THEN spec,THEN spec,where
x2=t' and x1=v and x=execs2]
  vpeq-transitive
  have vpeq-t-nt:  $\neg$  thread-empty (execs2 (current t'))  $\longrightarrow$  vpeq v t' (step (next-state t' execs2) (next-action
t' execs2)) by metis
  from this vpeq-reflexive

```

```

    have vpeq-t-nt: vpeq v t' ?nt
    by auto
  from vpeq-s-t ifp-v v-not-intermediary
  have vpeq v s t' by auto
  from this vpeq-s-ns vpeq-t-nt vpeq-transitive vpeq-symmetric vpeq-reflexive
  have vpeq v (step (next-state s execs) (next-action s execs)) ?nt
  by (metis (hide-lams, no-types))
}
hence vpeq-ns-nt:  $\forall v . \text{ifp } v \ u \wedge \neg \text{intermediary } v \ u \longrightarrow \text{vpeq } v \ (\text{step } (\text{next-state } s \ \text{execs}) \ (\text{next-action } s \ \text{execs})) \ ?nt$  by auto
  from vpeq-s-t 2 F purged-a-a2 current-s-t thread-not-empty-s have purged-na-na2: ipurged-relation1 u
(next-exec s execs) ?na2
  unfolding ipurged-relation1-def next-exec-def intermediary-def by (auto)
  from current-ns-nt current-ns-t current-next-state have current-ns-nt:
current (step (next-state s execs) (next-action s execs)) = current ?nt
  by auto
  from prec-s vpeq-ns-nt no-gateway-comm-na
  and IH[where t=Some ?nt and ?execs2.0=?na2 and u=u]
  and current-ns-nt purged-na-na2
  have eq-ns-nt: iequivalent-states (run n (Some (step (next-state s execs) (next-action s execs)))) (next-exec
s execs))
      (run n (Some ?nt) ?na2) u by auto

  from this not-interrupt thread-not-empty-s prec-t prec-s
  have current-rs-rt: current rs = current rt using rs rt by (cases thread-empty (execs2 (current
t')),simp,simp)
  {
  fix v
  assume ia: ifp v u  $\wedge$   $\neg$ intermediary v u
  from this eq-ns-nt not-interrupt thread-not-empty-s prec-s prec-t
  have vpeq v rs rt
  using rs rt by (cases thread-empty(execs2 (current t')),simp,simp)
  }
  from current-rs-rt and this show ?thesis using rs rt by auto
qed
qed
}
}
thus ?case by (simp add:option.splits,cases t,simp+)
qed
}
hence iview-partitioned-inductive:  $\forall u \ s \ t \ \text{execs} \ \text{execs2} \ n . \text{does-not-communicate-with-gateway } u \ \text{execs} \wedge \text{iequivalent-states}$ 
s t u  $\wedge$  ipurged-relation1 u execs execs2  $\longrightarrow$  iequivalent-states (run n s execs) (run n t execs2) u
  by blast
have ipurged-relation:  $\forall u \ \text{execs} . \text{ipurged-relation1 } u \ (\text{ipurge-l } \text{execs } u) \ (\text{ipurge-r } \text{execs } u)$ 
  by (unfold ipurged-relation1-def,unfold ipurge-l-def,unfold ipurge-r-def,auto)
{
  fix execs s t n u
  assume I: iequivalent-states s t u
  from ifp-reflexive
  have dir-source:  $\forall u . \text{ifp } u \ u \wedge \neg \text{intermediary } u \ u$  unfolding intermediary-def by auto
  from ipurge-l-removes-gateway-communications
  have does-not-communicate-with-gateway u (ipurge-l execs u)
  by auto
  from I this iview-partitioned-inductive ipurged-relation
  have iequivalent-states (run n s (ipurge-l execs u)) (run n t (ipurge-r execs u)) u by auto
  from this dir-source
  have run n s (ipurge-l execs u)  $\parallel$  run n t (ipurge-r execs u)  $\rightarrow$  ( $\lambda rs \ rt . \text{vpeq } u \ rs \ rt \wedge \text{current } rs = \text{current } rt$ )

```

```

using r-into-rtranclp unfolding B-def
by(cases run n s (ipurge-l execs u),simp,cases run n t (ipurge-r execs u),simp,auto)
}
thus ?thesis unfolding iview-partitioned-def Let-def by auto
qed

```

Returns True iff and only if the two states have the same active domain, *or* if one of the states is None.

```

definition mcurrents :: 'state-t option ⇒ 'state-t option ⇒ bool
where mcurrents m1 m2 ≡ m1 || m2 → (λ s t . current s = current t)

```

Proof that switching/interrupts are purely time-based and happen independent of the actions done by the domains. As all theorems in this locale, it holds vacuously whenever one of the states is None, i.e., whenever at some point a precondition does not hold.

lemma *current-independent-of-domain-actions*:

assumes *current-s-t: mcurrents s t*

shows *mcurrents (run n s execs) (run n t execs2)*

proof–

```

{
  fix n s execs t execs2
  have mcurrents s t → mcurrents (run n s execs) (run n t execs2)
  proof (induct n s execs arbitrary: t execs2 rule: run.induct)
  case (1 s execs t execs2)
    from this show ?case using current-s-t unfolding B-def by auto
  next
  case (2 n execs t execs2)
    show ?case unfolding mcurrents-def by(auto)
  next
  case (3 n s execs t execs2)
    assume interrupt: interrupt (Suc n)
    assume IH: (λ t execs2. mcurrents (Some (cswitch (Suc n) s)) t → mcurrents (run n (Some (cswitch (Suc n) s)) execs) (run n t execs2))
    {
      fix t'
      assume t: t = (Some t')
      assume curr: mcurrents (Some s) t
      from t curr cswitch-independent-of-state[THEN spec,THEN spec,THEN spec,where x1=s] have current-ns-nt: current (cswitch (Suc n) s) = current (cswitch (Suc n) t')
      unfolding mcurrents-def by simp
      from current-ns-nt IH[where t=Some (cswitch (Suc n) t') and ?execs2.0=execs2]
      have mcurrents-ns-nt: mcurrents (run n (Some (cswitch (Suc n) s)) execs) (run n (Some (cswitch (Suc n) t')) execs2)
      unfolding mcurrents-def by(auto)
      from mcurrents-ns-nt interrupt t
      have mcurrents (run (Suc n) (Some s) execs) (run (Suc n) t execs2)
      unfolding mcurrents-def B2-def B-def by(cases run n (Some (cswitch (Suc n) s)) execs, cases run (Suc n) t execs2,auto)
    }
    thus ?case unfolding mcurrents-def B2-def by(cases t,auto)
  next
  case (4 n execs s t execs2)
    assume not-interrupt: ¬interrupt (Suc n)
    assume thread-empty-s: thread-empty(execs (current s))
    assume IH: (λ t execs2. mcurrents (Some s) t → mcurrents (run n (Some s) execs) (run n t execs2))
    {
      fix t'
      assume t: t = (Some t')

```

```

assume curr: mcurrents (Some s) t
{
  assume thread-empty-t: thread-empty(execs2 (current t'))
  from t curr not-interrupt thread-empty-s this IH[where ?execs2.0=execs2 and t=Some t']
  have mcurrents (run (Suc n) (Some s) execs) (run (Suc n) t execs2)
  by auto
}
moreover
{
  assume not-prec-t:  $\neg$ thread-empty(execs2 (current t'))  $\wedge$   $\neg$ precondition (next-state t' execs2) (next-action t'
execs2)
  from t this not-interrupt
  have mcurrents (run (Suc n) (Some s) execs) (run (Suc n) t execs2)
  unfolding mcurrents-def by (simp add: rewrite-B2-cases)
}
moreover
{
  assume step-t:  $\neg$ thread-empty(execs2 (current t'))  $\wedge$  precondition (next-state t' execs2) (next-action t'
execs2)
  have mcurrents (Some s) (Some (step (next-state t' execs2) (next-action t' execs2)))
  using step-atomicity curr t current-next-state unfolding mcurrents-def
  unfolding step-def
  by (cases next-action t' execs2,auto)
  from t step-t curr not-interrupt thread-empty-s this IH[where ?execs2.0=next-exec t' execs2 and t=Some
(step (next-state t' execs2) (next-action t' execs2))]
  have mcurrents (run (Suc n) (Some s) execs) (run (Suc n) t execs2)
  by auto
}
ultimately have mcurrents (run (Suc n) (Some s) execs) (run (Suc n) t execs2) by blast
}
thus ?case unfolding mcurrents-def B2-def by(cases t,auto)
next
case (5 n execs s t execs2)
  assume not-interrupt-s:  $\neg$ interrupt (Suc n)
  assume thread-not-empty-s:  $\neg$ thread-empty(execs (current s))
  assume not-prec-s:  $\neg$  precondition (next-state s execs) (next-action s execs)
  hence run (Suc n) (Some s) execs = None using not-interrupt-s thread-not-empty-s by simp
  thus ?case unfolding mcurrents-def by(simp add:option.splits)
next
case (6 n execs s t execs2)
  assume not-interrupt:  $\neg$ interrupt (Suc n)
  assume thread-not-empty-s:  $\neg$ thread-empty(execs (current s))
  assume prec-s: precondition (next-state s execs) (next-action s execs)
  assume IH: ( $\wedge$ t execs2.
    mcurrents (Some (step (next-state s execs) (next-action s execs))) t  $\longrightarrow$ 
    mcurrents (run n (Some (step (next-state s execs) (next-action s execs))) (next-exec s execs)) (run n t
execs2))
  {
    fix t'
    assume t: t = (Some t')
    assume curr: mcurrents (Some s) t
    {
      assume thread-empty-t: thread-empty(execs2 (current t'))
      have mcurrents (Some (step (next-state s execs) (next-action s execs))) (Some t')
      using step-atomicity curr t current-next-state unfolding mcurrents-def
      unfolding step-def
      by (cases next-action s execs,auto)
    }
  }

```

```

    from t curr not-interrupt thread-not-empty-s prec-s thread-empty-t this IH[where ?execs2.0=execs2 and
t=Some t']
    have mcurrents (run (Suc n) (Some s) execs) (run (Suc n) t execs2)
    by auto
  }
  moreover
  {
    assume not-prec-t: ¬thread-empty(execs2 (current t')) ∧ ¬precondition (next-state t' execs2) (next-action t'
execs2)
    from t this not-interrupt
    have mcurrents (run (Suc n) (Some s) execs) (run (Suc n) t execs2)
    unfolding mcurrents-def B2-def by (auto)
  }
  moreover
  {
    assume step-t: ¬thread-empty(execs2 (current t')) ∧ precondition (next-state t' execs2) (next-action t'
execs2)
    have mcurrents (Some (step (next-state s execs) (next-action s execs))) (Some (step (next-state t' execs2)
(next-action t' execs2)))
    using step-atomicity curr t current-next-state unfolding mcurrents-def
    unfolding step-def
    by (cases next-action s execs,simp,cases next-action t' execs2,simp,simp,cases next-action t' execs2,simp,simp)
    from current-next-state t step-t curr not-interrupt thread-not-empty-s prec-s this IH[where ?execs2.0=next-exec
t' execs2 and t=Some (step (next-state t' execs2) (next-action t' execs2))]
    have mcurrents (run (Suc n) (Some s) execs) (run (Suc n) t execs2)
    by auto
  }
  ultimately have mcurrents (run (Suc n) (Some s) execs) (run (Suc n) t execs2) by blast
}
thus ?case unfolding mcurrents-def B2-def by(cases t,auto)
qed
}
thus ?thesis using current-s-t by auto
qed

```

theorem *unwinding-implies-NI-indirect-sources:*

shows *NI-indirect-sources*

proof–

```

{
  fix execs a n
  from assms unwinding-implies-view-partitioned1
  have vp: iview-partitioned by blast
  from vp and vpeq-reflexive
  have I: ∀ u . run n (Some s0) (ipurge-l execs u) || run n (Some s0) (ipurge-r execs u) → (λrs rt. vpeq u rs rt
∧ current rs = current rt)
    unfolding iview-partitioned-def by auto

  have run n (Some s0) execs → (λs-f. run n (Some s0) (ipurge-l execs (current s-f)) ||
run n (Some s0) (ipurge-r execs (current s-f)) →
(λs-l s-r. output-f s-l a = output-f s-r a))

  proof(cases run n (Some s0) execs)
  case None
    thus ?thesis unfolding B-def by simp
  next
  case (Some s-f)
    thus ?thesis
    proof(cases run n (Some s0) (ipurge-l execs (current s-f)))

```

```

case None
  from Some this show ?thesis unfolding B-def by simp
next
case (Some s-ipurge-l)
  show ?thesis
  proof(cases run n (Some s0) (ipurge-r execs (current s-f)))
  case None
    from (run n (Some s0) execs = Some s-f) Some this show ?thesis unfolding B-def by simp
  next
  case (Some s-ipurge-r)
    from cswitch-independent-of-state
      (run n (Some s0) execs = Some s-f) (run n (Some s0) (ipurge-l execs (current s-f)) = Some s-ipurge-l)
      current-independent-of-domain-actions[where n=n and s=Some s0 and t=Some s0 and execs=execs and
      ?execs2.0=(ipurge-l execs (current s-f))]
    have 2: current s-ipurge-l = current s-f
    unfolding mcurrents-def B-def by auto
  from (run n (Some s0) execs = Some s-f) (run n (Some s0) (ipurge-l execs (current s-f)) = Some s-ipurge-l)
    Some I[THEN spec,where x=current s-f]
  have vpeq (current s-f) s-ipurge-l s-ipurge-r  $\wedge$  current s-ipurge-l = current s-ipurge-r
  unfolding B-def by auto
  from this 2 have output-f s-ipurge-l a = output-f s-ipurge-r a
  using output-consistent by auto
  from (run n (Some s0) execs = Some s-f) (run n (Some s0) (ipurge-l execs (current s-f)) = Some s-ipurge-l)
    this Some
  show ?thesis unfolding B-def by auto
  qed
qed
qed
}
thus ?thesis unfolding NI-indirect-sources-def by auto
qed

```

theorem *unwinding-implies-isecure:*

shows *isecure*

using *unwinding-implies-NI-indirect-sources unwinding-implies-NI-unrelated assms unfolding isecure-def by(auto)*

end

end

2.3 ISK (Interruptible Separation Kernel)

theory *ISK*

imports *SK*

begin

At this point, the precondition linking action to state is generic and highly unconstrained. We refine the previous locale by given generic functions “precondition” and “realistic_trace” a definiton. This yields a total run function, instead of the partial one of locale Separation_Kernel.

This definition is based on a set of valid action sequences *AS_set*. Consider for example the following action sequence:

$$\gamma = [COPY_INIT, COPY_CHECK, COPY_COPY]$$

If action sequence γ is a member of *AS_set*, this means that the attack surface contains an action COPY, which consists of three consecutive atomic kernel actions. Interrupts can occur anywhere between these atomic actions.

Given a set of valid action sequences such as γ , generic function precondition can be defined. It now consists of 1.) a generic invariant and 2.) more refined preconditions for the current action.

These preconditions need to be proven inductive only according to action sequences. Assume, e.g., that $\gamma \in AS_set$ and that d is the currently active domain in state s . The following constraints are assumed and must therefore be proven for the instantiation:

- “AS_precondition s d COPY_INIT”
since COPY_INIT is the start of an action sequence.
- “AS_precondition (step s COPY_INIT) d COPY_CHECK”
since (COPY_INIT, COPY_CHECK) is a sub sequence.
- “AS_precondition (step s COPY_CHECK) d COPY_COPY”
since (COPY_CHECK, COPY_COPY) is a sub sequence.

Additionally, the precondition for domain d must be consistent when a context switch occurs, or when ever some other domain d' performs an action.

Locale *Interruptible_Separation_Kernel* refines locale *Separation_Kernel* in two ways. First, there is a definition of realistic executions. A realistic trace consists of action sequences from *AS_set*.

Secondly, the generic *control* function has been refined by additional assumptions. It is now assumed that control conforms to one of four possibilities:

1. The execution of the currently active domain is empty and the control function returns no action.
2. The currently active domain is executing the action sequence at the head of the execution. It returns the next kernel action of this sequence and updates the execution accordingly.
3. The action sequence is delayed.
4. The action sequence that is at the head of the execution is skipped and the execution is updated accordingly.

As for the state update, this is still completely unconstrained and generic as long as it respects the generic invariant and the precondition.

```

locale Interruptible-Separation-Kernel = Separation-Kernel kstep output-f s0 current cswitch interrupt kprecondition
realistic-execution control kinvolved ifp vpeq
for kstep :: 'state-t => 'action-t => 'state-t
and output-f :: 'state-t => 'action-t => 'output-t
and s0 :: 'state-t
and current :: 'state-t => 'dom-t — Returns the currently active domain
and cswitch :: time-t => 'state-t => 'state-t — Switches the current domain
and interrupt :: time-t => bool — Returns t iff an interrupt occurs in the given state at the given time
and kprecondition :: 'state-t => 'action-t => bool — Returns t if an precondition holds that relates the current
action to the state
and realistic-execution :: 'action-t execution => bool — In this locale, this function is completely unconstrained.
and control :: 'state-t => 'dom-t => 'action-t execution => (('action-t option) × 'action-t execution × 'state-t)
and kinvolved :: 'action-t => 'dom-t set
and ifp :: 'dom-t => 'dom-t => bool
and vpeq :: 'dom-t => 'state-t => 'state-t => bool
+
fixes AS-set :: ('action-t list) set — Returns a set of valid action sequences, i.e., the attack surface
and invariant :: 'state-t => bool
and AS-precondition :: 'state-t => 'dom-t => 'action-t => bool
and aborting :: 'state-t => 'dom-t => 'action-t => bool
and waiting :: 'state-t => 'dom-t => 'action-t => bool
assumes empty-in-AS-set: [] ∈ AS-set
and invariant-s0: invariant s0

```

and invariant-after-cswitch: $\forall s n . \text{invariant } s \longrightarrow \text{invariant } (\text{cswitch } n s)$
and precondition-after-cswitch: $\forall s d n a . \text{AS-precondition } s d a \longrightarrow \text{AS-precondition } (\text{cswitch } n s) d a$
and AS-prec-first-action: $\forall s d \text{aseq} . \text{invariant } s \wedge \text{aseq} \in \text{AS-set} \wedge \text{aseq} \neq [] \longrightarrow \text{AS-precondition } s d (\text{hd } \text{aseq})$
and AS-prec-after-step: $\forall s a a' . (\exists \text{aseq} \in \text{AS-set} . \text{is-sub-seq } a a' \text{aseq}) \wedge \text{invariant } s \wedge \text{AS-precondition } s (\text{current } s) a \wedge \neg \text{aborting } s (\text{current } s) a \wedge \neg \text{waiting } s (\text{current } s) a \longrightarrow \text{AS-precondition } (\text{kstep } s a) (\text{current } s) a'$
and AS-prec-dom-independent: $\forall s d a a' . \text{current } s \neq d \wedge \text{AS-precondition } s d a \longrightarrow \text{AS-precondition } (\text{kstep } s a') d a$
and spec-of-invariant: $\forall s a . \text{invariant } s \longrightarrow \text{invariant } (\text{kstep } s a)$

and kprecondition-def: $\text{kprecondition } s a \equiv \text{invariant } s \wedge \text{AS-precondition } s (\text{current } s) a$
and realistic-execution-def: $\text{realistic-execution } \text{aseq} \equiv \text{set } \text{aseq} \subseteq \text{AS-set}$
and control-spec: $\forall s d \text{aseqs} . \text{case control } s d \text{aseqs of } (a, \text{aseqs}', s') \Rightarrow$
 $(\text{thread-empty } \text{aseqs} \wedge (a, \text{aseqs}') = (\text{None}, [])) \vee (* \text{Nothing happens } *)$
 $(\text{aseqs} \neq [] \wedge \text{hd } \text{aseqs} \neq [] \wedge \neg \text{aborting } s' d (\text{the } a) \wedge \neg \text{waiting } s' d (\text{the } a) \wedge (a, \text{aseqs}') =$
 $(\text{Some } (\text{hd } (\text{hd } \text{aseqs})), (\text{tl } (\text{hd } \text{aseqs})) \# (\text{tl } \text{aseqs}))) \vee (* \text{Execute the first action of the current action sequence } *$
 $*)$
 $(\text{aseqs} \neq [] \wedge \text{hd } \text{aseqs} \neq [] \wedge \text{waiting } s' d (\text{the } a) \wedge (a, \text{aseqs}', s') = (\text{Some } (\text{hd } (\text{hd } \text{aseqs})), \text{aseqs}, s)) \vee (* \text{Nothing happens, waiting to execute the next action } *)$
 $(a, \text{aseqs}') = (\text{None}, \text{tl } \text{aseqs})$
and next-action-after-cswitch: $\forall s n d \text{aseqs} . \text{fst } (\text{control } (\text{cswitch } n s) d \text{aseqs}) = \text{fst } (\text{control } s d \text{aseqs})$
and next-action-after-next-state: $\forall s \text{execs } d . \text{current } s \neq d \longrightarrow \text{fst } (\text{control } (\text{next-state } s \text{execs}) d (\text{execs } d))$
 $= \text{None} \vee \text{fst } (\text{control } (\text{next-state } s \text{execs}) d (\text{execs } d)) = \text{fst } (\text{control } s d (\text{execs } d))$
and next-action-after-step: $\forall s a d \text{aseqs} . \text{current } s \neq d \longrightarrow \text{fst } (\text{control } (\text{step } s a) d \text{aseqs}) = \text{fst } (\text{control } s d \text{aseqs})$
and next-state-precondition: $\forall s d a \text{execs} . \text{AS-precondition } s d a \longrightarrow \text{AS-precondition } (\text{next-state } s \text{execs}) d a$
and next-state-invariant: $\forall s \text{execs} . \text{invariant } s \longrightarrow \text{invariant } (\text{next-state } s \text{execs})$
and spec-of-waiting: $\forall s a . \text{waiting } s (\text{current } s) a \longrightarrow \text{kstep } s a = s$

begin

We can now formulate a total run function, since based on the new assumptions the case where the precondition does not hold, will never occur.

function *run-total* :: *time-t* \Rightarrow *'state-t* \Rightarrow (*'dom-t* \Rightarrow *'action-t execution*) \Rightarrow *'state-t*
where *run-total* 0 *s execs* = *s*
 $| \text{interrupt } (\text{Suc } n) \Longrightarrow \text{run-total } (\text{Suc } n) s \text{execs} = \text{run-total } n (\text{cswitch } (\text{Suc } n) s) \text{execs}$
 $| \neg \text{interrupt } (\text{Suc } n) \Longrightarrow \text{thread-empty}(\text{execs } (\text{current } s)) \Longrightarrow \text{run-total } (\text{Suc } n) s \text{execs} = \text{run-total } n s \text{execs}$
 $| \neg \text{interrupt } (\text{Suc } n) \Longrightarrow \neg \text{thread-empty}(\text{execs } (\text{current } s)) \Longrightarrow$
 $\text{run-total } (\text{Suc } n) s \text{execs} = \text{run-total } n (\text{step } (\text{next-state } s \text{execs}) (\text{next-action } s \text{execs})) (\text{next-exec } s \text{execs})$
using *not0-implies-Suc* **by** (*metis prod-cases3, auto*)
termination **by** *lexicographic-order*

The major part of the proofs in this locale consist of proving that function *run_total* is equivalent to function *run*, i.e., that the precondition does always hold. This assumes that the executions are *realistic*. This means that the execution of each domain contains action sequences that are from *AS_set*. This ensures, e.g., that a *COPY_CHECK* is always preceded by a *COPY_INIT*.

definition *realistic-executions* :: (*'dom-t* \Rightarrow *'action-t execution*) \Rightarrow *bool*
where *realistic-executions* *execs* $\equiv \forall d . \text{realistic-execution } (\text{execs } d)$

Lemma *run_total_equals_run* is proven by doing induction. It is however not inductive and can therefore not be proven directly: a realistic execution is not necessarily realistic after performing one action. We generalize to do induction. Predicate *realistic_executions_ind* is the inductive version of *realistic_executions*. All action sequences in the tail of the executions must be complete action sequences (i.e., they must be from *AS_set*). The first action sequence, however, is being executed and is therefore not necessarily an action sequence from *AS_set*, but it is *the last part* of some action sequence from *AS_set*.

definition *realistic-AS-partial* :: *'action-t list* \Rightarrow *bool*
where *realistic-AS-partial* *aseq* $\equiv \exists n \text{aseq}' . n \leq \text{length } \text{aseq}' \wedge \text{aseq}' \in \text{AS-set} \wedge \text{aseq} = \text{lastn } n \text{aseq}'$

definition *realistic-executions-ind* :: ('dom-t \Rightarrow 'action-t execution) \Rightarrow bool
where *realistic-executions-ind* *execs* $\equiv \forall d . (case\ execs\ d\ of\ [] \Rightarrow True \mid (aseq\#\#aseqs) \Rightarrow realistic-AS-partial\ aseq \wedge set\ aseqs \subseteq AS-set)$

We need to know that invariably, the precondition holds. As this precondition consists of 1.) a generic invariant and 2.) more refined preconditions for the current action, we have to know that these two are invariably true.

definition *precondition-ind* :: 'state-t \Rightarrow ('dom-t \Rightarrow 'action-t execution) \Rightarrow bool
where *precondition-ind* *s* *execs* $\equiv invariant\ s \wedge (\forall d . fst(control\ s\ d\ (execs\ d)) \rightarrow AS-precondition\ s\ d)$

Proof that “execution is realistic” is inductive, i.e., assuming the current execution is realistic, the execution returned by the control mechanism is realistic.

lemma *next-execution-is-realistic-partial*:

assumes *na-def*: *next-exec* *s* *execs* *d* = *aseq* $\#\$ *aseqs*

and *d-is-curr*: *d* = *current* *s*

and *realistic*: *realistic-executions-ind* *execs*

and *thread-not-empty*: $\neg thread-empty(execs\ (current\ s))$

shows *realistic-AS-partial* *aseq* $\wedge set\ aseqs \subseteq AS-set$

proof–

let *?c* = *control* *s* (*current* *s*) (*execs* (*current* *s*))

{

assume *c-empty*: *let* (*a,aseqs',s'*) = *?c* *in*
(*a,aseqs'*) = (*None*,[])

from *na-def* *d-is-curr* *c-empty*

have *?thesis*

unfolding *realistic-executions-ind-def* *next-exec-def* **by** (*auto*)

}

moreover

{

let *?ct* = *execs* (*current* *s*)

let *?execs'* = (*tl* (*hd* *?ct*)) $\#\$ (*tl* *?ct*)

let *?a'* = *Some* (*hd* (*hd* *?ct*))

assume *hd-thread-not-empty*: *hd* (*execs* (*current* *s*)) $\neq []$

assume *c-executing*: *let* (*a,aseqs',s'*) = *?c* *in*
(*a,aseqs'*) = (*?a'*, *?execs'*)

from *na-def* *c-executing* *d-is-curr*

have *as-defs*: *aseq* = *tl* (*hd* *?ct*) \wedge *aseqs* = *tl* *?ct*

unfolding *next-exec-def* **by** (*auto*)

from *realistic*[*unfolded* *realistic-executions-ind-def*,*THEN* *spec*,**where** *x=d*] *d-is-curr*

have *subset*: *set* (*tl* *?execs'*) $\subseteq AS-set$

unfolding *Let-def* *realistic-AS-partial-def*

by (*cases* *execs* *d*,*auto*)

from *d-is-curr* *thread-not-empty* *hd-thread-not-empty* *realistic*[*unfolded* *realistic-executions-ind-def*,*THEN* *spec*,**where** *x=d*]

obtain *n* *aseq'* **where** *n-aseq'*: *n* \leq *length* *aseq'* \wedge *aseq'* $\in AS-set \wedge hd\ ?ct = lastn\ n\ aseq'$

unfolding *realistic-AS-partial-def*

by (*cases* *execs* *d*,*auto*)

from *this* *hd-thread-not-empty* **have** *n* > 0 **unfolding** *lastn-def* **by** (*cases* *n*,*auto*)

from *this* *n-aseq'* *lastn-one-less*[**where** *n=n* **and** *x=aseq'* **and** *a=hd* (*hd* *?ct*) **and** *y=tl* (*hd* *?ct*)] *hd-thread-not-empty*

have *n* $- 1 \leq$ *length* *aseq'* \wedge *aseq'* $\in AS-set \wedge tl$ (*hd* *?ct*) = *lastn* (*n* $- 1$) *aseq'*

by *auto*

from *this* *as-defs* *subset* **have** *?thesis*

unfolding *realistic-AS-partial-def*

by *auto*

}

moreover

{

```

let ?ct= execs (current s)
let ?execs' = ?ct
let ?a' = Some (hd (hd ?ct))
assume c-waiting: let (a,aseqs',s') = ?c in
    (a,aseqs') = (?a', ?execs')
from na-def c-waiting d-is-curr
  have as-defs: aseq = hd ?execs'  $\wedge$  aseqs = tl ?execs'
  unfolding next-execs-def by (auto)
  from realistic[unfolding realistic-executions-ind-def,THEN spec,where x=d] d-is-curr set-tl-is-subset[where
x=?execs']
  have subset: set (tl ?execs')  $\subseteq$  AS-set
  unfolding Let-def realistic-AS-partial-def
  by (cases execs d,auto)
from na-def c-waiting d-is-curr
  have ?execs'  $\neq$  [] unfolding next-execs-def by auto
from realistic[unfolding realistic-executions-ind-def,THEN spec,where x=d] d-is-curr thread-not-empty
  obtain n aseq' where witness: n  $\leq$  length aseq'  $\wedge$  aseq'  $\in$  AS-set  $\wedge$  hd (execs d) = lastn n aseq'
  unfolding realistic-AS-partial-def by (cases execs d,auto)
from d-is-curr this subset as-defs have ?thesis
  unfolding realistic-AS-partial-def
  by auto
}
moreover
{
  let ?ct= execs (current s)
  let ?execs' = tl ?ct
  let ?a' = None
  assume c-aborting: let (a,aseqs',s') = ?c in
    (a,aseqs') = (?a', ?execs')
  from na-def c-aborting d-is-curr
    have as-defs: aseq = hd ?execs'  $\wedge$  aseqs = tl ?execs'
    unfolding next-execs-def by (auto)
    from realistic[unfolding realistic-executions-ind-def,THEN spec,where x=d] d-is-curr set-tl-is-subset[where
x=?execs']
    have subset: set (tl ?execs')  $\subseteq$  AS-set
    unfolding Let-def realistic-AS-partial-def
    by (cases execs d,auto)
  from na-def c-aborting d-is-curr
    have ?execs'  $\neq$  [] unfolding next-execs-def by auto
  from empty-in-AS-set this
    realistic[unfolding realistic-executions-ind-def,THEN spec,where x=d] d-is-curr
    have length (hd ?execs')  $\leq$  length (hd ?execs')  $\wedge$  (hd ?execs')  $\in$  AS-set  $\wedge$  hd ?execs' = lastn (length (hd
?execs')) (hd ?execs')
    unfolding lastn-def
    by (cases execs (current s),auto)
  from this subset as-defs have ?thesis
  unfolding realistic-AS-partial-def
  by auto
}
ultimately
show ?thesis
  using control-spec[THEN spec,THEN spec,THEN spec,where x2=s and x1=current s and x=execs (current s)]
  d-is-curr thread-not-empty
  by (auto simp add: Let-def)
qed

```

The lemma that proves that the total run function is equivalent to the partial run function, i.e., that in this refinement the case of the run function where the precondition is False will never occur.

lemma *run-total-equals-run*:

assumes *realistic-exec*: *realistic-executions execs*
and invariant: *invariant s*
shows *strict-equal (run n (Some s) execs) (run-total n s execs)*

proof–
{
fix *n ms s execs*
have *strict-equal ms s \wedge realistic-executions-ind execs \wedge precondition-ind s execs \longrightarrow strict-equal (run n ms execs) (run-total n s execs)*
proof (*induct n ms execs arbitrary: s rule: run.induct*)
case (*1 s execs sa*)
show ?*case by auto*
next
case (*2 n execs s*)
show ?*case unfolding strict-equal-def by auto*
next
case (*3 n s execs sa*)
assume *interrupt: interrupt (Suc n)*
assume *IH: ($\wedge sa. strict-equal (Some (cswitch (Suc n) s)) sa \wedge realistic-executions-ind execs \wedge precondition-ind sa execs \longrightarrow$*
strict-equal (run n (Some (cswitch (Suc n) s)) execs) (run-total n sa execs))
{
assume *equal-s-sa: strict-equal (Some s) sa*
assume *realistic: realistic-executions-ind execs*
assume *inv-sa: precondition-ind sa execs*
have *inv-nsa: precondition-ind (cswitch (Suc n) sa) execs*
proof–
{
fix *d*
have *fst (control (cswitch (Suc n) sa) d (execs d)) \rightarrow AS-precondition (cswitch (Suc n) sa) d*
using *next-action-after-cswitch inv-sa[unfolded precondition-ind-def, THEN conjunct2, THEN spec, where*
x=d]
precondition-after-cswitch
unfolding *Let-def B-def precondition-ind-def*
by (*cases fst (control (cswitch (Suc n) sa) d (execs d)), auto*)
}
thus ?*thesis using inv-sa invariant-after-cswitch unfolding precondition-ind-def by auto*
qed
from *equal-s-sa realistic inv-nsa inv-sa IH[where sa=cswitch (Suc n) sa]*
have *equal-ns-nt: strict-equal (run n (Some (cswitch (Suc n) s)) execs) (run-total n (cswitch (Suc n) sa) execs)*
unfolding *strict-equal-def by(auto)*
}
from this interrupt show ?*case by auto*
next
case (*4 n execs s sa*)
assume *not-interrupt: \neg interrupt (Suc n)*
assume *thread-empty: thread-empty(execs (current s))*
assume *IH: ($\wedge sa. strict-equal (Some s) sa \wedge realistic-executions-ind execs \wedge precondition-ind sa execs \longrightarrow$*
strict-equal (run n (Some s) execs) (run-total n sa execs))
have *current-s-sa: strict-equal (Some s) sa \longrightarrow current s = current sa* **unfolding** *strict-equal-def by auto*
{
assume *equal-s-sa: strict-equal (Some s) sa*
assume *realistic: realistic-executions-ind execs*
assume *inv-sa: precondition-ind sa execs*
from *equal-s-sa realistic inv-sa IH[where sa=s]*
have *equal-ns-nt: strict-equal (run n (Some s) execs) (run-total n sa execs)*
}

```

    unfolding strict-equal-def by(auto)
  }
  from this current-s-sa thread-empty not-interrupt show ?case by auto
next
case (5 n execs s sa)
  assume not-interrupt:  $\neg$ interrupt (Suc n)
  assume thread-not-empty:  $\neg$ thread-empty(execs (current s))
  assume not-prec:  $\neg$ precondition (next-state s execs) (next-action s execs)
  — In locale ISK, the precondition can be proven to hold at all times. This case cannot happen, and we can prove
  False.
  {
    assume equal-s-sa: strict-equal (Some s) sa
    assume realistic: realistic-executions-ind execs
    assume inv-sa: precondition-ind sa execs
    from equal-s-sa have s-sa:  $s = sa$  unfolding strict-equal-def by auto
    from inv-sa have
      next-action sa execs  $\rightarrow$  AS-precondition sa (current sa)
    unfolding precondition-ind-def B-def next-action-def
    by (cases next-action sa execs,auto)
    from this next-state-precondition
    have next-action sa execs  $\rightarrow$  AS-precondition (next-state sa execs) (current sa)
    unfolding precondition-ind-def B-def
    by (cases next-action sa execs,auto)
    from inv-sa this s-sa next-state-invariant current-next-state
    have prec-s: precondition (next-state s execs) (next-action s execs)
    unfolding precondition-ind-def kprecondition-def precondition-def B-def
    by (cases next-action sa execs,auto)
    from this not-prec have False by auto
  }
  thus ?case by auto
next
case (6 n execs s sa)
  assume not-interrupt:  $\neg$ interrupt (Suc n)
  assume thread-not-empty:  $\neg$ thread-empty(execs (current s))
  assume prec: precondition (next-state s execs) (next-action s execs)
  assume IH: ( $\wedge sa$ . strict-equal (Some (step (next-state s execs) (next-action s execs))) sa  $\wedge$ 
    realistic-executions-ind (next-exec s execs)  $\wedge$  precondition-ind sa (next-exec s execs)  $\longrightarrow$ 
    strict-equal (run n (Some (step (next-state s execs) (next-action s execs))) (next-exec s execs)) (run-total
n sa (next-exec s execs)))
  have current-s-sa: strict-equal (Some s) sa  $\longrightarrow$  current s = current sa unfolding strict-equal-def by auto
  {
    assume equal-s-sa: strict-equal (Some s) sa
    assume realistic: realistic-executions-ind execs
    assume inv-sa: precondition-ind sa execs

    from equal-s-sa have s-sa:  $s = sa$  unfolding strict-equal-def by auto

    let ?a = next-action s execs
    let ?ns = step (next-state s execs) ?a
    let ?na = next-exec s execs
    let ?c = control s (current s) (execs (current s))

    have equal-ns-nsa: strict-equal (Some ?ns) ?ns unfolding strict-equal-def by auto
    from inv-sa equal-s-sa have inv-s: invariant s unfolding strict-equal-def precondition-ind-def by auto
  }

```

— Two things are proven inductive. First, the assumptions that the execution is realistic (statement realistic-na). This proof uses lemma next-execution-is-realistic-partial. Secondly, the precondition: if the precondition holds for

the current action, then it holds for the next action (statement invariant-na).

```

have realistic-na: realistic-executions-ind ?na
proof-
{
  fix d
  have case ?na d of []  $\Rightarrow$  True | aseq # aseqs  $\Rightarrow$  realistic-AS-partial aseq  $\wedge$  set aseqs  $\subseteq$  AS-set
  proof(cases ?na d, simp, rename-tac aseq aseqs, simp, cases d = current s)
  case False
    fix aseq aseqs
    assume next-execs s execs d = aseq # aseqs
    from False this realistic[unfolded realistic-executions-ind-def, THEN spec, where x=d]
    show realistic-AS-partial aseq  $\wedge$  set aseqs  $\subseteq$  AS-set
    unfolding next-execs-def by simp
  next
  case True
    fix aseq aseqs
    assume na-def: next-execs s execs d = aseq # aseqs
    from next-execution-is-realistic-partial na-def True realistic thread-not-empty
    show realistic-AS-partial aseq  $\wedge$  set aseqs  $\subseteq$  AS-set by blast
  qed
}
thus ?thesis unfolding realistic-executions-ind-def by auto
qed
have invariant-na: precondition-ind ?ns ?na
proof-
from spec-of-invariant inv-sa next-state-invariant s-sa have inv-ns: invariant ?ns
  unfolding precondition-ind-def step-def
  by (cases next-action sa execs, auto)
have  $\forall d. \text{fst}(\text{control } ?ns \ d \ (\ ?na \ d)) \rightarrow \text{AS-precondition } ?ns \ d$ 
proof-
{
  fix d
  {
    let ?a' = fst (control ?ns d (?na d))
    assume snd-action-not-none: ?a'  $\neq$  None
    have AS-precondition ?ns d (the ?a')
    proof (cases d = current s)
    case True
    {
      have ?thesis
      proof (cases ?a)
      case (Some a)
      — Assuming that the current domain executes some action a, and assuming that the action a' after that is
      not None (statement snd-action-not-none), we prove that the precondition is inductive, i.e., it will hold for a'. Two
      cases arise: either action a is delayed (case waiting) or not (case executing).
      show ?thesis
      proof(cases ?na d = execs (current s) rule :case-split[case-names waiting executing])
      case executing — The kernel is executing two consecutive actions a and a'. We show that [a,a'] is a
      subsequence in some action in AS-set. The PO's ensure that the precondition is inductive.
      from executing True Some control-spec[THEN spec, THEN spec, THEN spec, where x2=s and x1=d and
      x=execs d]
      have a-def: a = hd (hd (execs (current s)))  $\wedge$  ?na d = (tl (hd (execs (current s)))) # (tl (execs
      (current s)))
      unfolding next-action-def next-execs-def Let-def
      by(auto)
      from a-def True snd-action-not-none control-spec[THEN spec, THEN spec, THEN spec, where x2=?ns
      and x1=d and x=?na d]
    }
  }
}

```

$second\text{-}elt\text{-}is\text{-}hd\text{-}tl[\mathbf{where } x = hd(\text{execs } (current\ s)) \mathbf{and } a = hd(tl(hd(\text{execs } (current\ s)))) \mathbf{and } x' = tl(tl(hd(\text{execs } (current\ s))))]$
have $na\text{-}def: the\ ?a' = (hd(\text{execs } (current\ s)))!1$
unfolding $next\text{-}execs\text{-}def$
by $(auto)$
from $Some\ realistic[unfolding\ realistic\text{-}executions\text{-}ind\text{-}def, THEN\ spec, \mathbf{where } x = d]$ $True\ thread\text{-}not\text{-}empty$
obtain $n\ aseq'$ **where** $witness: n \leq length\ aseq' \wedge aseq' \in AS\text{-}set \wedge hd(\text{execs } d) = lastn\ n\ aseq'$
unfolding $realistic\text{-}AS\text{-}partial\text{-}def$ **by** $(cases\ \text{execs } d, auto)$
from $True\ executing\ length\text{-}lt\text{-}2\text{-}implies\text{-}tl\text{-}empty[\mathbf{where } x = hd(\text{execs } (current\ s))]$
 $Some\ control\text{-}spec[THEN\ spec, THEN\ spec, THEN\ spec, \mathbf{where } x2 = s \mathbf{and } x1 = d \mathbf{and } x = \text{execs } d]$
 $snd\text{-}action\text{-}not\text{-}none\ control\text{-}spec[THEN\ spec, THEN\ spec, THEN\ spec, \mathbf{where } x2 = ?ns \mathbf{and } x1 = d \mathbf{and } x = ?na\ d]$
have $in\text{-}action\text{-}sequence: length(hd(\text{execs } (current\ s))) \geq 2$
unfolding $next\text{-}action\text{-}def\ next\text{-}execs\text{-}def$
by $auto$
from $this\ witness\ consecutive\text{-}is\text{-}sub\text{-}seq[\mathbf{where } a = a \mathbf{and } b = the\ ?a' \mathbf{and } n = n \mathbf{and } y = aseq' \mathbf{and } x = tl(tl(hd(\text{execs } (current\ s))))]$
 $a\text{-}def\ na\text{-}def\ True\ in\text{-}action\text{-}sequence$
 $x\text{-}is\text{-}hd\text{-}snd\text{-}tl[\mathbf{where } x = hd(\text{execs } (current\ s))]$
have $I: \exists\ aseq' \in AS\text{-}set. is\text{-}sub\text{-}seq\ a\ (the\ ?a')\ aseq'$
by $(auto)$
from $True\ Some\ inv\text{-}sa[unfolding\ precondition\text{-}ind\text{-}def, THEN\ conjunct2, THEN\ spec, \mathbf{where } x = current\ s]$ $s\text{-}sa$
have $2: AS\text{-}precondition\ s\ (current\ s)\ a$
unfolding $strict\text{-}equal\text{-}def\ next\text{-}action\text{-}def\ B\text{-}def$ **by** $auto$
from $executing\ True\ Some\ control\text{-}spec[THEN\ spec, THEN\ spec, THEN\ spec, \mathbf{where } x2 = s \mathbf{and } x1 = d \mathbf{and } x = \text{execs } d]$
have $not\text{-}aborting: \neg aborting(next\text{-}state\ s\ \text{execs})\ (current\ s)\ (the\ ?a)$
unfolding $next\text{-}action\text{-}def\ next\text{-}state\text{-}def\ next\text{-}execs\text{-}def$
by $auto$
from $executing\ True\ Some\ control\text{-}spec[THEN\ spec, THEN\ spec, THEN\ spec, \mathbf{where } x2 = s \mathbf{and } x1 = d \mathbf{and } x = \text{execs } d]$
have $not\text{-}waiting: \neg waiting(next\text{-}state\ s\ \text{execs})\ (current\ s)\ (the\ ?a)$
unfolding $next\text{-}action\text{-}def\ next\text{-}state\text{-}def\ next\text{-}execs\text{-}def$
by $auto$
from $True\ this$
 $1\ 2\ inv\text{-}s$
 $sub\text{-}seq\text{-}in\text{-}prefixes[\mathbf{where } X = AS\text{-}set]$ $Some\ next\text{-}state\text{-}invariant$
 $current\text{-}next\text{-}state[THEN\ spec, THEN\ spec, \mathbf{where } x1 = s \mathbf{and } x = \text{execs}]$
 $AS\text{-}prec\text{-}after\text{-}step[THEN\ spec, THEN\ spec, THEN\ spec, \mathbf{where } x2 = next\text{-}state\ s\ \text{execs} \mathbf{and } x1 = a \mathbf{and } x = the\ ?a']$
 $next\text{-}state\text{-}precondition\ not\text{-}aborting\ not\text{-}waiting$
show $?thesis$
unfolding $step\text{-}def$
by $auto$
next
case $waiting$ — The kernel is delaying action a. Thus the action after a, which is a', is equal to a.
from $tl\text{-}hd\text{-}x\text{-}not\text{-}tl\text{-}x[\mathbf{where } x = \text{execs } d]$ $True\ waiting\ control\text{-}spec[THEN\ spec, THEN\ spec, THEN\ spec, \mathbf{where } x2 = s \mathbf{and } x1 = d \mathbf{and } x = \text{execs } d]$ $Some$
have $a\text{-}def: ?na\ d = \text{execs } (current\ s) \wedge next\text{-}state\ s\ \text{execs} = s \wedge waiting\ s\ d\ (the\ ?a)$
unfolding $next\text{-}action\text{-}def\ next\text{-}execs\text{-}def\ next\text{-}state\text{-}def$
by $(auto)$
from $Some\ waiting\ a\text{-}def\ True\ snd\text{-}action\text{-}not\text{-}none\ control\text{-}spec[THEN\ spec, THEN\ spec, THEN\ spec, \mathbf{where } x2 = ?ns \mathbf{and } x1 = d \mathbf{and } x = ?na\ d]$
have $na\text{-}def: the\ ?a' = hd(hd(\text{execs } (current\ s)))$
unfolding $next\text{-}action\text{-}def\ next\text{-}execs\text{-}def$
by $(auto)$

```

from spec-of-waiting a-def True
  have no-step: step s ?a = s unfolding step-def by (cases next-action s execs,auto)
from no-step Some True a-def
  inv-sa[unfolded precondition-ind-def,THEN conjunct2,THEN spec,where x=current s] s-sa
  have 2: AS-precondition s (current s) (the ?a')
  unfolding next-action-def B-def
  by(auto)
from a-def na-def this True Some no-step
  show ?thesis
  unfolding step-def
  by(auto)
qed
next
case None
  — Assuming that the current domain does not execute an action, and assuming that the action a' after that
  is not None (statement snd-action-not-none), we prove that the precondition is inductive, i.e., it will hold for a'.
  This holds, since the control mechanism will ensure that action a' is the start of a new action sequence in AS-set.

  from None True snd-action-not-none control-spec[THEN spec,THEN spec,THEN spec,where x2=?ns
and x1=d and x=?na d]
  control-spec[THEN spec,THEN spec,THEN spec,where x2=s and x1=d and x=execs d]
  have na-def: the ?a' = hd (hd (tl (execs (current s)))) ^ ?na d = tl (execs (current s))
  unfolding next-action-def next-exec-def
  by(auto)
  from True None snd-action-not-none control-spec[THEN spec,THEN spec,THEN spec,where x2=?ns
and x1=d and x=?na d]
  this
  have 1: tl (execs (current s)) ≠ [] ^ hd (tl (execs (current s))) ≠ []
  by auto
  from this realistic[unfolded realistic-executions-ind-def,THEN spec,where x=d] True thread-not-empty
  have hd (tl (execs (current s))) ∈ AS-set
  by (cases execs d,auto)
  from True snd-action-not-none this
  inv-ns this na-def 1
  AS-prec-first-action[THEN spec,THEN spec,THEN spec,where x2=?ns and x=hd (tl (execs (current
s))) and x1=d]
  show ?thesis by auto
  qed
}
thus ?thesis
  using control-spec[THEN spec,THEN spec,THEN spec,where x2=?ns and x1=current s and x=?na
(current s)]
  thread-not-empty True snd-action-not-none
  by (auto simp add: Let-def)
next
case False
  from False have equal-na-a: ?na d = execs d
  unfolding next-exec-def by auto
  from this False current-next-state next-action-after-step
  have ?a' = fst (control (next-state s execs) d (next-exec s execs d))
  unfolding next-action-def by auto
  from inv-sa[unfolded precondition-ind-def,THEN conjunct2,THEN spec,where x=d] s-sa equal-na-a this
next-action-after-next-state[THEN spec,THEN spec,THEN spec,where x=d and x2=s and x1=execs]
snd-action-not-none False
  have AS-precondition s d (the ?a')
  unfolding precondition-ind-def next-action-def B-def by (cases fst (control sa d (execs d)),auto)
  from equal-na-a False this next-state-precondition current-next-state

```

```

    AS-prec-dom-independent[THEN spec,THEN spec,THEN spec,THEN spec,where x3=next-state s execs
and x2=d and x=the ?a and x1=the ?a']
    show ?thesis
    unfolding step-def
    by (cases next-action s execs,auto)
  qed
}
hence fst (control ?ns d (?na d)) → AS-precondition ?ns d unfolding B-def
  by (cases fst (control ?ns d (?na d)),auto)
}
thus ?thesis by auto
qed
from this inv-ns show ?thesis
  unfolding precondition-ind-def B-def Let-def
  by (auto)
qed
from equal-ns-nsa realistic-na invariant-na s-sa IH[where sa=?ns]
  have equal-ns-nt: strict-equal (run n (Some ?ns) ?na) (run-total n (step (next-state sa execs) (next-action
sa execs)) (next-execs sa execs))
  by(auto)
}
from this current-s-sa thread-not-empty not-interrupt prec show ?case by auto
qed
}
hence thm-inductive: ∀ m s execs n . strict-equal m s ∧ realistic-executions-ind execs ∧ precondition-ind s execs
→ strict-equal (run n m execs) (run-total n s execs) by blast
have 1: strict-equal (Some s) s unfolding strict-equal-def by simp
have 2: realistic-executions-ind execs
proof-
{
  fix d
  have case execs d of [] ⇒ True | aseq # aseqs ⇒ realistic-AS-partial aseq ∧ set aseqs ⊆ AS-set
  proof(cases execs d,simp)
  case (Cons aseq aseqs)
  from Cons realistic-exec[unfolded realistic-executions-def,THEN spec,where x=d]
  have 0: length aseq ≤ length aseq ∧ aseq ∈ AS-set ∧ aseq = lastn (length aseq) aseq
  unfolding lastn-def realistic-execution-def by auto
  hence 1: realistic-AS-partial aseq unfolding realistic-AS-partial-def by auto
  from Cons realistic-exec[unfolded realistic-executions-def,THEN spec,where x=d]
  have 2: set aseqs ⊆ AS-set
  unfolding realistic-execution-def by auto
  from Cons 1 2 show ?thesis by auto
  qed
}
thus ?thesis unfolding realistic-executions-ind-def by auto
qed
have 3: precondition-ind s execs
proof-
{
  fix d
  {
  assume not-empty: fst (control s d (execs d)) ≠ None
  from not-empty realistic-exec[unfolded realistic-executions-def,THEN spec,where x=d]
  have current-aseq-is-realistic: hd (execs d) ∈ AS-set
  using control-spec[THEN spec,THEN spec,THEN spec,where x=execs d and x1=d and x2=s]
  unfolding realistic-execution-def by(cases execs d,auto)
  from not-empty current-aseq-is-realistic invariant AS-prec-first-action[THEN spec,THEN spec,THEN spec,

```

```

where  $x2=s$  and  $x1=d$  and  $x=hd$  (execs d)
  have AS-precondition s d (the fst (control s d (execs d)))
  using control-spec[THEN spec,THEN spec,THEN spec,where x=execs d and x1=d and x2=s]
  by auto
}
hence fst (control s d (execs d))  $\rightarrow$  AS-precondition s d
unfolding B-def
by (cases fst (control s d (execs d)),auto)
}
from this invariant show ?thesis unfolding precondition-ind-def by auto
qed
from thm-inductive 1 2 3 show ?thesis by auto
qed

```

Theorem `unwinding_implies_isecure` gives security for all realistic executions. For unrealistic executions, it holds vacuously and therefore does not tell us anything. In order to prove security for this refinement (i.e., for function `run_total`), we have to prove that purging yields realistic runs.

lemma *realistic-purge*:

```

shows  $\forall$  execs d . realistic-executions execs  $\longrightarrow$  realistic-executions (purge execs d)
proof-
{
  fix execs d
  assume realistic-executions execs
  hence realistic-executions (purge execs d)
  using someI[where  $P=$ realistic-execution and  $x=$ execs d]
  unfolding realistic-executions-def purge-def by (simp)
}
thus ?thesis by auto
qed

```

lemma *remove-gateway-comm-subset*:

```

shows set (remove-gateway-communications d exec)  $\subseteq$  set exec  $\cup$   $\{\{\}\}$ 
by (induct exec,auto)

```

lemma *realistic-ipurge-l*:

```

shows  $\forall$  execs d . realistic-executions execs  $\longrightarrow$  realistic-executions (ipurge-l execs d)
proof-
{
  fix execs d
  assume  $I$ : realistic-executions execs
  from empty-in-AS-set remove-gateway-comm-subset[where  $d=d$  and  $exec=$ execs d]  $I$  have realistic-executions (ipurge-l execs d)
  unfolding realistic-execution-def realistic-executions-def ipurge-l-def by (auto)
}
thus ?thesis by auto
qed

```

lemma *realistic-ipurge-r*:

```

shows  $\forall$  execs d . realistic-executions execs  $\longrightarrow$  realistic-executions (ipurge-r execs d)
proof-
{
  fix execs d
  assume  $I$ : realistic-executions execs
  from empty-in-AS-set remove-gateway-comm-subset[where  $d=d$  and  $exec=$ execs d]  $I$  have realistic-executions (ipurge-r execs d)
  using someI[where  $P=\lambda$   $x$  . realistic-execution x and  $x=$ execs d]
  unfolding realistic-execution-def realistic-executions-def ipurge-r-def by (auto)
}

```

```

}
thus ?thesis by auto
qed

```

We now have sufficient lemma's to prove security for `run_total`. The definition of security is similar to that in Section 2.2. It now assumes that the executions are realistic and concerns function `run_total` instead of function `run`.

definition *NI-unrelated-total::bool*

where *NI-unrelated-total*

$$\equiv \forall \text{ execs } a \ n. \text{ realistic-executions } \text{execs} \longrightarrow$$

$$\begin{aligned} & (\text{let } s\text{-}f = \text{run-total } n \ s0 \ \text{execs} \ \text{in} \\ & \text{output-f } s\text{-}f \ a = \text{output-f } (\text{run-total } n \ s0 \ (\text{purge } \text{execs} \ (\text{current } s\text{-}f))) \ a \\ & \wedge \text{current } s\text{-}f = \text{current } (\text{run-total } n \ s0 \ (\text{purge } \text{execs} \ (\text{current } s\text{-}f))) \end{aligned}$$

definition *NI-indirect-sources-total::bool*

where *NI-indirect-sources-total*

$$\equiv \forall \text{ execs } a \ n. \text{ realistic-executions } \text{execs} \longrightarrow$$

$$\begin{aligned} & (\text{let } s\text{-}f = \text{run-total } n \ s0 \ \text{execs} \ \text{in} \\ & \text{output-f } (\text{run-total } n \ s0 \ (\text{ipurge-l } \text{execs} \ (\text{current } s\text{-}f))) \ a = \\ & \text{output-f } (\text{run-total } n \ s0 \ (\text{ipurge-r } \text{execs} \ (\text{current } s\text{-}f))) \ a \end{aligned}$$

definition *isecure-total::bool*

where *isecure-total* \equiv *NI-unrelated-total* \wedge *NI-indirect-sources-total*

theorem *unwinding-implies-isecure-total:*

shows *isecure-total*

proof-

from *assms* *unwinding-implies-isecure* **have** *secure-partial: NI-unrelated* **unfolding** *isecure-def* **by** *blast*

from *assms* *unwinding-implies-isecure* **have** *isecure1-partial: NI-indirect-sources* **unfolding** *isecure-def* **by** *blast*

have *NI-unrelated-total: NI-unrelated-total*

proof-

{

fix *execs* *a* *n*

assume *realistic: realistic-executions* *execs*

from *assms* *invariant-s0* *realistic* *run-total-equals-run* [**where** *n=n* **and** *s=s0* **and** *execs=execs*]

have *1: strict-equal* (*run* *n* (*Some* *s0*) *execs*) (*run-total* *n* *s0* *execs*) **by** *auto*

have *let* *s-f* = *run-total* *n* *s0* *execs* *in* *output-f* *s-f* *a* = *output-f* (*run-total* *n* *s0* (*purge* *execs* (*current* *s-f*))) *a* \wedge *current* *s-f* = *current* (*run-total* *n* *s0* (*purge* *execs* (*current* *s-f*)))

proof (*cases* *run* *n* (*Some* *s0*) *execs*)

case *None*

thus ?thesis **using** *1* **unfolding** *NI-unrelated-total-def* *strict-equal-def* **by** *auto*

next

case (*Some* *s-f*)

from *realistic-purge* *assms* *invariant-s0* *realistic* *run-total-equals-run* [**where** *n=n* **and** *s=s0* **and** *execs=purge* *execs* (*current* *s-f*)]

have *2: strict-equal* (*run* *n* (*Some* *s0*) (*purge* *execs* (*current* *s-f*))) (*run-total* *n* *s0* (*purge* *execs* (*current* *s-f*)))

by *auto*

show ?thesis **proof**(*cases* *run* *n* (*Some* *s0*) (*purge* *execs* (*current* *s-f*)))

case *None*

from *2* *None* **show** ?thesis **using** *2* **unfolding** *NI-unrelated-total-def* *strict-equal-def* **by** *auto*

next

case (*Some* *s-f2*)

from (*run* *n* (*Some* *s0*) *execs* = *Some* *s-f*) *Some* *1* *2* *secure-partial*[*unfolded* *NI-unrelated-def*, *THEN* *spec*, *THEN* *spec*, *THEN* *spec*, **where** *x=n* **and** *x2=execs*]

```

    show ?thesis
    unfolding strict-equal-def NI-unrelated-def
    by(simp add: Let-def B-def B2-def)
  qed
  qed
}
thus ?thesis unfolding NI-unrelated-total-def by auto
qed
have NI-indirect-sources-total: NI-indirect-sources-total
proof-
{
  fix execs a n
  assume realistic: realistic-executions execs
  from assms invariant-s0 realistic run-total-equals-run[where n=n and s=s0 and execs=execs]
  have 1: strict-equal (run n (Some s0) execs) (run-total n s0 execs) by auto

  have let s-f = run-total n s0 execs in output-f (run-total n s0 (ipurge-l execs (current s-f))) a = output-f
(run-total n s0 (ipurge-r execs (current s-f))) a
  proof (cases run n (Some s0) execs)
  case None
    thus ?thesis using 1 unfolding NI-unrelated-total-def strict-equal-def by auto
  next
  case (Some s-f)
    from realistic-ipurge-l assms invariant-s0 realistic run-total-equals-run[where n=n and s=s0 and execs=ipurge-l
execs (current s-f)]
    have 2: strict-equal (run n (Some s0) (ipurge-l execs (current s-f))) (run-total n s0 (ipurge-l execs (current
s-f)))
    by auto
    from realistic-ipurge-r assms invariant-s0 realistic run-total-equals-run[where n=n and s=s0 and execs=ipurge-r
execs (current s-f)]
    have 3: strict-equal (run n (Some s0) (ipurge-r execs (current s-f))) (run-total n s0 (ipurge-r execs (current
s-f)))
    by auto

  show ?thesis proof(cases run n (Some s0) (ipurge-l execs (current s-f)))
  case None
    from 2 None show ?thesis using 2 unfolding NI-unrelated-total-def strict-equal-def by auto
  next
  case (Some s-ipurge-l)
    show ?thesis
    proof(cases run n (Some s0) (ipurge-r execs (current s-f)))
    case None
      from 3 None show ?thesis using 2 unfolding NI-unrelated-total-def strict-equal-def by auto
    next
    case (Some s-ipurge-r)
      from (run n (Some s0) execs = Some s-f) (run n (Some s0) (ipurge-l execs (current s-f)) = Some s-ipurge-l
Some 1 2 3 isecure1-partial[unfolded NI-indirect-sources-def, THEN spec, THEN spec, THEN spec, where
x=n and x2=execs]
      show ?thesis
      unfolding strict-equal-def NI-unrelated-def
      by(simp add: Let-def B-def B2-def)
    qed
  qed
  qed
}
thus ?thesis unfolding NI-indirect-sources-total-def by auto
qed

```

```

from NI-unrelated-total NI-indirect-sources-total show ?thesis unfolding isecure-total-def by auto
qed

end
end

```

2.4 CISK (Controlled Interruptible Separation Kernel)

```

theory CISK
imports ISK
begin

```

This section presents a generic model of a Controlled Interruptible Separation Kernel (CISK). It formulates security, i.e., intransitive noninterference. For a presentation of this model, see Section 2 of [3].

First, a locale is defined that defines all generic functions and all proof obligations (see Section 2.3 of [3]).

```

locale Controllable-Interruptible-Separation-Kernel = — CISK
fixes kstep :: 'state-t ⇒ 'action-t ⇒ 'state-t — Executes one atomic kernel action
and output-f :: 'state-t ⇒ 'action-t ⇒ 'output-t — Returns the observable behavior
and s0 :: 'state-t — The initial state
and current :: 'state-t ⇒ 'dom-t — Returns the currently active domain
and cswitch :: time-t ⇒ 'state-t ⇒ 'state-t — Performs a context switch
and interrupt :: time-t ⇒ bool — Returns t iff an interrupt occurs in the given state at the given time
and kinvolved :: 'action-t ⇒ 'dom-t set — Returns the set of domains that are involved in the given action
and ifp :: 'dom-t ⇒ 'dom-t ⇒ bool — The security policy.
and vpeq :: 'dom-t ⇒ 'state-t ⇒ 'state-t ⇒ bool — View partitioning equivalence
and AS-set :: ('action-t list) set — Returns a set of valid action sequences, i.e., the attack surface
and invariant :: 'state-t ⇒ bool — Returns an inductive state-invariant
and AS-precondition :: 'state-t ⇒ 'dom-t ⇒ 'action-t ⇒ bool — Returns the preconditions under which the given
action can be executed.
and aborting :: 'state-t ⇒ 'dom-t ⇒ 'action-t ⇒ bool — Returns true iff the action is aborted.
and waiting :: 'state-t ⇒ 'dom-t ⇒ 'action-t ⇒ bool — Returns true iff execution of the given action is delayed.
and set-error-code :: 'state-t ⇒ 'action-t ⇒ 'state-t — Sets an error code when actions are aborted.
assumes vpeq-transitive: ∀ a b c u. (vpeq u a b ∧ vpeq u b c) → vpeq u a c
and vpeq-symmetric: ∀ a b u. vpeq u a b → vpeq u b a
and vpeq-reflexive: ∀ a u. vpeq u a a
and ifp-reflexive: ∀ u. ifp u u
and weakly-step-consistent: ∀ s t u a. vpeq u s t ∧ vpeq (current s) s t ∧ invariant s ∧ AS-precondition s (current
s) a ∧ invariant t ∧ AS-precondition t (current t) a ∧ current s = current t → vpeq u (kstep s a) (kstep t a)
and locally-respects: ∀ a s u. ¬ifp (current s) u ∧ invariant s ∧ AS-precondition s (current s) a → vpeq u s
(kstep s a)
and output-consistent: ∀ a s t. vpeq (current s) s t ∧ current s = current t → (output-f s a) = (output-f t a)
and step-atomicity: ∀ s a. current (kstep s a) = current s
and cswitch-independent-of-state: ∀ n s t. current s = current t → current (cswitch n s) = current (cswitch n
t)
and cswitch-consistency: ∀ u s t n. vpeq u s t → vpeq u (cswitch n s) (cswitch n t)
and empty-in-AS-set: [] ∈ AS-set
and invariant-s0: invariant s0
and invariant-after-cswitch: ∀ s n. invariant s → invariant (cswitch n s)
and precondition-after-cswitch: ∀ s d n a. AS-precondition s d a → AS-precondition (cswitch n s) d a
and AS-prec-first-action: ∀ s d aseq. invariant s ∧ aseq ∈ AS-set ∧ aseq ≠ [] → AS-precondition s d (hd aseq)
and AS-prec-after-step: ∀ s a a'. (∃ aseq ∈ AS-set. is-sub-seq a a' aseq) ∧ invariant s ∧ AS-precondition s
(current s) a ∧ ¬aborting s (current s) a ∧ ¬waiting s (current s) a → AS-precondition (kstep s a) (current s)
a'

```

and AS-prec-dom-independent: $\forall s d a a' . \text{current } s \neq d \wedge \text{AS-precondition } s d a \longrightarrow \text{AS-precondition } (kstep s a') d a$
and spec-of-invariant: $\forall s a . \text{invariant } s \longrightarrow \text{invariant } (kstep s a)$
and aborting-switch-independent: $\forall n s . \text{aborting } (cswitch n s) = \text{aborting } s$
and aborting-error-update: $\forall s d a' a . \text{current } s \neq d \wedge \text{aborting } s d a \longrightarrow \text{aborting } (set-error-code s a') d a$
and aborting-after-step: $\forall s a d . \text{current } s \neq d \longrightarrow \text{aborting } (kstep s a) d = \text{aborting } s d$
and aborting-consistent: $\forall s t u . \text{vpeq } u s t \longrightarrow \text{aborting } s u = \text{aborting } t u$
and waiting-switch-independent: $\forall n s . \text{waiting } (cswitch n s) = \text{waiting } s$
and waiting-error-update: $\forall s d a' a . \text{current } s \neq d \wedge \text{waiting } s d a \longrightarrow \text{waiting } (set-error-code s a') d a$
and waiting-consistent: $\forall s t u a . \text{vpeq } (current s) s t \wedge (\forall d \in \text{kinvolved } a . \text{vpeq } d s t) \wedge \text{vpeq } u s t \longrightarrow \text{waiting } s u a = \text{waiting } t u a$
and spec-of-waiting: $\forall s a . \text{waiting } s (current s) a \longrightarrow kstep s a = s$
and set-error-consistent: $\forall s t u a . \text{vpeq } u s t \longrightarrow \text{vpeq } u (set-error-code s a) (set-error-code t a)$
and set-error-locally-respects: $\forall s u a . \neg \text{ifp } (current s) u \longrightarrow \text{vpeq } u s (set-error-code s a)$
and current-set-error-code: $\forall s a . \text{current } (set-error-code s a) = \text{current } s$
and precondition-after-set-error-code: $\forall s d a a' . \text{AS-precondition } s d a \wedge \text{aborting } s (current s) a' \longrightarrow \text{AS-precondition } (set-error-code s a') d a$
and invariant-after-set-error-code: $\forall s a . \text{invariant } s \longrightarrow \text{invariant } (set-error-code s a)$
and involved-ifp: $\forall s a . \forall d \in (\text{kinvolved } a) . \text{AS-precondition } s (current s) a \longrightarrow \text{ifp } d (current s)$
begin

2.4.1 Execution semantics

Control is based on generic functions *aborting*, *waiting* and *set_error_code*. Function *aborting* decides whether a certain action is aborting, given its domain and the state. If so, then function *set_error_code* will be used to update the state, possibly communicating to other domains that an action has been aborted. Function *waiting* can delay the execution of an action. This behavior is implemented in function *CISK_control*.

function *CISK-control* :: 'state-t \Rightarrow 'dom-t \Rightarrow 'action-t execution \Rightarrow ('action-t option \times 'action-t execution \times 'state-t)
where *CISK-control* $s d []$ = (None, [], s) — The thread is empty
| *CISK-control* $s d ([] \# [])$ = (None, [], s) — The current action sequence has been finished and the thread has no next action sequences to execute
| *CISK-control* $s d ([] \# (as' \# execs'))$ = (None, as' \# execs', s) — The current action sequence has been finished. Skip to the next sequence
| *CISK-control* $s d ((a \# as) \# execs')$ = (if *aborting* $s d a$ then
(None, execs', set-error-code s a)
else if *waiting* $s d a$ then
(Some a, (a \# as) \# execs', s)
else
(Some a, as \# execs', s)) — Executing an action sequence

by *pat-completeness auto*

termination by *lexicographic-order*

Function *run* defines the execution semantics. This function is presented in [3] by pseudo code (see Algorithm 1). Before defining the run function, we define accessor functions for the control mechanism. Functions *next_action*, *next_execs* and *next_state* correspond to “control.a”, “control.x” and “control.s” in [3].

abbreviation *next-action*:: 'state-t \Rightarrow ('dom-t \Rightarrow 'action-t execution) \Rightarrow 'action-t option
where *next-action* \equiv *Kernel.next-action* *current CISK-control*
abbreviation *next-exec*:: 'state-t \Rightarrow ('dom-t \Rightarrow 'action-t execution) \Rightarrow ('dom-t \Rightarrow 'action-t execution)
where *next-exec* \equiv *Kernel.next-exec* *current CISK-control*
abbreviation *next-state*:: 'state-t \Rightarrow ('dom-t \Rightarrow 'action-t execution) \Rightarrow 'state-t
where *next-state* \equiv *Kernel.next-state* *current CISK-control*

A thread is empty iff either it has no further action sequences to execute, or when the current action

sequence is finished and there are no further action sequences to execute.

abbreviation *thread-empty*::'action-t execution \Rightarrow bool

where *thread-empty exec* \equiv *exec* = [] \vee *exec* = [[]]

The following function defines the execution semantics of CISK, using function CISK_control.

function *run* :: *time-t* \Rightarrow '*state-t* \Rightarrow ('*dom-t* \Rightarrow '*action-t execution*) \Rightarrow '*state-t*

where *run 0 s execs* = *s*

| *interrupt (Suc n)* \Longrightarrow *run (Suc n) s execs* = *run n (cswitch (Suc n) s) execs*

| \neg *interrupt (Suc n)* \Longrightarrow *thread-empty(execs (current s))* \Longrightarrow *run (Suc n) s execs* = *run n s execs*

| \neg *interrupt (Suc n)* \Longrightarrow \neg *thread-empty(execs (current s))* \Longrightarrow

run (Suc n) s execs = (let *control-a* = *next-action s execs*;

control-s = *next-state s execs*;

control-x = *next-execs s execs* in

case *control-a* of *None* \Rightarrow *run n control-s control-x*

| (*Some a*) \Rightarrow *run n (kstep control-s a) control-x*)

using *not0-implies-Suc* **by** (*metis prod-cases3,auto*)

termination by *lexicographic-order*

2.4.2 Formulations of security

The definitions of security as presented in Section 2.2 of [3].

abbreviation *kprecondition*

where *kprecondition s a* \equiv *invariant s* \wedge *AS-precondition s (current s) a*

definition *realistic-execution*

where *realistic-execution aseq* \equiv *set aseq* \subseteq *AS-set*

definition *realistic-executions* :: ('*dom-t* \Rightarrow '*action-t execution*) \Rightarrow bool

where *realistic-executions execs* \equiv $\forall d$. *realistic-execution (execs d)*

abbreviation *involved* **where** *involved* \equiv *Kernel.involved kinvolved*

abbreviation *step* **where** *step* \equiv *Kernel.step kstep*

abbreviation *purge* **where** *purge* \equiv *Separation-Kernel.purge realistic-execution ifp*

abbreviation *ipurge-l* **where** *ipurge-l* \equiv *Separation-Kernel.ipurge-l kinvolved ifp*

abbreviation *ipurge-r* **where** *ipurge-r* \equiv *Separation-Kernel.ipurge-r realistic-execution kinvolved ifp*

definition *NI-unrelated*::bool

where *NI-unrelated*

\equiv \forall *execs a n*. *realistic-executions execs* \longrightarrow

(let *s-f* = *run n s0 execs* in

output-f s-f a = *output-f (run n s0 (purge execs (current s-f))) a*)

definition *NI-indirect-sources*::bool

where *NI-indirect-sources*

\equiv \forall *execs a n*. *realistic-executions execs* \longrightarrow

(let *s-f* = *run n s0 execs* in

output-f (run n s0 (ipurge-l execs (current s-f))) a =

output-f (run n s0 (ipurge-r execs (current s-f))) a)

definition *isecure*::bool

where *isecure* \equiv *NI-unrelated* \wedge *NI-indirect-sources*

2.4.3 Proofs

The final theorem is *unwinding_implies_isecure_CISK*. This theorem shows that any interpretation of locale CISK is secure.

To prove this theorem, the refinement framework is used. CISK is a refinement of ISK, as the only idfference is the control function. In ISK, this function is a generic function called *control*, in CISK it is interpreted in function *CISK_control*. It is proven that function *CISK_control* satisfies all the proof obligations concerning generic function *control*. In other words, *CISK_control* is proven to be an interpretation of control. Therefore, all theorems on *run_total* apply to the *run* function of CISK as well.

lemma *next-action-consistent*:

shows $\forall s t \text{ execs} . \text{vpeq} (\text{current } s) s t \wedge (\forall d \in \text{involved} (\text{next-action } s \text{ execs}) . \text{vpeq } d s t) \wedge \text{current } s = \text{current } t \longrightarrow \text{next-action } s \text{ execs} = \text{next-action } t \text{ execs}$

proof–

```
{
  fix s t execs
  assume vpeq: vpeq (current s) s t
  assume vpeq-involved:  $\forall d \in \text{involved} (\text{next-action } s \text{ execs}) . \text{vpeq } d s t$ 
  assume current-s-t: current s = current t
  from aborting-consistent current-s-t vpeq
  have aborting t (current s) = aborting s (current s) by auto
  from current-s-t this waiting-consistent vpeq-involved
  have next-action s execs = next-action t execs
  unfolding Kernel.next-action-def
  by(cases (s,(current s)),execs (current s)) rule: CISK-control.cases,auto)
}
thus ?thesis by auto
qed
```

lemma *next-execs-consistent*:

shows $\forall s t \text{ execs} . \text{vpeq} (\text{current } s) s t \wedge (\forall d \in \text{involved} (\text{next-action } s \text{ execs}) . \text{vpeq } d s t) \wedge \text{current } s = \text{current } t \longrightarrow \text{fst} (\text{snd} (\text{CISK-control } s (\text{current } s) (\text{execs} (\text{current } s)))) = \text{fst} (\text{snd} (\text{CISK-control } t (\text{current } s) (\text{execs} (\text{current } s))))$

proof–

```
{
  fix s t execs
  assume vpeq: vpeq (current s) s t
  assume vpeq-involved:  $\forall d \in \text{involved} (\text{next-action } s \text{ execs}) . \text{vpeq } d s t$ 
  assume current-s-t: current s = current t
  from aborting-consistent current-s-t vpeq
  have 1: aborting t (current s) = aborting s (current s) by auto
  from 1 vpeq current-s-t vpeq-involved waiting-consistent[THEN spec,THEN spec,THEN spec,THEN spec,where
x3=s and x2=t and x1=current s and x=the (next-action s execs)]
  have fst (snd (CISK-control s (current s) (execs (current s)))) = fst (snd (CISK-control t (current s) (execs
(current s))))
  unfolding Kernel.next-action-def Kernel.involved-def
  by(cases (s,(current s)),execs (current s)) rule: CISK-control.cases,auto split add: split-if-asm)
}
thus ?thesis by auto
qed
```

lemma *next-state-consistent*:

shows $\forall s t u \text{ execs} . \text{vpeq} (\text{current } s) s t \wedge \text{vpeq } u s t \wedge \text{current } s = \text{current } t \longrightarrow \text{vpeq } u (\text{next-state } s \text{ execs}) (\text{next-state } t \text{ execs})$

proof–

```
{
  fix s t u execs
  assume vpeq-s-t: vpeq (current s) s t  $\wedge$  vpeq u s t
  assume current-s-t: current s = current t
  from vpeq-s-t current-s-t
  have vpeq u (next-state s execs) (next-state t execs)
  unfolding Kernel.next-state-def
  using aborting-consistent set-error-consistent
  by(cases (s,(current s)),execs (current s)) rule: CISK-control.cases,auto)
}
thus ?thesis by auto
qed
```

lemma *current-next-state*:

shows $\forall s \text{ execs} . \text{current} (\text{next-state } s \text{ execs}) = \text{current } s$

proof–

```
{
  fix s execs
  have current (next-state s execs) = current s
    unfolding Kernel.next-state-def
    using current-set-error-code
    by(cases (s,(current s),execs (current s)) rule: CISK-control.cases,auto)
}
thus ?thesis by auto
qed
```

lemma *locally-respects-next-state*:

shows $\forall s u \text{ execs} . \neg \text{ifp} (\text{current } s) u \longrightarrow \text{vpeq } u s (\text{next-state } s \text{ execs})$

proof–

```
{
  fix s u execs
  assume  $\neg \text{ifp} (\text{current } s) u$ 
  hence vpeq u s (next-state s execs)
    unfolding Kernel.next-state-def
    using vpeq-reflexive set-error-locally-respects
    by(cases (s,(current s),execs (current s)) rule: CISK-control.cases,auto)
}
thus ?thesis by auto
qed
```

lemma *CISK-control-spec*:

shows $\forall s d \text{ aseqs} .$

case *CISK-control* $s d \text{ aseqs}$ of
 $(a, \text{aseqs}', s') \Rightarrow$
 $\text{thread-empty } \text{aseqs} \wedge (a, \text{aseqs}') = (\text{None}, []) \vee$
 $\text{aseqs} \neq [] \wedge \text{hd } \text{aseqs} \neq [] \wedge \neg \text{aborting } s' d (\text{the } a) \wedge \neg \text{waiting } s' d (\text{the } a) \wedge (a, \text{aseqs}') = (\text{Some } (\text{hd } (\text{hd } \text{aseqs})), \text{tl } (\text{hd } \text{aseqs}) \# \text{tl } \text{aseqs}) \vee$
 $\text{aseqs} \neq [] \wedge \text{hd } \text{aseqs} \neq [] \wedge \text{waiting } s' d (\text{the } a) \wedge (a, \text{aseqs}', s') = (\text{Some } (\text{hd } (\text{hd } \text{aseqs})), \text{aseqs}, s) \vee (a, \text{aseqs}') = (\text{None}, \text{tl } \text{aseqs})$

proof–

```
{
  fix s d aseqs
  have case CISK-control s d aseqs of
    (a, aseqs', s')  $\Rightarrow$ 
      thread-empty aseqs  $\wedge$  (a, aseqs') = (None, [])  $\vee$ 
      aseqs  $\neq$  []  $\wedge$  hd aseqs  $\neq$  []  $\wedge$   $\neg$  aborting s' d (the a)  $\wedge$   $\neg$  waiting s' d (the a)  $\wedge$  (a, aseqs') = (Some (hd (hd aseqs)), tl (hd aseqs) # tl aseqs)  $\vee$ 
      aseqs  $\neq$  []  $\wedge$  hd aseqs  $\neq$  []  $\wedge$  waiting s' d (the a)  $\wedge$  (a, aseqs', s') = (Some (hd (hd aseqs)), aseqs, s)  $\vee$  (a, aseqs') = (None, tl aseqs)
  by(cases (s,d,aseqs) rule: CISK-control.cases,auto)
}
thus ?thesis by auto
qed
```

lemma *next-action-after-cswitch*:

shows $\forall s n d \text{ aseqs} . \text{fst} (\text{CISK-control} (\text{cswitch } n s) d \text{ aseqs}) = \text{fst} (\text{CISK-control } s d \text{ aseqs})$

proof–

```
{
  fix s n d aseqs
```

```

have fst (CISK-control (cswitch n s) d aseqs) = fst (CISK-control s d aseqs)
using aborting-switch-independent waiting-switch-independent
by(cases (s,d,aseqs) rule: CISK-control.cases,auto)
}
thus ?thesis by auto
qed

```

lemma next-action-after-next-state:

```

shows  $\forall s \text{ execs } d . \text{current } s \neq d \longrightarrow \text{fst (CISK-control (next-state s execs) d (execs d))} = \text{None} \vee \text{fst (CISK-control (next-state s execs) d (execs d))} = \text{fst (CISK-control s d (execs d))}$ 
proof-
{
  fix s execs d aseqs
  assume I: current s  $\neq$  d
  have fst (CISK-control (next-state s execs) d aseqs) = None  $\vee$  fst (CISK-control (next-state s execs) d aseqs) = fst (CISK-control s d aseqs)
  proof(cases (s,d,aseqs) rule: CISK-control.cases,simp,simp,simp)
  case (4 sa da a as execs')
    thus ?thesis
      unfolding Kernel.next-state-def
      using aborting-error-update waiting-error-update I
      by(cases (sa,current sa,execs (current sa)) rule: CISK-control.cases,auto split: split-if-asm)
    qed
}
thus ?thesis by auto
qed

```

lemma next-action-after-step:

```

shows  $\forall s a d \text{ aseqs} . \text{current } s \neq d \longrightarrow \text{fst (CISK-control (step s a) d aseqs)} = \text{fst (CISK-control s d aseqs)}$ 
proof-
{
  fix s a d aseqs
  assume I: current s  $\neq$  d
  from this aborting-after-step
  have fst (CISK-control (step s a) d aseqs) = fst (CISK-control s d aseqs)
  unfolding Kernel.step-def
  by(cases (s,d,aseqs) rule: CISK-control.cases,simp,simp,simp,cases a,auto)
}
thus ?thesis by auto
qed

```

lemma next-state-precondition:

```

shows  $\forall s d a \text{ execs} . \text{AS-precondition } s d a \longrightarrow \text{AS-precondition (next-state s execs) d a}$ 
proof-
{
  fix s a d execs
  assume AS-precondition s d a
  hence AS-precondition (next-state s execs) d a
  unfolding Kernel.next-state-def
  using precondition-after-set-error-code
  by(cases (s,(current s),execs (current s)) rule: CISK-control.cases,auto)
}
thus ?thesis by auto
qed

```

lemma next-state-invariant:

shows $\forall s \text{ execs. invariant } s \longrightarrow \text{invariant } (\text{next-state } s \text{ execs})$

proof-

```
{
  fix s execs
  assume invariant s
  hence invariant (next-state s execs)
  unfolding Kernel.next-state-def
  using invariant-after-set-error-code
  by(cases (s,(current s),execs (current s)) rule: CISK-control.cases,auto)
}
thus ?thesis by auto
qed
```

lemma *next-action-from-execs*:

shows $\forall s \text{ execs} . \text{next-action } s \text{ execs} \rightarrow (\lambda a . a \in \text{actions-in-execution } (\text{execs } (\text{current } s)))$

proof-

```
{
  fix s execs
  {
    fix a
    assume I: next-action s execs = Some a
    from I have a ∈ actions-in-execution (execs (current s))
    unfolding Kernel.next-action-def actions-in-execution-def
    by (cases (s,(current s),execs (current s)) rule: CISK-control.cases,auto split add: split-if-asm)
  }
  hence next-action s execs → (λ a . a ∈ actions-in-execution (execs (current s)))
  unfolding B-def
  by (cases next-action s execs,auto)
}
thus ?thesis unfolding B-def by (auto)
qed
```

lemma *next-execs-subset*:

shows $\forall s \text{ execs } u . \text{actions-in-execution } (\text{next-execs } s \text{ execs } u) \subseteq \text{actions-in-execution } (\text{execs } u)$

proof-

```
{
  fix s execs u
  have actions-in-execution (next-execs s execs u) ⊆ actions-in-execution (execs u)
  unfolding Kernel.next-execs-def actions-in-execution-def
  by (cases (s,(current s),execs (current s)) rule: CISK-control.cases,auto split add: split-if-asm)
}
thus ?thesis by auto
qed
```

theorem *unwinding-implies-isecure-CISK*:

shows *isecure*

proof-

interpret *int*: *Interruptible-Separation-Kernel kstep output-fs0 current cswitch interrupt kprecondition realistic-execution CISK-control kinvolved ifp vpeq AS-set invariant AS-precondition aborting waiting*

proof (*unfold-locales*)

show $\forall a b c u. vpeq u a b \wedge vpeq u b c \longrightarrow vpeq u a c$

using *vpeq-transitive* **by** *blast*

show $\forall a b u. vpeq u a b \longrightarrow vpeq u b a$

using *vpeq-symmetric* **by** *blast*

show $\forall a u. vpeq u a a$

using *vpeq-reflexive* **by** *blast*

```

show  $\forall u. \text{ifp } u \ u$ 
using ifp-reflexive by blast
show  $\forall s \ t \ u \ a. \text{vpeq } u \ s \ t \wedge \text{vpeq } (\text{current } s) \ s \ t \wedge \text{kprecondition } s \ a \wedge \text{kprecondition } t \ a \wedge \text{current } s = \text{current } t$ 
 $\longrightarrow \text{vpeq } u \ (\text{kstep } s \ a) \ (\text{kstep } t \ a)$ 
using weakly-step-consistent by blast
show  $\forall a \ s \ u. \neg \text{ifp } (\text{current } s) \ u \wedge \text{kprecondition } s \ a \longrightarrow \text{vpeq } u \ s \ (\text{kstep } s \ a)$ 
using locally-respects by blast
show  $\forall a \ s \ t. \text{vpeq } (\text{current } s) \ s \ t \wedge \text{current } s = \text{current } t \longrightarrow (\text{output-f } s \ a) = (\text{output-f } t \ a)$ 
using output-consistent by blast
show  $\forall s \ a. \text{current } (\text{kstep } s \ a) = \text{current } s$ 
using step-atomicity by blast
show  $\forall n \ s \ t. \text{current } s = \text{current } t \longrightarrow \text{current } (\text{cswitch } n \ s) = \text{current } (\text{cswitch } n \ t)$ 
using cswitch-independent-of-state by blast
show  $\forall u \ s \ t \ n. \text{vpeq } u \ s \ t \longrightarrow \text{vpeq } u \ (\text{cswitch } n \ s) \ (\text{cswitch } n \ t)$ 
using cswitch-consistency by blast
show  $\forall s \ t \ \text{execs}. \text{vpeq } (\text{current } s) \ s \ t \wedge (\forall d \in \text{involved } (\text{next-action } s \ \text{execs}) . \text{vpeq } d \ s \ t) \wedge \text{current } s = \text{current } t$ 
 $\longrightarrow \text{next-action } s \ \text{execs} = \text{next-action } t \ \text{execs}$ 
using next-action-consistent by blast
show  $\forall s \ t \ \text{execs}.$ 
 $\text{vpeq } (\text{current } s) \ s \ t \wedge (\forall d \in \text{involved } (\text{next-action } s \ \text{execs}) . \text{vpeq } d \ s \ t) \wedge \text{current } s = \text{current } t \longrightarrow$ 
 $\text{fst } (\text{snd } (\text{CISK-control } s \ (\text{current } s) \ (\text{execs } (\text{current } s)))) = \text{fst } (\text{snd } (\text{CISK-control } t \ (\text{current } s) \ (\text{execs } (\text{current } s))))$ 
using next-execs-consistent by blast
show  $\forall s \ t \ u \ \text{execs}. \text{vpeq } (\text{current } s) \ s \ t \wedge \text{vpeq } u \ s \ t \wedge \text{current } s = \text{current } t \longrightarrow \text{vpeq } u \ (\text{next-state } s \ \text{execs})$ 
 $(\text{next-state } t \ \text{execs})$ 
using next-state-consistent by auto
show  $\forall s \ \text{execs}. \text{current } (\text{next-state } s \ \text{execs}) = \text{current } s$ 
using current-next-state by auto
show  $\forall s \ u \ \text{execs}. \neg \text{ifp } (\text{current } s) \ u \longrightarrow \text{vpeq } u \ s \ (\text{next-state } s \ \text{execs})$ 
using locally-respects-next-state by auto
show  $[] \in \text{AS-set}$ 
using empty-in-AS-set by blast
show  $\forall s \ n. \text{invariant } s \longrightarrow \text{invariant } (\text{cswitch } n \ s)$ 
using invariant-after-cswitch by blast
show  $\forall s \ d \ n \ a. \text{AS-precondition } s \ d \ a \longrightarrow \text{AS-precondition } (\text{cswitch } n \ s) \ d \ a$ 
using precondition-after-cswitch by blast
show invariant s0
using invariant-s0 by blast
show  $\forall s \ d \ \text{aseq}. \text{invariant } s \wedge \text{aseq} \in \text{AS-set} \wedge \text{aseq} \neq [] \longrightarrow \text{AS-precondition } s \ d \ (\text{hd } \text{aseq})$ 
using AS-prec-first-action by blast
show  $\forall s \ a \ a'. (\exists \text{aseq} \in \text{AS-set}. \text{is-sub-seq } a \ a' \ \text{aseq}) \wedge \text{invariant } s \wedge \text{AS-precondition } s \ (\text{current } s) \ a \wedge \neg$ 
 $\text{aborting } s \ (\text{current } s) \ a \wedge \neg \text{waiting } s \ (\text{current } s) \ a \longrightarrow$ 
 $\text{AS-precondition } (\text{kstep } s \ a) \ (\text{current } s) \ a'$ 
using AS-prec-after-step by blast
show  $\forall s \ d \ a \ a'. \text{current } s \neq d \wedge \text{AS-precondition } s \ d \ a \longrightarrow \text{AS-precondition } (\text{kstep } s \ a') \ d \ a$ 
using AS-prec-dom-independent by blast
show  $\forall s \ a. \text{invariant } s \longrightarrow \text{invariant } (\text{kstep } s \ a)$ 
using spec-of-invariant by blast
show  $\wedge s \ a. \text{kprecondition } s \ a \equiv \text{kprecondition } s \ a$ 
by auto
show  $\wedge \text{aseq}. \text{realistic-execution } \text{aseq} \equiv \text{set } \text{aseq} \subseteq \text{AS-set}$ 
unfolding realistic-execution-def
by auto
show  $\forall s \ a. \forall d \in \text{involved } a. \text{kprecondition } s \ (\text{the } a) \longrightarrow \text{ifp } d \ (\text{current } s)$ 
using involved-ifp unfolding Kernel.involved-def by (auto split: option.splits)
show  $\forall s \ \text{execs}. \text{next-action } s \ \text{execs} \rightarrow (\lambda a. a \in \text{actions-in-execution } (\text{execs } (\text{current } s)))$ 
using next-action-from-execs by blast

```

show $\forall s \text{ execs } u. \text{actions-in-execution (next-execs } s \text{ execs } u) \subseteq \text{actions-in-execution (execs } u)$
using *next-execs-subset* **by** *blast*
show $\forall s \text{ } d \text{ aseqs.}$
case CISK-control $s \text{ } d \text{ aseqs of}$
 $(a, \text{aseqs}', s') \Rightarrow$
 $\text{thread-empty aseqs} \wedge (a, \text{aseqs}') = (\text{None}, []) \vee$
 $\text{aseqs} \neq [] \wedge \text{hd aseqs} \neq [] \wedge \neg \text{aborting } s' \text{ } d \text{ (the } a) \wedge \neg \text{waiting } s' \text{ } d \text{ (the } a) \wedge (a, \text{aseqs}') = (\text{Some (hd (hd aseqs))), \text{tl (hd aseqs)} \# \text{tl aseqs}) \vee$
 $\text{aseqs} \neq [] \wedge \text{hd aseqs} \neq [] \wedge \text{waiting } s' \text{ } d \text{ (the } a) \wedge (a, \text{aseqs}', s') = (\text{Some (hd (hd aseqs))), \text{aseqs}, s) \vee (a, \text{aseqs}') = (\text{None}, \text{tl aseqs})$
using *CISK-control-spec* **by** *blast*
show $\forall s \text{ } n \text{ } d \text{ aseqs. fst (CISK-control (cswitch } n \text{ } s) \text{ } d \text{ aseqs}) = \text{fst (CISK-control } s \text{ } d \text{ aseqs)}$
using *next-action-after-cswitch* **by** *auto*
show $\forall s \text{ execs } d.$
 $\text{current } s \neq d \longrightarrow$
 $\text{fst (CISK-control (next-state } s \text{ execs) } d \text{ (execs } d)) = \text{None} \vee \text{fst (CISK-control (next-state } s \text{ execs) } d \text{ (execs } d)) = \text{fst (CISK-control } s \text{ } d \text{ (execs } d))$
using *next-action-after-next-state* **by** *auto*
show $\forall s \text{ } a \text{ } d \text{ aseqs. current } s \neq d \longrightarrow \text{fst (CISK-control (step } s \text{ } a) \text{ } d \text{ aseqs}) = \text{fst (CISK-control } s \text{ } d \text{ aseqs)}$
using *next-action-after-step* **by** *auto*
show $\forall s \text{ } d \text{ } a \text{ execs. AS-precondition } s \text{ } d \text{ } a \longrightarrow \text{AS-precondition (next-state } s \text{ execs) } d \text{ } a$
using *next-state-precondition* **by** *auto*
show $\forall s \text{ execs. invariant } s \longrightarrow \text{invariant (next-state } s \text{ execs)}$
using *next-state-invariant* **by** *auto*
show $\forall s \text{ } a. \text{waiting } s \text{ (current } s) \text{ } a \longrightarrow \text{kstep } s \text{ } a = s$
using *spec-of-waiting* **by** *blast*
qed

note *interpreted* = *(Interruptible-Separation-Kernel kstep output-f s0 current cswitch kprecondition realistic-execution CISK-control kinvolved ifp vpeq AS-set invariant AS-precondition aborting waiting)*
note *run-total-induct* = *Interruptible-Separation-Kernel.run-total.induct[of kstep output-f s0 current cswitch kprecondition realistic-execution CISK-control kinvolved ifp vpeq AS-set invariant AS-precondition aborting waiting - interrupt]*

have *run-equals-run-total*:
 $\wedge n \text{ } s \text{ execs. run } n \text{ } s \text{ execs} \equiv \text{Interruptible-Separation-Kernel.run-total kstep current cswitch interrupt CISK-control } n \text{ } s \text{ execs}$
proof–
fix $n \text{ } s \text{ execs}$
show $\text{run } n \text{ } s \text{ execs} \equiv \text{Interruptible-Separation-Kernel.run-total kstep current cswitch interrupt CISK-control } n \text{ } s \text{ execs}$
using *interpreted int.step-def*
by (*induct* $n \text{ } s \text{ execs rule: run-total-induct, auto split: option.splits$)
qed
from *interpreted*
have 0: *Interruptible-Separation-Kernel.isecure-total kstep output-f s0 current cswitch interrupt realistic-execution CISK-control kinvolved ifp*
by (*metis int.unwinding-implies-isecure-total*)
from 0 *run-equals-run-total*
have 1: *NI-unrelated*
by (*metis realistic-executions-def int.isecure-total-def int.realistic-executions-def int.NI-unrelated-total-def NI-unrelated-def*)
from 0 *run-equals-run-total*
have 2: *NI-indirect-sources*
by (*metis realistic-executions-def int.NI-indirect-sources-total-def int.isecure-total-def int.realistic-executions-def NI-indirect-sources-def*)
from 1 2 **show** *?thesis unfolding isecure-def by auto*

qed

end
end

3 Instantiation by a separation kernel with concrete actions

In the previous section, no concrete actions for the step function were given. The foremost point we want to make by this instantiation is to show that we can instantiate the CISK model of the previous section with an implementation that, for the step function, as actions, provides events and interprocess communication (IPC). System call invocations that can be interrupted at certain interrupt points are split into several atomic steps. A communication interface of events and IPC is less “trivial” than it may seem it at a first glance, for example the L4 microkernel API *only* provided IPC as communication primitive [1]. In particular, the concrete actions illustrate how an application of the CISK framework can be used to separate policy enforcement from other computations unrelated to policy enforcement.

Our separation kernel instantiation also has a notion of *partitions*. A *partition* is a logical unit that serves to encapsulate a group of CISK threads by, amongst others, enforcing a static per-partition access control policy to system resources. In the following instantiation, while the subjects of the step function are individual threads, the information flow policy *ifp* is defined at the granularity of partitions, which is realistic for many separation kernel implementations.

Lastly, as a limited manipulation of an access control policy is often needed, we also provide an invariant for having a dynamic access control policy whose maximal closure is bounded by the static per-partition access control policy. That the dynamic access control policy is a subset of a static access control policy is expressed by the invariant *sp_subset*. A use case for this is when you have statically configured access to files by subjects, but whether a file can be read/written also depends on whether the file has been dynamically opened or not. The instantiation provides infrastructure for such an invariant on the relation of a dynamic policy to a static policy, and shows how the invariant is maintained, without modeling any API for an open/close operation.

3.1 Model of a separation kernel configuration

```
theory step-configuration
  imports Main
begin
```

3.1.1 Type definitions

The separation kernel partitions are considered to be the “subjects” of the information flow policy *ifp*. A file provider is a partition that, via a file API (read/write), provides files to other partitions. The configuration statically defines which partitions can act as a file provider and also the access rights (right/write) of other partitions to the files provided by the file provider. Some separation kernels include a management for address spaces (tasks), that may be hierachically structured. Such a task hierarchy is not part of this model.

```
typedefcl partition-id-t
typedefcl thread-id-t
```

```
typedefcl page-t — physical address of a memory page
typedefcl filep-t — name of file provider
```

```
datatype obj-id-t =
  PAGE page-t
| FILEP filep-t
```

```
datatype mode-t =
```

READ — The subject has right to read from the memory page, from the files served by a file provider.
| *WRITE* — The subject has right to write to the memory page, from the files served by a file provider.
| *PROVIDE* — The subject has right serve as the file provider. This mode is not used for memory pages or ports.

3.1.2 Configuration

The information flow policy is implicitly specified by the configuration. The configuration does not contain the communication rights between partitions (subjects). However, the rights can be derived from the configuration. For example, if two partitions p and p' can access a file f , then p and p' can communicate. See below.

consts

configured-subj-obj :: *partition-id-t* \Rightarrow *obj-id-t* \Rightarrow *mode-t* \Rightarrow *bool*

Each user thread belongs to a partition. The relation is fixed at system startup. The configuration specifies how many threads a partition can create, but this limit is not part of the model.

consts

partition :: *thread-id-t* \Rightarrow *partition-id-t*

end

3.2 Formulation of a subject-subject communication policy and an information flow policy, and showing both can be derived from subject-object configuration data

theory *step-policies*

imports *step-configuration*

begin

3.2.1 Specification

In order to use CISK, we need an information flow policy *ifp* relation. We also express a static subject-subject *sp-spec-subj-obj* and subject-object *sp-spec-subj-subj* access control policy for the implementation of the model. The following locale summarizes all properties we need.

locale *policy-axioms* =

fixes *sp-spec-subj-obj* :: '*a* \Rightarrow *obj-id-t* \Rightarrow *mode-t* \Rightarrow *bool*

and *sp-spec-subj-subj* :: '*a* \Rightarrow '*a* \Rightarrow *bool*

and *ifp* :: '*a* \Rightarrow '*a* \Rightarrow *bool*

assumes *sp-spec-file-provider*: $\forall p1 p2 f m1 m2 .$

sp-spec-subj-obj $p1$ (*FILEP* f) $m1 \wedge$

sp-spec-subj-obj $p2$ (*FILEP* f) $m2 \longrightarrow sp-spec-subj-subj p1 p2$

and *sp-spec-no-wronly-pages*:

$\forall p x . sp-spec-subj-obj p$ (*PAGE* x) *WRITE* $\longrightarrow sp-spec-subj-obj p$ (*PAGE* x) *READ*

and *ifp-reflexive*:

$\forall p . ifp p p$

and *ifp-compatible-with-sp-spec*:

$\forall a b . sp-spec-subj-subj a b \longrightarrow ifp a b \wedge ifp b a$

and *ifp-compatible-with-ipc*:

$\forall a b c x . (sp-spec-subj-subj a b$

$\wedge sp-spec-subj-obj b$ (*PAGE* x) *WRITE* $\wedge sp-spec-subj-obj c$ (*PAGE* x) *READ*)

$\longrightarrow ifp a c$

begin end

3.2.2 Derivation

The configuration data only consists of a subject-object policy. We derive the subject-subject policy and the information flow policy from the configuration data and prove that properties we specified in Section 3.2.1 are satisfied.

locale *abstract-policy-derivation* =
fixes *configuration-subj-obj* :: 'a ⇒ obj-id-t ⇒ mode-t ⇒ bool
begin

definition *sp-spec-subj-obj a x m* ≡
configuration-subj-obj a x m ∨ (∃ y . x = PAGE y ∧ m = READ ∧ *configuration-subj-obj a x WRITE*)

definition *sp-spec-subj-subj a b* ≡
 ∃ f m1 m2 . *sp-spec-subj-obj a (FILEP f) m1* ∧ *sp-spec-subj-obj b (FILEP f) m2*

definition *ifp a b* ≡
sp-spec-subj-subj a b
 ∨ *sp-spec-subj-subj b a*
 ∨ (∃ c y . *sp-spec-subj-subj a c*
 ∧ *sp-spec-subj-obj c (PAGE y) WRITE*
 ∧ *sp-spec-subj-obj b (PAGE y) READ*)
 ∨ (a = b)

Show that the policies specified in Section 3.2.1 can be derived from the configuration and their definitions.

lemma *correct*:

shows *policy-axioms sp-spec-subj-obj sp-spec-subj-subj ifp*

proof (*unfold-locales*)

show *sp-spec-file-provider*:

∃ p1 p2 f m1 m2 .
sp-spec-subj-obj p1 (FILEP f) m1 ∧
sp-spec-subj-obj p2 (FILEP f) m2 → *sp-spec-subj-subj p1 p2*

unfolding *sp-spec-subj-subj-def* **by** *auto*

show *sp-spec-no-wronly-pages*:

∃ p x . *sp-spec-subj-obj p (PAGE x) WRITE* → *sp-spec-subj-obj p (PAGE x) READ*

unfolding *sp-spec-subj-obj-def* **by** *auto*

show *ifp-reflexive*:

∃ p . *ifp p p*

unfolding *ifp-def* **by** *auto*

show *ifp-compatible-with-sp-spec*:

∃ a b . *sp-spec-subj-subj a b* → *ifp a b* ∧ *ifp b a*

unfolding *ifp-def* **by** *auto*

show *ifp-compatible-with-ipc*:

∃ a b c x . (*sp-spec-subj-subj a b*
 ∧ *sp-spec-subj-obj b (PAGE x) WRITE* ∧ *sp-spec-subj-obj c (PAGE x) READ*)
 → *ifp a c*

unfolding *ifp-def* **by** *auto*

qed

end

type-synonym *sp-subj-subj-t* = *partition-id-t* ⇒ *partition-id-t* ⇒ bool

type-synonym *sp-subj-obj-t* = *partition-id-t* ⇒ *obj-id-t* ⇒ *mode-t* ⇒ bool

interpretation *Policy*: *abstract-policy-derivation configured-subj-obj*.

interpretation *Policy-properties*: *policy-axioms Policy.sp-spec-subj-obj Policy.sp-spec-subj-subj Policy.ifp*

using *Policy.correct* **by** *auto*

lemma *example-how-to-use-properties-in-proofs*:
shows $\forall p . \text{Policy.ifp } p \ p$
using *Policy-properties.ifp-reflexive* **by** *auto*

end

3.3 Separation kernel state and atomic step function

theory *step*
imports *step-policies*
begin

3.3.1 Interrupt points

To model concurrency, each system call is split into several atomic steps, while allowing interrupts between the steps. The state of a thread is represented by an “interrupt point” (which corresponds to the value of the program counter saved by the system when a thread is interrupted).

datatype *ipc-direction-t* = *SEND* | *RECV*
datatype *ipc-stage-t* = *PREP* | *WAIT* | *BUF* *page-t*

datatype *ev-consume-t* = *EV-CONSUME-ALL* | *EV-CONSUME-ONE*
datatype *ev-wait-stage-t* = *EV-PREP* | *EV-WAIT* | *EV-FINISH*
datatype *ev-signal-stage-t* = *EV-SIGNAL-PREP* | *EV-SIGNAL-FINISH*

datatype *int-point-t* =
SK-IPC ipc-direction-t ipc-stage-t thread-id-t page-t — The thread is executing a sending / receiving IPC.
| *SK-EV-WAIT ev-wait-stage-t ev-consume-t* — The thread is waiting for an event.
| *SK-EV-SIGNAL ev-signal-stage-t thread-id-t* — The thread is sending an event.
| *NONE* — The thread is not executing any system call.

3.3.2 System state

typeddecl *obj-t* — value of an object

Each thread belongs to a partition. The relation is fixed (in this instantiation of a separation kernel).

consts
partition :: *thread-id-t* \Rightarrow *partition-id-t*

The state contains the dynamic policy (the communication rights in the current state of the system, for example).

record *thread-t* =

ev-counter :: *nat* — event counter

record *state-t* =
sp-impl-subj-subj :: *sp-subj-subj-t* — current subject-subject policy
sp-impl-subj-obj :: *sp-subj-obj-t* — current subject-object policy
current :: *thread-id-t* — current thread
obj :: *obj-id-t* \Rightarrow *obj-t* — values of all objects
thread :: *thread-id-t* \Rightarrow *thread-t* — internal state of threads

Later (Section 3.4), the system invariant *sp-subset* will be used to ensure that the dynamic policies (*sp_impl_...*) are a subset of the corresponding static policies (*sp_spec_...*).

3.3.3 Atomic step

Helper functions Set new value for an object.

definition *set-object-value* :: *obj-id-t* \Rightarrow *obj-t* \Rightarrow *state-t* \Rightarrow *state-t* **where**

set-object-value *obj-id* *val* *s* =
 s (\mid *obj* := *fun-upd* (*obj* *s*) *obj-id* *val* \mid)

Return a representation of the opposite direction of IPC communication.

definition *opposite-ipc-direction* :: *ipc-direction-t* \Rightarrow *ipc-direction-t* **where**

opposite-ipc-direction *dir* \equiv *case dir of SEND* \Rightarrow *RECV* \mid *RECV* \Rightarrow *SEND*

Add an access right from one partition to an object. In this model, not available from the API, but shows how dynamic changes of access rights could be implemented.

definition *add-access-right* :: *partition-id-t* \Rightarrow *obj-id-t* \Rightarrow *mode-t* \Rightarrow *state-t* \Rightarrow *state-t* **where**

add-access-right *part-id* *obj-id* *m* *s* =
 s (\mid *sp-impl-subj-obj* := λ *q* *q'* *q''*. (*part-id* = *q* \wedge *obj-id* = *q'* \wedge *m* = *q''*)
 \vee *sp-impl-subj-obj* *s* *q* *q'* \mid)

Add a communication right from one partition to another. In this model, not available from the API.

definition *add-comm-right* :: *partition-id-t* \Rightarrow *partition-id-t* \Rightarrow *state-t* \Rightarrow *state-t* **where**

add-comm-right *p* *p'* *s* \equiv
 s (\mid *sp-impl-subj-subj* := λ *q* *q'*. (*p* = *q* \wedge *p'* = *q'*) \vee *sp-impl-subj-subj* *s* *q* *q'* \mid)

Model of IPC system call We model IPC with the following simplifications:

1. The model contains the system calls for sending an IPC (SEND) and receiving an IPC (RECV), often implementations have a richer API (e.g. combining SEND and RECV in one invocation).
2. We model only a copying (“BUF”) mode, not a memory-mapping mode.
3. The model always copies one page per syscall.

definition *ipc-precondition* :: *thread-id-t* \Rightarrow *ipc-direction-t* \Rightarrow *thread-id-t* \Rightarrow *page-t* \Rightarrow *state-t* \Rightarrow *bool* **where**

ipc-precondition *tid* *dir* *partner* *page* *s* \equiv
let sender = (*case dir of SEND* \Rightarrow *tid* \mid *RECV* \Rightarrow *partner*) *in*
let receiver = (*case dir of SEND* \Rightarrow *partner* \mid *RECV* \Rightarrow *tid*) *in*
let local-access-mode = (*case dir of SEND* \Rightarrow *READ* \mid *RECV* \Rightarrow *WRITE*) *in*
(*sp-impl-subj-subj* *s* (*partition sender*) (*partition receiver*)
 \wedge *sp-impl-subj-obj* *s* (*partition tid*) (*PAGE page*) *local-access-mode*)

definition *atomic-step-ipc* :: *thread-id-t* \Rightarrow *ipc-direction-t* \Rightarrow *ipc-stage-t* \Rightarrow *thread-id-t* \Rightarrow *page-t* \Rightarrow *state-t* \Rightarrow *state-t* **where**

atomic-step-ipc *tid* *dir* *stage* *partner* *page* *s* \equiv
case stage of
PREP \Rightarrow
 s
 \mid *WAIT* \Rightarrow
 s
 \mid *BUF* *page'* \Rightarrow
(*case dir of*
SEND \Rightarrow
(*set-object-value* (*PAGE page'*) (*obj s* (*PAGE page*))) *s*)
 \mid *RECV* \Rightarrow *s*)

Model of event syscalls **definition** $ev\text{-}signal\text{-}precondition :: thread\text{-}id\text{-}t \Rightarrow thread\text{-}id\text{-}t \Rightarrow state\text{-}t \Rightarrow bool$ **where**
 $ev\text{-}signal\text{-}precondition\ tid\ partner\ s \equiv$
 $(sp\text{-}impl\text{-}subj\text{-}subj\ s\ (partition\ tid)\ (partition\ partner))$

definition $atomic\text{-}step\text{-}ev\text{-}signal :: thread\text{-}id\text{-}t \Rightarrow thread\text{-}id\text{-}t \Rightarrow state\text{-}t \Rightarrow state\text{-}t$ **where**
 $atomic\text{-}step\text{-}ev\text{-}signal\ tid\ partner\ s =$
 $s\ (\lambda\ thread := fun\text{-}upd\ (thread\ s)\ partner\ (thread\ s\ partner\ (\lambda\ ev\text{-}counter := Suc\ (ev\text{-}counter\ (thread\ s\ partner))\)\)\)\)$

definition $atomic\text{-}step\text{-}ev\text{-}wait\text{-}one :: thread\text{-}id\text{-}t \Rightarrow state\text{-}t \Rightarrow state\text{-}t$ **where**
 $atomic\text{-}step\text{-}ev\text{-}wait\text{-}one\ tid\ s =$
 $s\ (\lambda\ thread := fun\text{-}upd\ (thread\ s)\ tid\ (thread\ s\ tid\ (\lambda\ ev\text{-}counter := (ev\text{-}counter\ (thread\ s\ tid) - 1)\)\)\)\)$

definition $atomic\text{-}step\text{-}ev\text{-}wait\text{-}all :: thread\text{-}id\text{-}t \Rightarrow state\text{-}t \Rightarrow state\text{-}t$ **where**
 $atomic\text{-}step\text{-}ev\text{-}wait\text{-}all\ tid\ s =$
 $s\ (\lambda\ thread := fun\text{-}upd\ (thread\ s)\ tid\ (thread\ s\ tid\ (\lambda\ ev\text{-}counter := 0\)\)\)\)$

Instantiation of CISK aborting and waiting In this instantiation of CISK, the *aborting* function is used to indicate security policy enforcement. An IPC call aborts in its *PREP* stage if the precondition for the calling thread does not hold. An event signal call aborts in its *EV-SIGNAL-PREP* stage if the precondition for the calling thread does not hold.

definition $aborting :: state\text{-}t \Rightarrow thread\text{-}id\text{-}t \Rightarrow int\text{-}point\text{-}t \Rightarrow bool$
where $aborting\ s\ tid\ a \equiv case\ a\ of\ SK\text{-}IPC\ dir\ PREP\ partner\ page \Rightarrow$
 $\quad -ipc\text{-}precondition\ tid\ dir\ partner\ page\ s$
 $\quad | SK\text{-}EV\text{-}SIGNAL\ EV\text{-}SIGNAL\text{-}PREP\ partner \Rightarrow$
 $\quad -ev\text{-}signal\text{-}precondition\ tid\ partner\ s$
 $\quad | - \Rightarrow False$

The *waiting* function is used to indicate synchronization. An IPC call waits in its *WAIT* stage while the precondition for the partner thread does not hold. An *EV_WAIT* call waits until the event counter is not zero.

definition $waiting :: state\text{-}t \Rightarrow thread\text{-}id\text{-}t \Rightarrow int\text{-}point\text{-}t \Rightarrow bool$
where $waiting\ s\ tid\ a \equiv$
 $case\ a\ of\ SK\text{-}IPC\ dir\ WAIT\ partner\ page \Rightarrow$
 $\quad -ipc\text{-}precondition\ partner\ (opposite\text{-}ipc\text{-}direction\ dir)\ tid\ (SOME\ page' . True)\ s$
 $\quad | SK\text{-}EV\text{-}WAIT\ EV\text{-}PREP - \Rightarrow False$
 $\quad | SK\text{-}EV\text{-}WAIT\ EV\text{-}WAIT - \Rightarrow ev\text{-}counter\ (thread\ s\ tid) = 0$
 $\quad | SK\text{-}EV\text{-}WAIT\ EV\text{-}FINISH - \Rightarrow False$
 $\quad | - \Rightarrow False$

The atomic step function. In the definition of *atomic-step* the arguments to an interrupt point are not taken from the thread state – the argument given to *atomic-step* could have an arbitrary value. So, seen in isolation, *atomic-step* allows more transitions than actually occur in the separation kernel. However, the CISK framework (1) restricts the atomic step function by the *waiting* and *aborting* functions as well (2) the set of realistic traces as attack sequences *rAS-set* (Section 3.8). An additional condition is that (3) the dynamic policy used in *aborting* is a subset of the static policy. This is ensured by the invariant *sp-subset*.

definition $atomic\text{-}step :: state\text{-}t \Rightarrow int\text{-}point\text{-}t \Rightarrow state\text{-}t$ **where**
 $atomic\text{-}step\ s\ ipt \equiv$
 $case\ ipt\ of$
 $\quad SK\text{-}IPC\ dir\ stage\ partner\ page \Rightarrow$
 $\quad atomic\text{-}step\text{-}ipc\ (current\ s)\ dir\ stage\ partner\ page\ s$

```

| SK-EV-WAIT EV-PREP consume  $\Rightarrow$   $s$ 
| SK-EV-WAIT EV-WAIT consume  $\Rightarrow$   $s$ 
| SK-EV-WAIT EV-FINISH consume  $\Rightarrow$ 
  case consume of
    EV-CONSUME-ONE  $\Rightarrow$  atomic-step-ev-wait-one (current  $s$ )  $s$ 
    | EV-CONSUME-ALL  $\Rightarrow$  atomic-step-ev-wait-all (current  $s$ )  $s$ 
| SK-EV-SIGNAL EV-SIGNAL-PREP partner  $\Rightarrow$   $s$ 
| SK-EV-SIGNAL EV-SIGNAL-FINISH partner  $\Rightarrow$ 
  atomic-step-ev-signal (current  $s$ ) partner  $s$ 
| NONE  $\Rightarrow$   $s$ 

```

end

3.4 Preconditions and invariants for the atomic step

theory *step-invariants*

imports *step*

begin

The dynamic/implementation policies have to be compatible with the static configuration.

definition *sp-subset* $s \equiv$

```

( $\forall$   $p1$   $p2$  . sp-impl-subj-subj  $s$   $p1$   $p2 \longrightarrow$  Policy.sp-spec-subj-subj  $p1$   $p2$ )
 $\wedge$  ( $\forall$   $p1$   $p2$   $m$  . sp-impl-subj-obj  $s$   $p1$   $p2$   $m \longrightarrow$  Policy.sp-spec-subj-obj  $p1$   $p2$   $m$ )

```

The following predicate expresses the precondition for the atomic step. The precondition depends on the type of the atomic action.

definition *atomic-step-precondition* :: *state-t* \Rightarrow *thread-id-t* \Rightarrow *int-point-t* \Rightarrow *bool* **where**

atomic-step-precondition s *tid* *ipt* \equiv

case *ipt* of

SK-IPC *dir* *WAIT* *partner* *page* \Rightarrow

(* the thread managed it past PREP stage *)

ipc-precondition *tid* *dir* *partner* *page* s

| *SK-IPC* *dir* (*BUF* *page'*) *partner* *page* \Rightarrow

(* both the calling thread and its communication partner
managed it past PREP and WAIT stages *)

ipc-precondition *tid* *dir* *partner* *page* s

\wedge *ipc-precondition* *partner* (*opposite-ipc-direction* *dir*) *tid* *page'* s

| *SK-EV-SIGNAL* *EV-SIGNAL-FINISH* *partner* \Rightarrow

ev-signal-precondition *tid* *partner* s

| - \Rightarrow

(* No precondition for other interrupt points. *)

True

The invariant to be preserved by the atomic step function. The invariant is independent from the type of the atomic action.

definition *atomic-step-invariant* :: *state-t* \Rightarrow *bool* **where**

atomic-step-invariant $s \equiv$

sp-subset s

3.4.1 Atomic steps of SK_IPC preserve invariants

lemma *set-object-value-invariant*:

shows *atomic-step-invariant* $s =$ *atomic-step-invariant* (*set-object-value* *ob* *va* s)

proof –

show ?*thesis* **using** *assms*

unfolding *atomic-step-invariant-def* *atomic-step-precondition-def* *ipc-precondition-def*

```

    sp-subset-def set-object-value-def Let-def
  by (simp split add: int-point-t.splits ipc-stage-t.splits ipc-direction-t.splits)
qed

```

lemma *set-thread-value-invariant*:

```

shows atomic-step-invariant s = atomic-step-invariant (s (| thread := thrst |))
proof –
  show ?thesis using assms
  unfolding atomic-step-invariant-def atomic-step-precondition-def ipc-precondition-def
    sp-subset-def set-object-value-def Let-def
  by (simp split add: int-point-t.splits ipc-stage-t.splits ipc-direction-t.splits)
qed

```

lemma *atomic-ipc-preserves-invariants*:

```

fixes s :: state-t
  and tid :: thread-id-t
assumes atomic-step-invariant s
shows atomic-step-invariant (atomic-step-ipc tid dir stage partner page s)
proof –
  show ?thesis
  proof (cases stage)
  case PREP
    from this assms show ?thesis
    unfolding atomic-step-ipc-def atomic-step-invariant-def by auto
  next
  case WAIT
    from this assms show ?thesis
    unfolding atomic-step-ipc-def atomic-step-invariant-def by auto
  next
  case BUF
    show ?thesis
    using assms BUF set-object-value-invariant
    unfolding atomic-step-ipc-def
    by (simp split add: ipc-direction-t.splits)
  qed
qed

```

lemma *atomic-ev-wait-one-preserves-invariants*:

```

fixes s :: state-t
  and tid :: thread-id-t
assumes atomic-step-invariant s
shows atomic-step-invariant (atomic-step-ev-wait-one tid s)
proof –
  from assms show ?thesis
  unfolding atomic-step-ev-wait-one-def atomic-step-invariant-def sp-subset-def
  by auto
qed

```

lemma *atomic-ev-wait-all-preserves-invariants*:

```

fixes s :: state-t
  and tid :: thread-id-t
assumes atomic-step-invariant s
shows atomic-step-invariant (atomic-step-ev-wait-all tid s)
proof –
  from assms show ?thesis
  unfolding atomic-step-ev-wait-all-def atomic-step-invariant-def sp-subset-def
  by auto

```

qed

lemma *atomic-ev-signal-preserves-invariants*:

fixes $s :: \text{state-}t$

and $tid :: \text{thread-id-}t$

assumes *atomic-step-invariant* s

shows *atomic-step-invariant* (*atomic-step-ev-signal* tid *partner* s)

proof –

from *assms* **show** *?thesis*

unfolding *atomic-step-ev-signal-def* *atomic-step-invariant-def* *sp-subset-def*

by *auto*

qed

3.4.2 Summary theorems on atomic step invariants

Now we are ready to show that an atomic step from the current interrupt point in any thread preserves invariants.

theorem *atomic-step-preserves-invariants*:

fixes $s :: \text{state-}t$

and $tid :: \text{thread-id-}t$

assumes *atomic-step-invariant* s

shows *atomic-step-invariant* (*atomic-step* s a)

proof (*cases* a)

case *SK-IPC*

then show *?thesis* **unfolding** *atomic-step-def*

using *assms* *atomic-ipc-preserves-invariants*

by *simp*

next case (*SK-EV-WAIT* *ev-wait-stage* *consume*)

then show *?thesis*

proof (*cases* *consume*)

case *EV-CONSUME-ALL*

then show *?thesis* **unfolding** *atomic-step-def*

using *SK-EV-WAIT* *assms* *atomic-ev-wait-all-preserves-invariants*

by (*simp* *split: ev-wait-stage-t.splits*)

next case *EV-CONSUME-ONE*

then show *?thesis* **unfolding** *atomic-step-def*

using *SK-EV-WAIT* *assms* *atomic-ev-wait-one-preserves-invariants*

by (*simp* *split: ev-wait-stage-t.splits*)

qed

next case *SK-EV-SIGNAL*

then show *?thesis* **unfolding** *atomic-step-def*

using *assms* *atomic-ev-signal-preserves-invariants*

by (*simp* *add: ev-signal-stage-t.splits*)

next case *NONE*

then show *?thesis* **unfolding** *atomic-step-def*

using *assms*

by *auto*

qed

Finally, the invariants do not depend on the current thread. That is, the context switch preserves the invariants, and an atomic step that is not a context switch does not change the current thread.

theorem *cswitch-preserves-invariants*:

fixes $s :: \text{state-}t$

and $\text{new-current} :: \text{thread-id-}t$

assumes *atomic-step-invariant* s

shows *atomic-step-invariant* (s (\mid *current* := *new-current* \mid))

proof –

```

let ?s1 = s (| current := new-current |)
have sp-subset s = sp-subset ?s1
  unfolding sp-subset-def by auto
from assms this show ?thesis
  unfolding atomic-step-invariant-def by metis
qed

```

theorem *atomic-step-does-not-change-current-thread*:

shows *current* (*atomic-step* s *ipt*) = *current* s

proof –

show ?*thesis*

unfolding *atomic-step-def*

and *atomic-step-ipc-def*

and *set-object-value-def* *Let-def*

and *atomic-step-ev-wait-one-def* *atomic-step-ev-wait-all-def*

and *atomic-step-ev-signal-def*

by (*simp* *split* *add*: *int-point-t.splits* *ipc-stage-t.splits* *ipc-direction-t.splits*
ev-consume-t.splits *ev-wait-stage-t.splits* *ev-signal-stage-t.splits*)

qed

end

3.5 The view-partitioning equivalence relation

theory *step-vpeq*

imports *step* *step-invariants*

begin

The view consists of

1. View of object values.
2. View of subject-subject dynamic policy. The threads can discover the policy at runtime, e.g. by calling `ipc()` and observing success or failure.
3. View of subject-object dynamic policy. The threads can discover the policy at runtime, e.g. by calling `open()` and observing success or failure.

definition *vpeq-obj* :: *partition-id-t* \Rightarrow *state-t* \Rightarrow *state-t* \Rightarrow *bool* **where**

vpeq-obj u s t \equiv \forall *obj-id* . *Policy.sp-spec-subj-obj* u *obj-id* *READ* \longrightarrow (*obj* s) *obj-id* = (*obj* t) *obj-id*

definition *vpeq-subj-subj* :: *partition-id-t* \Rightarrow *state-t* \Rightarrow *state-t* \Rightarrow *bool* **where**

vpeq-subj-subj u s t \equiv

\forall v . ((*Policy.sp-spec-subj-subj* u v \longrightarrow *sp-impl-subj-subj* s u v = *sp-impl-subj-subj* t u v)

\wedge (*Policy.sp-spec-subj-subj* v u \longrightarrow *sp-impl-subj-subj* s v u = *sp-impl-subj-subj* t v u))

definition *vpeq-subj-obj* :: *partition-id-t* \Rightarrow *state-t* \Rightarrow *state-t* \Rightarrow *bool* **where**

vpeq-subj-obj u s t \equiv

\forall *ob m p1* .

(*Policy.sp-spec-subj-obj* u *ob m* \longrightarrow *sp-impl-subj-obj* s u *ob m* = *sp-impl-subj-obj* t u *ob m*)

\wedge (*Policy.sp-spec-subj-obj* *p1* *ob* *PROVIDE* \wedge (*Policy.sp-spec-subj-obj* u *ob* *READ* \vee *Policy.sp-spec-subj-obj* u *ob* *WRITE*) \longrightarrow

sp-impl-subj-obj s *p1* *ob* *PROVIDE* = *sp-impl-subj-obj* t *p1* *ob* *PROVIDE*)

definition *vpeq-local* :: *partition-id-t* \Rightarrow *state-t* \Rightarrow *state-t* \Rightarrow *bool* **where**

$vpeq\text{-local } u s t \equiv$
 $\forall tid . (partition\ tid) = u \longrightarrow (thread\ s\ tid) = (thread\ t\ tid)$

definition $vpeq\ u s t \equiv$
 $vpeq\text{-obj } u s t \wedge vpeq\text{-subj-subj } u s t \wedge vpeq\text{-subj-obj } u s t \wedge vpeq\text{-local } u s t$

3.5.1 Elementary properties

lemma $vpeq\text{-rel}$:

shows $vpeq\text{-refl}$: $vpeq\ u s s$

and $vpeq\text{-sym}$ [sym]: $vpeq\ u s t \implies vpeq\ u t s$

and $vpeq\text{-trans}$ [$trans$]: $[[vpeq\ u s1 s2 ; vpeq\ u s2 s3]] \implies vpeq\ u s1 s3$

unfolding $vpeq\text{-def } vpeq\text{-obj-def } vpeq\text{-subj-subj-def } vpeq\text{-subj-obj-def } vpeq\text{-local-def}$
by *auto*

Auxiliary equivalence relation.

lemma $set\text{-object-value-ign}$:

assumes $eq\text{-obs}$: $\sim Policy.sp\text{-spec-subj-obj } u x READ$

shows $vpeq\ u s (set\text{-object-value } x y s)$

proof –

from *assms* **show** *?thesis*

unfolding $vpeq\text{-def } vpeq\text{-obj-def } vpeq\text{-subj-subj-def } vpeq\text{-subj-obj-def } set\text{-object-value-def}$
 $vpeq\text{-local-def}$

by *auto*

qed

Context-switch and fetch operations are also consistent with $vpeq$ and locally respect everything.

theorem $cswitch\text{-consistency-and-respect}$:

fixes $u :: partition\text{-id-t}$

and $s :: state\text{-t}$

and $new\text{-current} :: thread\text{-id-t}$

assumes $atomic\text{-step-invariant } s$

shows $vpeq\ u s (s (\downarrow current := new\text{-current} \downarrow))$

proof –

show *?thesis*

unfolding $vpeq\text{-def } vpeq\text{-obj-def } vpeq\text{-subj-subj-def } vpeq\text{-subj-obj-def } vpeq\text{-local-def}$

by *auto*

qed

end

3.6 Atomic step locally respects the information flow policy

theory $step\text{-vpeq-locally-respects}$

imports $step\text{-step-invariants } step\text{-vpeq}$

begin

The notion of locally respects is common usage. We augment it by assuming that the $atomic\text{-step-invariant}$ holds (see [3]).

3.6.1 Locally respects of atomic step functions

lemma $ipc\text{-respects-policy}$:

assumes $no: \neg Policy.ifp$ (partition tid) u
and $inv: atomic-step-invariant$ s
and $prec: atomic-step-precondition$ s tid (SK-IPC dir stage partner pag)
and $ipt-case: ipt = SK-IPC$ dir stage partner page
shows $vpeq$ u s (atomic-step-ipc tid dir stage partner page s)
proof(cases stage)
case PREP
thus ?thesis
unfolding atomic-step-ipc-def
using $vpeq-refl$ **by** simp
next
case WAIT
thus ?thesis
unfolding atomic-step-ipc-def
using $vpeq-refl$ **by** simp
next case (BUF mypage)
show ?thesis
proof(cases dir)
case RECV
thus ?thesis
unfolding atomic-step-ipc-def
using $vpeq-refl$ BUF **by** simp
next
case SEND
have $Policy.sp-spec-subj-subj$ (partition tid) (partition partner)
and $Policy.sp-spec-subj-obj$ (partition partner) (PAGE mypage) WRITE
using BUF SEND inv $prec$ $ipt-case$
unfolding atomic-step-invariant-def $sp-subset-def$
unfolding atomic-step-precondition-def $ipc-precondition-def$ $opposite-ipc-direction-def$
by auto
hence $\neg Policy.sp-spec-subj-obj$ u (PAGE mypage) READ
using no $Policy-properties.ifp-compatible-with-ipc$
by auto
thus ?thesis
using BUF SEND $assms$
unfolding atomic-step-ipc-def $set-object-value-def$
unfolding $vpeq-def$ $vpeq-obj-def$ $vpeq-subj-obj-def$ $vpeq-subj-subj-def$ $vpeq-local-def$
by auto
qed
qed

lemma $ev-signal-respects-policy$:

assumes $no: \neg Policy.ifp$ (partition tid) u
and $inv: atomic-step-invariant$ s
and $prec: atomic-step-precondition$ s tid (SK-EV-SIGNAL EV-SIGNAL-FINISH partner)
and $ipt-case: ipt = SK-EV-SIGNAL$ EV-SIGNAL-FINISH partner
shows $vpeq$ u s (atomic-step-ev-signal tid partner s)
proof –
from inv no **have** $\neg sp-impl-subj-subj$ s (partition tid) u
unfolding $Policy.ifp-def$ $atomic-step-invariant-def$ $sp-subset-def$
by auto
with $prec$ **have** $1:(partition$ partner) $\neq u$
unfolding $atomic-step-precondition-def$ $ev-signal-precondition-def$
by (auto simp add: $ev-signal-stage-t.splits$)
then **have** $2:vpeq-local$ u s (atomic-step-ev-signal tid partner s)
unfolding $vpeq-local-def$ $atomic-step-ev-signal-def$
by simp

have 3:*vpeq-obj* *u s* (*atomic-step-ev-signal tid partner s*)
unfolding *vpeq-obj-def atomic-step-ev-signal-def*
by *simp*
have 4:*vpeq-subj-subj* *u s* (*atomic-step-ev-signal tid partner s*)
unfolding *vpeq-subj-subj-def atomic-step-ev-signal-def*
by *simp*
have 5:*vpeq-subj-obj* *u s* (*atomic-step-ev-signal tid partner s*)
unfolding *vpeq-subj-obj-def atomic-step-ev-signal-def*
by *simp*
with 2 3 4 5 **show** ?thesis
unfolding *vpeq-def*
by *simp*
qed

lemma *ev-wait-all-respects-policy*:

assumes *no*: \neg *Policy.ifp* (*partition tid*) *u*
and *inv*: *atomic-step-invariant s*
and *prec*: *atomic-step-precondition s tid ipt*
and *ipt-case*: *ipt* = *SK-EV-WAIT ev-wait-stage EV-CONSUME-ALL*
shows *vpeq u s* (*atomic-step-ev-wait-all tid s*)
proof –
from *assms* **have** 1:(*partition tid*) \neq *u*
unfolding *Policy.ifp-def*
by *simp*
then **have** 2:*vpeq-local* *u s* (*atomic-step-ev-wait-all tid s*)
unfolding *vpeq-local-def atomic-step-ev-wait-all-def*
by *simp*
have 3:*vpeq-obj* *u s* (*atomic-step-ev-wait-all tid s*)
unfolding *vpeq-obj-def atomic-step-ev-wait-all-def*
by *simp*
have 4:*vpeq-subj-subj* *u s* (*atomic-step-ev-wait-all tid s*)
unfolding *vpeq-subj-subj-def atomic-step-ev-wait-all-def*
by *simp*
have 5:*vpeq-subj-obj* *u s* (*atomic-step-ev-wait-all tid s*)
unfolding *vpeq-subj-obj-def atomic-step-ev-wait-all-def*
by *simp*
with 2 3 4 5 **show** ?thesis
unfolding *vpeq-def*
by *simp*
qed

lemma *ev-wait-one-respects-policy*:

assumes *no*: \neg *Policy.ifp* (*partition tid*) *u*
and *inv*: *atomic-step-invariant s*
and *prec*: *atomic-step-precondition s tid ipt*
and *ipt-case*: *ipt* = *SK-EV-WAIT ev-wait-stage EV-CONSUME-ONE*
shows *vpeq u s* (*atomic-step-ev-wait-one tid s*)
proof –
from *assms* **have** 1:(*partition tid*) \neq *u*
unfolding *Policy.ifp-def*
by *simp*
then **have** 2:*vpeq-local* *u s* (*atomic-step-ev-wait-one tid s*)
unfolding *vpeq-local-def atomic-step-ev-wait-one-def*
by *simp*
have 3:*vpeq-obj* *u s* (*atomic-step-ev-wait-one tid s*)
unfolding *vpeq-obj-def atomic-step-ev-wait-one-def*
by *simp*

```

have 4:vpeq-subj-subj u s (atomic-step-ev-wait-one tid s)
unfolding vpeq-subj-subj-def atomic-step-ev-wait-one-def
by simp
have 5:vpeq-subj-obj u s (atomic-step-ev-wait-one tid s)
unfolding vpeq-subj-obj-def atomic-step-ev-wait-one-def
by simp
with 2 3 4 5 show ?thesis
unfolding vpeq-def
by simp
qed

```

3.6.2 Summary theorems on view-partitioning locally respects

Atomic step locally respects the information flow policy (ifp). The policy ifp is not necessarily the same as `sp_spec_subj_subj`.

```

theorem atomic-step-respects-policy:
assumes no:  $\neg$  Policy.ifp (partition (current s)) u
and inv: atomic-step-invariant s
and prec: atomic-step-precondition s (current s) ipt
shows vpeq u s (atomic-step s ipt)
proof –
show ?thesis
using assms ipc-respects-policy vpeq-refl
      ev-signal-respects-policy ev-wait-one-respects-policy
      ev-wait-all-respects-policy
unfolding atomic-step-def
by (auto split add: int-point-t.splits ev-consume-t.splits ev-wait-stage-t.splits ev-signal-stage-t.splits)
qed

end

```

3.7 Weak step consistency

```

theory step-vpeq-weakly-step-consistent
imports step step-invariants step-vpeq
begin

```

The notion of weak step consistency is common usage. We augment it by assuming that the *atomic-step-invariant* holds (see [3]).

3.7.1 Weak step consistency of auxiliary functions

```

lemma ipc-precondition-weakly-step-consistent:
assumes eq-tid: vpeq (partition tid) s1 s2
and inv1: atomic-step-invariant s1
and inv2: atomic-step-invariant s2
shows ipc-precondition tid dir partner page s1 = ipc-precondition tid dir partner page s2
proof –
let ?sender = case dir of SEND  $\Rightarrow$  tid | RECV  $\Rightarrow$  partner
let ?receiver = case dir of SEND  $\Rightarrow$  partner | RECV  $\Rightarrow$  tid
let ?local-access-mode = case dir of SEND  $\Rightarrow$  READ | RECV  $\Rightarrow$  WRITE
let ?A = sp-impl-subj-subj s1 (partition ?sender) (partition ?receiver)
      = sp-impl-subj-subj s2 (partition ?sender) (partition ?receiver)
let ?B = sp-impl-subj-obj s1 (partition tid) (PAGE page) ?local-access-mode
      = sp-impl-subj-obj s2 (partition tid) (PAGE page) ?local-access-mode

```

```

have A: ?A
proof (cases Policy.sp-spec-subj-subj (partition ?sender) (partition ?receiver))
  case True
    thus ?A
    using eq-tid unfolding vpeq-def vpeq-subj-subj-def
    by (simp split add: ipc-direction-t.splits)
  next case False
    have sp-subset s1 and sp-subset s2
    using inv1 inv2 unfolding atomic-step-invariant-def sp-subset-def by auto
    hence  $\neg$  sp-impl-subj-subj s1 (partition ?sender) (partition ?receiver)
    and  $\neg$  sp-impl-subj-subj s2 (partition ?sender) (partition ?receiver)
    using False unfolding sp-subset-def by auto
    thus ?A by auto
  qed
have B: ?B
proof (cases Policy.sp-spec-subj-obj (partition tid) (PAGE page) ?local-access-mode)
  case True
    thus ?B
    using eq-tid unfolding vpeq-def vpeq-subj-obj-def
    by (simp split add: ipc-direction-t.splits)
  next case False
    have sp-subset s1 and sp-subset s2
    using inv1 inv2 unfolding atomic-step-invariant-def sp-subset-def by auto
    hence  $\neg$  sp-impl-subj-obj s1 (partition tid) (PAGE page) ?local-access-mode
    and  $\neg$  sp-impl-subj-obj s2 (partition tid) (PAGE page) ?local-access-mode
    using False unfolding sp-subset-def by auto
    thus ?B by auto
  qed
show ?thesis using A B unfolding ipc-precondition-def by auto
qed

lemma ev-signal-precondition-weakly-step-consistent:
assumes eq-tid: vpeq (partition tid) s1 s2
  and inv1: atomic-step-invariant s1
  and inv2: atomic-step-invariant s2
shows ev-signal-precondition tid partner s1 = ev-signal-precondition tid partner s2
proof –
let ?A = sp-impl-subj-subj s1 (partition tid) (partition partner)
  = sp-impl-subj-subj s2 (partition tid) (partition partner)
have A: ?A
proof (cases Policy.sp-spec-subj-subj (partition tid) (partition partner))
  case True
    thus ?A
    using eq-tid unfolding vpeq-def vpeq-subj-subj-def
    by (simp split add: ipc-direction-t.splits)
  next case False
    have sp-subset s1 and sp-subset s2
    using inv1 inv2 unfolding atomic-step-invariant-def sp-subset-def by auto
    hence  $\neg$  sp-impl-subj-subj s1 (partition tid) (partition partner)
    and  $\neg$  sp-impl-subj-subj s2 (partition tid) (partition partner)
    using False unfolding sp-subset-def by auto
    thus ?A by auto
  qed
show ?thesis using A unfolding ev-signal-precondition-def by auto
qed

```

lemma *set-object-value-consistent*:

assumes *eq-obs*: $vpeq\ u\ s1\ s2$

shows $vpeq\ u\ (set-object-value\ x\ y\ s1)\ (set-object-value\ x\ y\ s2)$

proof –

let $?s1' = set-object-value\ x\ y\ s1$ **and** $?s2' = set-object-value\ x\ y\ s2$

have *E1*: $vpeq-obj\ u\ ?s1'\ ?s2'$

proof –

{ **fix** x'

assume *I*: *Policy.sp-spec-subj-obj* $u\ x'\ READ$

have $obj\ ?s1'\ x' = obj\ ?s2'\ x'$ **proof** (*cases* $x = x'$)

case *True*

thus $obj\ ?s1'\ x' = obj\ ?s2'\ x'$ **unfolding** *set-object-value-def* **by** *auto*

next case *False*

hence *2*: $obj\ ?s1'\ x' = obj\ s1\ x'$

and *3*: $obj\ ?s2'\ x' = obj\ s2\ x'$

unfolding *set-object-value-def* **by** *auto*

have *4*: $obj\ s1\ x' = obj\ s2\ x'$

using *I eq-obs* **unfolding** *vpeq-def vpeq-obj-def* **by** *auto*

from *2 3 4* **show** $obj\ ?s1'\ x' = obj\ ?s2'\ x'$

by *simp*

qed }

thus $vpeq-obj\ u\ ?s1'\ ?s2'$ **unfolding** *vpeq-obj-def* **by** *auto*

qed

have *E4*: $vpeq-subj-subj\ u\ ?s1'\ ?s2'$

proof –

have *sp-impl-subj-subj* $?s1' = sp-impl-subj-subj\ s1$

and *sp-impl-subj-subj* $?s2' = sp-impl-subj-subj\ s2$

unfolding *set-object-value-def* **by** *auto*

thus $vpeq-subj-subj\ u\ ?s1'\ ?s2'$

using *eq-obs* **unfolding** *vpeq-def vpeq-subj-subj-def* **by** *auto*

qed

have *E5*: $vpeq-subj-obj\ u\ ?s1'\ ?s2'$

proof –

have *sp-impl-subj-obj* $?s1' = sp-impl-subj-obj\ s1$

and *sp-impl-subj-obj* $?s2' = sp-impl-subj-obj\ s2$

unfolding *set-object-value-def* **by** *auto*

thus $vpeq-subj-obj\ u\ ?s1'\ ?s2'$

using *eq-obs* **unfolding** *vpeq-def vpeq-subj-obj-def* **by** *auto*

qed

from *eq-obs* **have** *E6*: $vpeq-local\ u\ ?s1'\ ?s2'$

unfolding *vpeq-def vpeq-local-def set-object-value-def*

by *simp*

from *E1 E4 E5 E6*

show *?thesis* **unfolding** *vpeq-def*

by *auto*

qed

3.7.2 Weak step consistency of atomic step functions

lemma *ipc-weakly-step-consistent*:

assumes *eq-obs*: $vpeq\ u\ s1\ s2$

and *eq-act*: $vpeq\ (partition\ tid)\ s1\ s2$

and *inv1*: *atomic-step-invariant* $s1$

and *inv2*: *atomic-step-invariant* $s2$

and *prec1*: *atomic-step-precondition* $s1\ tid\ ipt$

and *prec2*: *atomic-step-precondition* $s1\ tid\ ipt$

and *ipt-case*: $ipt = SK-IPC\ dir\ stage\ partner\ page$

shows $vpeq\ u$
 (atomic-step-ipc tid dir stage partner page s1)
 (atomic-step-ipc tid dir stage partner page s2)

proof –
have $\wedge\ mypage . \llbracket\ dir = SEND; stage = BUF\ mypage\ \rrbracket \implies\ ?thesis$
proof –
fix $mypage$
assume $dir\text{-}send: dir = SEND$
assume $stage\text{-}buf: stage = BUF\ mypage$
have $Policy.sp\text{-}spec\text{-}subj\text{-}obj\ (partition\ tid)\ (PAGE\ page)\ READ$
using $inv1\ prec1\ dir\text{-}send\ stage\text{-}buf\ ipt\text{-}case$
unfolding $atomic\text{-}step\text{-}invariant\text{-}def\ sp\text{-}subset\text{-}def$
unfolding $atomic\text{-}step\text{-}precondition\text{-}def\ ipc\text{-}precondition\text{-}def\ opposite\text{-}ipc\text{-}direction\text{-}def$
by $auto$
hence $obj\ s1\ (PAGE\ page) = obj\ s2\ (PAGE\ page)$
using $eq\text{-}act$ **unfolding** $vpeq\text{-}def\ vpeq\text{-}obj\text{-}def\ vpeq\text{-}local\text{-}def$
by $auto$
thus $vpeq\ u$
 (atomic-step-ipc tid dir stage partner page s1)
 (atomic-step-ipc tid dir stage partner page s2)
using $dir\text{-}send\ stage\text{-}buf\ eq\text{-}obs\ set\text{-}object\text{-}value\text{-}consistent$
unfolding $atomic\text{-}step\text{-}ipc\text{-}def$
by $auto$
qed
thus $?thesis$
using $eq\text{-}obs$ **unfolding** $atomic\text{-}step\text{-}ipc\text{-}def$
by ($cases\ stage, auto, cases\ dir, auto$)
qed

lemma $ev\text{-}wait\text{-}one\text{-}weakly\text{-}step\text{-}consistent$:
assumes $eq\text{-}obs: vpeq\ u\ s1\ s2$
and $eq\text{-}act: vpeq\ (partition\ tid)\ s1\ s2$
and $inv1: atomic\text{-}step\text{-}invariant\ s1$
and $inv2: atomic\text{-}step\text{-}invariant\ s2$
and $prec1: atomic\text{-}step\text{-}precondition\ s1\ (current\ s1)\ ipt$
and $prec2: atomic\text{-}step\text{-}precondition\ s1\ (current\ s1)\ ipt$
shows $vpeq\ u$
 (atomic-step-ev-wait-one tid s1)
 (atomic-step-ev-wait-one tid s2)

using $assms$
unfolding $vpeq\text{-}def\ vpeq\text{-}subj\text{-}subj\text{-}def\ vpeq\text{-}obj\text{-}def\ vpeq\text{-}subj\text{-}obj\text{-}def\ vpeq\text{-}local\text{-}def$
 $atomic\text{-}step\text{-}ev\text{-}wait\text{-}one\text{-}def$
by $simp$

lemma $ev\text{-}wait\text{-}all\text{-}weakly\text{-}step\text{-}consistent$:
assumes $eq\text{-}obs: vpeq\ u\ s1\ s2$
and $eq\text{-}act: vpeq\ (partition\ tid)\ s1\ s2$
and $inv1: atomic\text{-}step\text{-}invariant\ s1$
and $inv2: atomic\text{-}step\text{-}invariant\ s2$
and $prec1: atomic\text{-}step\text{-}precondition\ s1\ (current\ s1)\ ipt$
and $prec2: atomic\text{-}step\text{-}precondition\ s1\ (current\ s1)\ ipt$
shows $vpeq\ u$
 (atomic-step-ev-wait-all tid s1)
 (atomic-step-ev-wait-all tid s2)

using $assms$
unfolding $vpeq\text{-}def\ vpeq\text{-}subj\text{-}subj\text{-}def\ vpeq\text{-}obj\text{-}def\ vpeq\text{-}subj\text{-}obj\text{-}def\ vpeq\text{-}local\text{-}def$
 $atomic\text{-}step\text{-}ev\text{-}wait\text{-}all\text{-}def$

by *simp*

lemma *ev-signal-weakly-step-consistent*:

assumes *eq-obs*: $vpeq\ u\ s1\ s2$

and *eq-act*: $vpeq\ (partition\ tid)\ s1\ s2$

and *inv1*: *atomic-step-invariant* $s1$

and *inv2*: *atomic-step-invariant* $s2$

and *prec1*: *atomic-step-precondition* $s1\ (current\ s1)\ ipt$

and *prec2*: *atomic-step-precondition* $s1\ (current\ s1)\ ipt$

shows $vpeq\ u$

(*atomic-step-ev-signal* $tid\ partner\ s1$)

(*atomic-step-ev-signal* $tid\ partner\ s2$)

using *assms*

unfolding *vpeq-def* *vpeq-subj-subj-def* *vpeq-obj-def* *vpeq-subj-obj-def* *vpeq-local-def*

atomic-step-ev-signal-def

by *simp*

The use of *extend-f* is to provide infrastructure to support use in dynamic policies, currently not used.

definition *extend-f* :: $(partition-id-t \Rightarrow partition-id-t \Rightarrow bool) \Rightarrow (partition-id-t \Rightarrow partition-id-t \Rightarrow bool) \Rightarrow (partition-id-t \Rightarrow partition-id-t \Rightarrow bool)$ **where**

$extend-ff\ g \equiv \lambda\ p1\ p2 . f\ p1\ p2 \vee g\ p1\ p2$

definition *extend-subj-subj* :: $(partition-id-t \Rightarrow partition-id-t \Rightarrow bool) \Rightarrow state-t \Rightarrow state-t$ **where**

$extend-subj-subj\ f\ s \equiv s\ (\lambda\ sp-impl-subj-subj := extend-ff\ (sp-impl-subj-subj\ s))$

lemma *extend-subj-subj-consistent*:

fixes $f :: partition-id-t \Rightarrow partition-id-t \Rightarrow bool$

assumes $vpeq\ u\ s1\ s2$

shows $vpeq\ u\ (extend-subj-subj\ f\ s1)\ (extend-subj-subj\ f\ s2)$

proof –

let $?g1 = sp-impl-subj-subj\ s1$ **and** $?g2 = sp-impl-subj-subj\ s2$

have $\forall v . Policy.sp-spec-subj-subj\ u\ v \longrightarrow ?g1\ u\ v = ?g2\ u\ v$

and $\forall v . Policy.sp-spec-subj-subj\ v\ u \longrightarrow ?g1\ v\ u = ?g2\ v\ u$

using *assms* **unfolding** *vpeq-def* *vpeq-subj-subj-def* **by** *auto*

hence $\forall v . Policy.sp-spec-subj-subj\ u\ v \longrightarrow extend-ff\ ?g1\ u\ v = extend-ff\ ?g2\ u\ v$

and $\forall v . Policy.sp-spec-subj-subj\ v\ u \longrightarrow extend-ff\ ?g1\ v\ u = extend-ff\ ?g2\ v\ u$

unfolding *extend-f-def* **by** *auto*

hence 1: $vpeq-subj-subj\ u\ (extend-subj-subj\ f\ s1)\ (extend-subj-subj\ f\ s2)$

unfolding *vpeq-subj-subj-def* *extend-subj-subj-def*

by *auto*

have 2: $vpeq-obj\ u\ (extend-subj-subj\ f\ s1)\ (extend-subj-subj\ f\ s2)$

using *assms* **unfolding** *vpeq-def* *vpeq-obj-def* *extend-subj-subj-def* **by** *fastforce*

have 3: $vpeq-subj-obj\ u\ (extend-subj-subj\ f\ s1)\ (extend-subj-subj\ f\ s2)$

using *assms* **unfolding** *vpeq-def* *vpeq-subj-obj-def* *extend-subj-subj-def* **by** *fastforce*

have 4: $vpeq-local\ u\ (extend-subj-subj\ f\ s1)\ (extend-subj-subj\ f\ s2)$

using *assms* **unfolding** *vpeq-def* *vpeq-local-def* *extend-subj-subj-def* **by** *fastforce*

from 1 2 3 4 **show** *thesis*

using *assms* **unfolding** *vpeq-def* **by** *fast*

qed

3.7.3 Summary theorems on view-partitioning weak step consistency

The atomic step is weakly step consistent with view partitioning. Here, the “weakness” is that we assume that the two states are vp-equivalent not only w.r.t. the observer domain u , but also w.r.t. the caller domain $step.partition\ tid$).

theorem *atomic-step-weakly-step-consistent*:

```

assumes eq-obs: vpeq u s1 s2
  and eq-act: vpeq (partition (current s1)) s1 s2
  and inv1: atomic-step-invariant s1
  and inv2: atomic-step-invariant s2
  and prec1: atomic-step-precondition s1 (current s1) ipt
  and prec2: atomic-step-precondition s2 (current s2) ipt
  and eq-curr: current s1 = current s2
shows vpeq u (atomic-step s1 ipt) (atomic-step s2 ipt)
proof –
show ?thesis
using assms
  ipc-weakly-step-consistent
  ev-wait-all-weakly-step-consistent
  ev-wait-one-weakly-step-consistent
  ev-signal-weakly-step-consistent
  vpeq-refl ev-signal-stage-t.exhaust
unfolding atomic-step-def
apply (cases ipt, auto)
apply (simp split add: ev-consume-t.splits ev-wait-stage-t.splits)
by (simp split add: ev-signal-stage-t.splits)
qed
end

```

3.8 Separation kernel model

```

theory separation-kernel-model
imports ../Theories-step/step
  ../Theories-step/step-invariants
  ../Theories-step/step-vpeq
  ../Theories-step/step-vpeq-locally-respects
  ../Theories-step/step-vpeq-weakly-step-consistent
  CISK
begin

```

First (Section 3.8.1) we instantiate the CISK generic model. Functions that instantiate a generic function of the CISK model are prefixed with an ‘r’, ‘r’ standing for “Rushby”; as CISK is derived originally from a model by Rushby [3]. For example, ‘rifp’ is the instantiation of the generic ‘ifp’.

Later (Section 3.8.5) all CISK proof obligations are discharged, e.g., weak step consistency, output consistency, etc. These will be used in Section 3.9.

3.8.1 Initial state of separation kernel model

We assume that the initial state of threads and memory is given. The initial state of threads is arbitrary, but the threads are not executing the system call. The purpose of the following definitions is to obtain the initial state without potentially dangerous axioms. The only axioms we admit without proof are formulated using the “consts” syntax and thus safe.

consts

```

initial-current :: thread-id-t
initial-obj :: obj-id-t ⇒ obj-t

```

definition *s0* :: *state-t* where

```

s0 ≡ (| sp-impl-subj-subj = Policy.sp-spec-subj-subj,
  sp-impl-subj-obj = Policy.sp-spec-subj-obj,
  current = initial-current,
  obj = initial-obj,

```

$$\text{thread} = \lambda s. (| \text{ev-counter} = 0 |)$$

lemma *initial-invariant*:

shows *atomic-step-invariant* *s0*

proof –

have *sp-subset* *s0*

unfolding *sp-subset-def* *s0-def* **by** *auto*

thus *?thesis*

unfolding *atomic-step-invariant-def* **by** *auto*

qed

3.8.2 Types for instantiation of the generic model

To simplify formulations, we include the state invariant *atomic-step-invariant* in the state data type. The initial state *s0* serves as witness that *rstate-t* is non-empty.

typedef *rstate-t* = { *s* . *atomic-step-invariant* *s* }

using *initial-invariant* **by** *auto*

definition *abs* :: *state-t* \Rightarrow *rstate-t* (\uparrow -) **where** *abs* = *Abs-rstate-t*

definition *rep* :: *rstate-t* \Rightarrow *state-t* (\downarrow -) **where** *rep* = *Rep-rstate-t*

lemma *rstate-invariant*:

shows *atomic-step-invariant* ($\downarrow s$)

unfolding *rep-def* **by** (*metis* *Rep-rstate-t* *mem-Collect-eq*)

lemma *rstate-down-up*[*simp*]:

shows ($\uparrow \downarrow s$) = *s*

unfolding *rep-def* *abs-def* **using** *Rep-rstate-t-inverse* **by** *auto*

lemma *rstate-up-down*[*simp*]:

assumes *atomic-step-invariant* *s*

shows ($\downarrow \uparrow s$) = *s*

using *assms* *Abs-rstate-t-inverse* **unfolding** *rep-def* *abs-def* **by** *auto*

A CISK action is identified with an interrupt point.

type-synonym *raction-t* = *int-point-t*

definition *rcurrent* :: *rstate-t* \Rightarrow *thread-id-t* **where**

rcurrent *s* = *current* $\downarrow s$

definition *rstep* :: *rstate-t* \Rightarrow *raction-t* \Rightarrow *rstate-t* **where**

rstep *s* *a* \equiv \uparrow (*atomic-step* ($\downarrow s$) *a*)

Each CISK domain is identified with a thread id.

type-synonym *rdom-t* = *thread-id-t*

The output function returns the contents of all memory accessible to the subject. The action argument of the output function is ignored.

datatype *visible-obj-t* = *VALUE* *obj-t* | *EXCEPTION*

type-synonym *routput-t* = *page-t* \Rightarrow *visible-obj-t*

definition *routput-f* :: *rstate-t* \Rightarrow *raction-t* \Rightarrow *routput-t* **where**

routput-f *s* *a* *p* \equiv

if *sp-impl-subj-obj* ($\downarrow s$) (*partition* (*rcurrent* *s*)) (*PAGE* *p*) *READ* then

VALUE (*obj* ($\downarrow s$) (*PAGE* *p*))

else

EXCEPTION

The precondition for the generic model. Note that *atomic-step-invariant* is already part of the state.

definition $rprecondition :: rstate-t \Rightarrow rdom-t \Rightarrow raction-t \Rightarrow bool$ **where**
 $rprecondition\ s\ d\ a \equiv atomic\text{-}step\text{-}precondition\ (\downarrow s)\ d\ a$

abbreviation $rinvariant$

where $rinvariant\ s \equiv True$ — The invariant is already in the state type.

Translate view-partitioning and interaction-allowed relations.

definition $rvpeq :: rdom-t \Rightarrow rstate-t \Rightarrow rstate-t \Rightarrow bool$ **where**
 $rvpeq\ u\ s1\ s2 \equiv vpeq\ (partition\ u)\ (\downarrow s1)\ (\downarrow s2)$

definition $rifp :: rdom-t \Rightarrow rdom-t \Rightarrow bool$ **where**
 $rifp\ u\ v = Policy.ifp\ (partition\ u)\ (partition\ v)$

Context Switches

definition $rcswitch :: nat \Rightarrow rstate-t \Rightarrow rstate-t$ **where**
 $rcswitch\ n\ s \equiv \uparrow((\downarrow s)\ (\downarrow current := (SOME\ t.\ True)))$

3.8.3 Possible action sequences

An *SK-IPC* consists of three atomic actions *PREP*, *WAIT* and *BUF* with the same parameters.

definition $is\text{-}SK\text{-}IPC :: raction\text{-}t\ list \Rightarrow bool$

where $is\text{-}SK\text{-}IPC\ aseq \equiv \exists\ dir\ partner\ page.$

$aseq = [SK\text{-}IPC\ dir\ PREP\ partner\ page, SK\text{-}IPC\ dir\ WAIT\ partner\ page, SK\text{-}IPC\ dir\ (BUF\ (SOME\ page' . True))\ partner\ page]$

An *SK-EV-WAIT* consists of three atomic actions, one for each of the stages *EV-PREP*, *EV-WAIT* and *EV-FINISH* with the same parameters.

definition $is\text{-}SK\text{-}EV\text{-}WAIT :: raction\text{-}t\ list \Rightarrow bool$

where $is\text{-}SK\text{-}EV\text{-}WAIT\ aseq \equiv \exists\ consume.$

$aseq = [SK\text{-}EV\text{-}WAIT\ EV\text{-}PREP\ consume,\ SK\text{-}EV\text{-}WAIT\ EV\text{-}WAIT\ consume,\ SK\text{-}EV\text{-}WAIT\ EV\text{-}FINISH\ consume]$

An *SK-EV-SIGNAL* consists of two atomic actions, one for each of the stages *EV-SIGNAL-PREP* and *EV-SIGNAL-FINISH* with the same parameters.

definition $is\text{-}SK\text{-}EV\text{-}SIGNAL :: raction\text{-}t\ list \Rightarrow bool$

where $is\text{-}SK\text{-}EV\text{-}SIGNAL\ aseq \equiv \exists\ partner.$

$aseq = [SK\text{-}EV\text{-}SIGNAL\ EV\text{-}SIGNAL\text{-}PREP\ partner,\ SK\text{-}EV\text{-}SIGNAL\ EV\text{-}SIGNAL\text{-}FINISH\ partner]$

The complete attack surface consists of IPC calls, events, and noops.

definition $rAS\text{-}set :: raction\text{-}t\ list\ set$

where $rAS\text{-}set \equiv \{ aseq . is\text{-}SK\text{-}IPC\ aseq \vee is\text{-}SK\text{-}EV\text{-}WAIT\ aseq \vee is\text{-}SK\text{-}EV\text{-}SIGNAL\ aseq \} \cup \{ [] \}$

3.8.4 Control

When are actions aborting, and when are actions waiting. We do not currently use the *set-error-code* function yet.

abbreviation $raborting$

where $raborting\ s \equiv aborting\ (\downarrow s)$

abbreviation $rwaiting$

where $rwaiting\ s \equiv waiting\ (\downarrow s)$

definition *rset-error-code* :: *rstate-t* \Rightarrow *raction-t* \Rightarrow *rstate-t*
where *rset-error-code* *s a* \equiv *s*

Returns the set of threads that are involved in a certain action. For example, for an IPC call, the *WAIT* stage synchronizes with the partner. This partner is involved in that action.

definition *rkinvolved* :: *int-point-t* \Rightarrow *rdom-t* *set*
where *rkinvolved* *a* \equiv
case a of SK-IPC dir WAIT partner page \Rightarrow {*partner*}
| *SK-EV-SIGNAL EV-SIGNAL-FINISH partner* \Rightarrow {*partner*}
| - \Rightarrow {}

abbreviation *rinvolved* :: *int-point-t option* \Rightarrow *rdom-t* *set*
where *rinvolved* \equiv *Kernel.involved rkinvolved*

3.8.5 Discharging the proof obligations

lemma *inst-vpeq-rel*:
shows *rvpeq-refl*: *rvpeq u s s*
and *rvpeq-sym*: *rvpeq u s1 s2* \implies *rvpeq u s2 s1*
and *rvpeq-trans*: \llbracket *rvpeq u s1 s2*; *rvpeq u s2 s3* $\rrbracket \implies$ *rvpeq u s1 s3*
unfolding *rvpeq-def* **using** *vpeq-rel* **by** *metis+*

lemma *inst-ifp-refl*:
shows $\forall u .$ *rifp u u*
unfolding *rifp-def* **using** *Policy-properties.ifp-reflexive* **by** *fast*

lemma *inst-step-atomicity* [*simp*]:
shows $\forall s a .$ *rcurrent (rstep s a)* = *rcurrent s*
unfolding *rstep-def* *rcurrent-def*
using *atomic-step-does-not-change-current-thread* *rstate-up-down* *rstate-invariant* *atomic-step-preserves-invariants*
by *auto*

lemma *inst-weakly-step-consistent*:
assumes *rvpeq u s t*
and *rvpeq (rcurrent s) s t*
and *rcurrent s = rcurrent t*
and *rprecondition s (rcurrent s) a*
and *rprecondition t (rcurrent t) a*
shows *rvpeq u (rstep s a) (rstep t a)*
using *assms* *atomic-step-weakly-step-consistent* *rstate-invariant* *atomic-step-preserves-invariants*
unfolding *rcurrent-def* *rstep-def* *rvpeq-def* *rprecondition-def*
by *auto*

lemma *inst-local-respect*:
assumes *not-ifp*: \neg *rifp (rcurrent s) u*
and *prec*: *rprecondition s (rcurrent s) a*
shows *rvpeq u s (rstep s a)*
using *assms* *atomic-step-respects-policy* *rstate-invariant* *atomic-step-preserves-invariants*
unfolding *rifp-def* *rprecondition-def* *rvpeq-def* *rstep-def* *rcurrent-def*
by *auto*

lemma *inst-output-consistency*:

assumes *rvpeq*: *rvpeq* (*rcurrent* *s*) *s* *t*

and *current-eq*: *rcurrent* *s* = *rcurrent* *t*

shows *routput-f* *s* *a* = *routput-f* *t* *a*

proof–

have $\forall a s t. \text{rvpeq } (rcurrent\ s)\ s\ t \wedge rcurrent\ s = rcurrent\ t \longrightarrow \text{routput-f } s\ a = \text{routput-f } t\ a$

proof–

{ **fix** *a* :: *raction-t*

fix *s* *t* :: *rstate-t*

fix *p* :: *page-t*

assume *1*: *rvpeq* (*rcurrent* *s*) *s* *t*

and *2*: *rcurrent* *s* = *rcurrent* *t*

let *?part* = *partition* (*rcurrent* *s*)

have *routput-f* *s* *a* *p* = *routput-f* *t* *a* *p*

proof (*cases* *Policy.sp-spec-subj-obj* *?part* (*PAGE* *p*) *READ*

rule: *case-split* [*case-names* *Allowed Denied*])

case *Allowed*

have *5*: *obj* ($\downarrow s$) (*PAGE* *p*) = *obj* ($\downarrow t$) (*PAGE* *p*)

using *1 Allowed* **unfolding** *rvpeq-def* *vpeq-def* *vpeq-obj-def* **by** *auto*

have *6*: *sp-impl-subj-obj* ($\downarrow s$) *?part* (*PAGE* *p*) *READ* = *sp-impl-subj-obj* ($\downarrow t$) *?part* (*PAGE* *p*) *READ*

using *1 2 Allowed* **unfolding** *rvpeq-def* *vpeq-def* *vpeq-subj-obj-def* **by** *auto*

show *routput-f* *s* *a* *p* = *routput-f* *t* *a* *p*

unfolding *routput-f-def* **using** *2 5 6* **by** *auto*

next case *Denied*

hence *sp-impl-subj-obj* ($\downarrow s$) *?part* (*PAGE* *p*) *READ* = *False*

and *sp-impl-subj-obj* ($\downarrow t$) *?part* (*PAGE* *p*) *READ* = *False*

using *rstate-invariant* **unfolding** *atomic-step-invariant-def* *sp-subset-def*

by *auto*

thus *routput-f* *s* *a* *p* = *routput-f* *t* *a* *p*

using *2* **unfolding** *routput-f-def* **by** *simp*

qed }

thus $\forall a s t. \text{rvpeq } (rcurrent\ s)\ s\ t \wedge rcurrent\ s = rcurrent\ t \longrightarrow \text{routput-f } s\ a = \text{routput-f } t\ a$

by *auto*

qed

thus *?thesis* **using** *assms* **by** *auto*

qed

lemma *inst-cswitch-independent-of-state*:

assumes *rcurrent* *s* = *rcurrent* *t*

shows *rcurrent* (*rcswitch* *n* *s*) = *rcurrent* (*rcswitch* *n* *t*)

using *rstate-invariant* *cswitch-preserves-invariants* **unfolding** *rcurrent-def* *rcswitch-def* **by** *simp*

lemma *inst-cswitch-consistency*:

assumes *rvpeq* *u* *s* *t*

shows *rvpeq* *u* (*rcswitch* *n* *s*) (*rcswitch* *n* *t*)

proof–

have *1*: *vpeq* (*partition* *u*) ($\downarrow s$) \downarrow (*rcswitch* *n* *s*)

using *rstate-invariant* *cswitch-consistency-and-respect* *cswitch-preserves-invariants*

unfolding *rcswitch-def*

by *auto*

have *2*: *vpeq* (*partition* *u*) ($\downarrow t$) \downarrow (*rcswitch* *n* *t*)

using *rstate-invariant* *cswitch-consistency-and-respect* *cswitch-preserves-invariants*

unfolding *rcswitch-def*

by *auto*

from 1 2 *assms* **show** ?thesis **unfolding** *rvpeq-def* **using** *vpeq-rel* **by** *metis*
qed

For the *PREP* stage (the first stage of the IPC action sequence) the precondition is True.

lemma *prec-first-IPC-action*:
assumes *is-SK-IPC aseq*
shows *rprecondition s d (hd aseq)*
using *assms*
unfolding *is-SK-IPC-def rprecondition-def atomic-step-precondition-def*
by *auto*

For the the first stage of the *EV-WAIT* action sequence the precondition is True.

lemma *prec-first-EV-WAIT-action*:
assumes *is-SK-EV-WAIT aseq*
shows *rprecondition s d (hd aseq)*
using *assms*
unfolding *is-SK-EV-WAIT-def rprecondition-def atomic-step-precondition-def*
by *auto*

For the first stage of the *EV-SIGNAL* action sequence the precondition is True.

lemma *prec-first-EV-SIGNAL-action*:
assumes *is-SK-EV-SIGNAL aseq*
shows *rprecondition s d (hd aseq)*
using *assms*
unfolding *is-SK-EV-SIGNAL-def rprecondition-def atomic-step-precondition-def*
ev-signal-precondition-def
by *auto*

When not waiting or aborting, the precondition is “1-step inductive”, that is at all times the precondition holds initially (for the first step of an action sequence) and after doing one step.

lemma *prec-after-IPC-step*:
assumes *prec: rprecondition s (rcurrent s) (aseq ! n)*
and *n-bound: Suc n < length aseq*
and *IPC: is-SK-IPC aseq*
and *not-aborting: ¬raborting s (rcurrent s) (aseq ! n)*
and *not-waiting: ¬rwaiting s (rcurrent s) (aseq ! n)*
shows *rprecondition (rstep s (aseq ! n)) (rcurrent s) (aseq ! Suc n)*
proof–
{
fix *dir partner page*
let ?*page'* = (*SOME page' . True*)
assume *IPC: aseq = [SK-IPC dir PREP partner page,SK-IPC dir WAIT partner page,SK-IPC dir (BUF ?page')*
partner page]
{
assume 0: *n=0*
from 0 *IPC prec not-aborting*
have ?*thesis*
unfolding *rprecondition-def atomic-step-precondition-def rstep-def rcurrent-def atomic-step-def atomic-step-ipc-def*
aborting-def
by(*auto*)
}
}
moreover
{
assume 1: *n=1*
from 1 *IPC prec not-waiting*
have ?*thesis*
unfolding *rprecondition-def atomic-step-precondition-def rstep-def rcurrent-def atomic-step-def atomic-step-ipc-def*
waiting-def

```

    by(auto)
  }
  moreover
  from IPC
  have length aseq = 3
  by auto
  ultimately
  have ?thesis
  using n-bound
  by arith
}
thus ?thesis
using IPC
unfolding is-SK-IPC-def
by(auto)
qed

```

When not waiting or aborting, the precondition is 1-step inductive.

```

lemma prec-after-EV-WAIT-step:
assumes prec: rprecondition s (rcurrent s) (aseq ! n)
  and n-bound: Suc n < length aseq
  and IPC: is-SK-EV-WAIT aseq
  and not-aborting: ¬raborting s (rcurrent s) (aseq ! n)
  and not-waiting: ¬rwaiting s (rcurrent s) (aseq ! n)
shows rprecondition (rstep s (aseq ! n)) (rcurrent s) (aseq ! Suc n)
proof-
{
  fix consume

  assume WAIT: aseq = [SK-EV-WAIT EV-PREP consume,
    SK-EV-WAIT EV-WAIT consume,
    SK-EV-WAIT EV-FINISH consume]

  {
    assume 0: n=0
    from 0 WAIT prec not-aborting
    have ?thesis
    unfolding rprecondition-def atomic-step-precondition-def
    by(auto)
  }
  moreover
  {
    assume 1: n=1
    from 1 WAIT prec not-waiting
    have ?thesis
    unfolding rprecondition-def atomic-step-precondition-def
    by(auto)
  }
  moreover
  from WAIT
  have length aseq = 3
  by auto
  ultimately
  have ?thesis
  using n-bound
  by arith
}
thus ?thesis
using assms

```

unfolding *is-SK-EV-WAIT-def*
by *auto*
qed

When not waiting or aborting, the precondition is 1-step inductive.

lemma *prec-after-EV-SIGNAL-step*:
assumes *prec: rprecondition s (rcurrent s) (aseq ! n)*
and *n-bound: Suc n < length aseq*
and *SIGNAL: is-SK-EV-SIGNAL aseq*
and *not-aborting: ¬raborting s (rcurrent s) (aseq ! n)*
and *not-waiting: ¬rwaiting s (rcurrent s) (aseq ! n)*
shows *rprecondition (rstep s (aseq ! n)) (rcurrent s) (aseq ! Suc n)*
proof–
{ **fix** *partner*
assume *SIGNAL1: aseq = [SK-EV-SIGNAL EV-SIGNAL-PREP partner,*
SK-EV-SIGNAL EV-SIGNAL-FINISH partner]
{
assume *0: n=0*
from *0 SIGNAL1 prec not-aborting*
have *?thesis*
unfolding *rprecondition-def atomic-step-precondition-def ev-signal-precondition-def*
aborting-def rstep-def atomic-step-def
by *auto*
}
moreover
from *SIGNAL1*
have *length aseq = 2*
by *auto*
ultimately
have *?thesis*
using *n-bound*
by *arith*
}
thus *?thesis*
using *assms*
unfolding *is-SK-EV-SIGNAL-def*
by *auto*
qed

lemma *on-set-object-value*:
shows *sp-impl-subj-subj (set-object-value ob val s) = sp-impl-subj-subj s*
and *sp-impl-subj-obj (set-object-value ob val s) = sp-impl-subj-obj s*
unfolding *set-object-value-def* **apply** *simp+ done*

lemma *prec-IPC-dom-independent*:
assumes *current s ≠ d*
and *atomic-step-invariant s*
and *atomic-step-precondition s d a*
shows *atomic-step-precondition (atomic-step-ipc (current s) dir stage partner page s) d a*
using *assms on-set-object-value*
unfolding *atomic-step-precondition-def atomic-step-ipc-def ipc-precondition-def*
ev-signal-precondition-def set-object-value-def
by (*auto split add: int-point-t.splits ipc-stage-t.splits ipc-direction-t.splits*
ev-consume-t.splits ev-wait-stage-t.splits ev-signal-stage-t.splits)

lemma *prec-ev-signal-dom-independent*:
assumes *current s ≠ d*
and *atomic-step-invariant s*

and *atomic-step-precondition* $s \ d \ a$
shows *atomic-step-precondition* (*atomic-step-ev-signal* (*current* s) *partner* s) $d \ a$
using *assms on-set-object-value*
unfolding *atomic-step-precondition-def* *atomic-step-ev-signal-def* *ipc-precondition-def*
ev-signal-precondition-def *set-object-value-def*
by (*auto split add: int-point-t.splits ipc-stage-t.splits ipc-direction-t.splits*
ev-consume-t.splits ev-wait-stage-t.splits ev-signal-stage-t.splits)

lemma *prec-ev-wait-one-dom-independent*:

assumes *current* $s \neq d$
and *atomic-step-invariant* s
and *atomic-step-precondition* $s \ d \ a$
shows *atomic-step-precondition* (*atomic-step-ev-wait-one* (*current* s) s) $d \ a$
using *assms on-set-object-value*
unfolding *atomic-step-precondition-def* *atomic-step-ev-wait-one-def* *ipc-precondition-def*
ev-signal-precondition-def *set-object-value-def*
by (*auto split add: int-point-t.splits ipc-stage-t.splits ipc-direction-t.splits*
ev-consume-t.splits ev-wait-stage-t.splits ev-signal-stage-t.splits)

lemma *prec-ev-wait-all-dom-independent*:

assumes *current* $s \neq d$
and *atomic-step-invariant* s
and *atomic-step-precondition* $s \ d \ a$
shows *atomic-step-precondition* (*atomic-step-ev-wait-all* (*current* s) s) $d \ a$
using *assms on-set-object-value*
unfolding *atomic-step-precondition-def* *atomic-step-ev-wait-all-def* *ipc-precondition-def*
ev-signal-precondition-def *set-object-value-def*
by (*auto split add: int-point-t.splits ipc-stage-t.splits ipc-direction-t.splits*
ev-consume-t.splits ev-wait-stage-t.splits ev-signal-stage-t.splits)

lemma *prec-dom-independent*:

shows $\forall s \ d \ a \ a' . rcurrent \ s \neq d \wedge rprecondition \ s \ d \ a \longrightarrow rprecondition \ (rstep \ s \ a') \ d \ a$
using *atomic-step-preserves-invariants*
rstate-invariant *prec-IPC-dom-independent* *prec-ev-signal-dom-independent*
prec-ev-wait-all-dom-independent *prec-ev-wait-one-dom-independent*
unfolding *rcurrent-def* *rprecondition-def* *rstep-def* *atomic-step-def*
by (*auto split add: int-point-t.splits ev-consume-t.splits ev-wait-stage-t.splits ev-signal-stage-t.splits*)

lemma *ipc-precondition-after-cswitch*[*simp*]:

shows *ipc-precondition* $d \ dir \ partner \ page \ ((\downarrow s)(current := new-current))$
 $= \text{ipc-precondition } d \ dir \ partner \ page \ (\downarrow s)$
using *assms*
unfolding *ipc-precondition-def*
by (*auto split add: ipc-direction-t.splits*)

lemma *precondition-after-cswitch*:

shows $\forall s \ d \ n \ a . rprecondition \ s \ d \ a \longrightarrow rprecondition \ (rcswitch \ n \ s) \ d \ a$
using *cswitch-preserves-invariants* *rstate-invariant*
unfolding *rprecondition-def* *rcswitch-def* *atomic-step-precondition-def*
ev-signal-precondition-def
by (*auto split add: int-point-t.splits ipc-stage-t.splits ev-signal-stage-t.splits*)

lemma *aborting-switch-independent*:

shows $\forall n \ s . raborting \ (rcswitch \ n \ s) = raborting \ s$
proof–
 $\{$
fix $n \ s$

```

{
  fix tid a
  have raborting (rcswitch n s) tid a = raborting s tid a
  using rstate-invariant cswitch-preserves-invariants ev-signal-precondition-weakly-step-consistent
    cswitch-consistency-and-respect
  unfolding aborting-def rcswitch-def
  apply (auto split add: int-point-t.splits ipc-stage-t.splits
    ev-wait-stage-t.splits ev-signal-stage-t.splits)
  apply (metis (full-types))
  by blast
}
hence raborting (rcswitch n s) = raborting s by auto
}
thus ?thesis by auto
qed
lemma waiting-switch-independent:
shows  $\forall n s. rwaiting (rcswitch n s) = rwaiting s$ 
proof-
{
  fix n s
  {
    fix tid a
    have rwaiting (rcswitch n s) tid a = rwaiting s tid a
    using rstate-invariant cswitch-preserves-invariants
    unfolding waiting-def rcswitch-def
    by(auto split add: int-point-t.splits ipc-stage-t.splits ev-wait-stage-t.splits)
  }
  hence rwaiting (rcswitch n s) = rwaiting s by auto
}
thus ?thesis by auto
qed

lemma aborting-after-IPC-step:
assumes  $d1 \neq d2$ 
shows aborting (atomic-step-ipc d1 dir stage partner page s) d2 a = aborting s d2 a
unfolding atomic-step-ipc-def aborting-def set-object-value-def ipc-precondition-def
  ev-signal-precondition-def
by(auto split add: int-point-t.splits ipc-stage-t.splits ipc-direction-t.splits
  ev-signal-stage-t.splits)

lemma waiting-after-IPC-step:
assumes  $d1 \neq d2$ 
shows waiting (atomic-step-ipc d1 dir stage partner page s) d2 a = waiting s d2 a
unfolding atomic-step-ipc-def waiting-def set-object-value-def ipc-precondition-def
by(auto split add: int-point-t.splits ipc-stage-t.splits ipc-direction-t.splits
  ev-wait-stage-t.splits)

lemma raborting-consistent:
shows  $\forall s t u. rvpeq u s t \longrightarrow raborting s u = raborting t u$ 
proof-
{
  fix s t u
  assume vpeq: rvpeq u s t
  {
    fix a

```

```

from vpeq ipc-precondition-weakly-step-consistent rstate-invariant
  have  $\wedge$  tid dir partner page . ipc-precondition u dir partner page ( $\downarrow s$ )
      = ipc-precondition u dir partner page ( $\downarrow t$ )
  unfolding rvpeq-def
  by auto
with vpeq rstate-invariant have raborting s u a = raborting t u a
  unfolding aborting-def rvpeq-def vpeq-def vpeq-local-def ev-signal-precondition-def
      vpeq-subj-subj-def atomic-step-invariant-def sp-subset-def rep-def
  apply (auto split add: int-point-t.splits ipc-stage-t.splits ev-signal-stage-t.splits)
  by blast
}
hence raborting s u = raborting t u by auto
}
thus ?thesis by auto
qed

lemma aborting-dom-independent:
  assumes rcurrent s  $\neq$  d
  shows raborting (rstep s a) d a' = raborting s d a'
proof –
  have  $\wedge$  tid dir partner page s . ipc-precondition tid dir partner page s = ipc-precondition tid dir partner page
    (atomic-step s a)
       $\wedge$  ev-signal-precondition tid partner s = ev-signal-precondition tid partner (atomic-step s a)

  proof –
  fix tid dir partner page s
  let ?s = atomic-step s a
  have ( $\forall$  p q . sp-impl-subj-subj s p q = sp-impl-subj-subj ?s p q)
       $\wedge$  ( $\forall$  p x m . sp-impl-subj-obj s p x m = sp-impl-subj-obj ?s p x m)
  unfolding atomic-step-def atomic-step-ipc-def
      atomic-step-ev-wait-all-def atomic-step-ev-wait-one-def
      atomic-step-ev-signal-def set-object-value-def
  by (auto split add: int-point-t.splits ipc-stage-t.splits ipc-direction-t.splits
      ev-wait-stage-t.splits ev-consume-t.splits ev-signal-stage-t.splits)
  thus ipc-precondition tid dir partner page s = ipc-precondition tid dir partner page (atomic-step s a)
       $\wedge$  ev-signal-precondition tid partner s = ev-signal-precondition tid partner (atomic-step s a)
  unfolding ipc-precondition-def ev-signal-precondition-def by simp
  qed
moreover have  $\wedge$  b . ( $\downarrow$ ( $\uparrow$ (atomic-step ( $\downarrow s$ ) b))) = atomic-step ( $\downarrow s$ ) b
  using rstate-invariant atomic-step-preserves-invariants rstate-up-down by auto
ultimately show ?thesis
  unfolding aborting-def rstep-def ev-signal-precondition-def

  by (simp split add: int-point-t.splits ipc-stage-t.splits ev-wait-stage-t.splits
      ev-signal-stage-t.splits)
qed

lemma ipc-precondition-of-partner-consistent:
  assumes vpeq:  $\forall$  d  $\in$  rkinvolved (SK-IPC dir WAIT partner page) . rvpeq d s t
  shows ipc-precondition partner dir' u page' ( $\downarrow s$ ) = ipc-precondition partner dir' u page'  $\downarrow t$ 
proof–
  from assms ipc-precondition-weakly-step-consistent rstate-invariant
  show ?thesis
  unfolding rvpeq-def rkinvolved-def
  by auto
qed

```

lemma *ev-signal-precondition-of-partner-consistent*:

assumes *vpeq*: $\forall d \in r\text{kinvolved } (SK\text{-EV}\text{-SIGNAL } EV\text{-SIGNAL}\text{-FINISH } partner) . rvpeq\ d\ s\ t$

shows *ev-signal-precondition partner* $u\ (\downarrow s) = ev\text{-signal}\text{-precondition } partner\ u\ (\downarrow t)$

proof–

from *assms ev-signal-precondition-weakly-step-consistent rstate-invariant*

show *?thesis*

unfolding *rvpeq-def rkinvolved-def*

by *auto*

qed

lemma *waiting-consistent*:

shows $\forall s\ t\ u\ a . rvpeq\ (r\text{current } s)\ s\ t \wedge (\forall d \in r\text{kinvolved } a . rvpeq\ d\ s\ t)$

$\wedge rvpeq\ u\ s\ t$

$\longrightarrow r\text{waiting } s\ u\ a = r\text{waiting } t\ u\ a$

proof–

{

fix *s t u a*

assume *vpeq*: $rvpeq\ (r\text{current } s)\ s\ t$

assume *vpeq-involved*: $\forall d \in r\text{kinvolved } a . rvpeq\ d\ s\ t$

assume *vpeq-u*: $rvpeq\ u\ s\ t$

have $r\text{waiting } s\ u\ a = r\text{waiting } t\ u\ a$ **proof** (*cases a*)

case *SK-IPC*

thus $r\text{waiting } s\ u\ a = r\text{waiting } t\ u\ a$

using *ipc-precondition-of-partner-consistent vpeq-involved*

unfolding *waiting-def* **by** (*auto split add: ipc-stage-t.splits*)

next case *SK-EV-WAIT*

thus $r\text{waiting } s\ u\ a = r\text{waiting } t\ u\ a$

using *ev-signal-precondition-of-partner-consistent*

vpeq-involved vpeq vpeq-u

unfolding *waiting-def rkinvolved-def ev-signal-precondition-def*

rvpeq-def vpeq-def vpeq-local-def

by (*auto split add: ipc-stage-t.splits ev-wait-stage-t.splits ev-consume-t.splits*)

qed (*simp add: waiting-def, simp add: waiting-def*)

}

thus *?thesis* **by** *auto*

qed

lemma *ipc-precondition-ensures-ifp*:

assumes *ipc-precondition (current s) dir partner page s*

and *atomic-step-invariant s*

shows *rifp partner (current s)*

proof –

let $?sp = \lambda t1\ t2 . Policy.sp\text{-spec}\text{-subj}\text{-subj } (partition\ t1) (partition\ t2)$

have $?sp\ (current\ s)\ partner \vee ?sp\ partner\ (current\ s)$

using *assms unfolding ipc-precondition-def atomic-step-invariant-def sp-subset-def*

by (*cases dir, auto*)

thus *?thesis*

unfolding *rifp-def* **using** *Policy-properties.ifp-compatible-with-sp-spec* **by** *auto*

qed

lemma *ev-signal-precondition-ensures-ifp*:

assumes *ev-signal-precondition (current s) partner s*

and *atomic-step-invariant s*

shows *rifp partner (current s)*

proof –

let $?sp = \lambda t1\ t2 . Policy.sp\text{-spec}\text{-subj}\text{-subj } (partition\ t1) (partition\ t2)$

have $?sp\ (current\ s)\ partner \vee ?sp\ partner\ (current\ s)$

```

using assms unfolding ev-signal-precondition-def atomic-step-invariant-def sp-subset-def
by (auto)
thus ?thesis
unfolding rifp-def using Policy-properties.ifp-compatible-with-sp-spec by auto
qed

```

lemma *involved-ifp*:

shows $\forall s a . \forall d \in r\text{involved } a . r\text{precondition } s (r\text{current } s) a \longrightarrow \text{rifp } d (r\text{current } s)$

proof–

```

{
  fix s a d
  assume d-involved:  $d \in r\text{involved } a$ 
  assume prec:  $r\text{precondition } s (r\text{current } s) a$ 
  from d-involved prec have  $\text{rifp } d (r\text{current } s)$ 
  using ipc-precondition-ensures-ifp ev-signal-precondition-ensures-ifp rstate-invariant
  unfolding rinvolved-def rprecondition-def atomic-step-precondition-def rcurrent-def Kernel.involved-def
  by(cases a,simp,auto split add: int-point-t.splits ipc-stage-t.splits ev-signal-stage-t.splits)
}
thus ?thesis by auto
qed

```

lemma *spec-of-waiting-ev*:

shows $\forall s a . r\text{waiting } s (r\text{current } s) (\text{SK-EV-WAIT EV-FINISH EV-CONSUME-ALL}) \longrightarrow r\text{step } s a = s$

unfolding *waiting-def*

by *auto*

lemma *spec-of-waiting-ev-w*:

shows $\forall s a . r\text{waiting } s (r\text{current } s) (\text{SK-EV-WAIT EV-WAIT EV-CONSUME-ALL}) \longrightarrow r\text{step } s (\text{SK-EV-WAIT EV-WAIT EV-CONSUME-ALL}) = s$

unfolding *rstep-def atomic-step-def*

by (*auto split add: int-point-t.splits ipc-stage-t.splits ev-wait-stage-t.splits*)

lemma *spec-of-waiting*:

shows $\forall s a . r\text{waiting } s (r\text{current } s) a \longrightarrow r\text{step } s a = s$

unfolding *waiting-def rstep-def atomic-step-def atomic-step-ipc-def*

atomic-step-ev-signal-def atomic-step-ev-wait-all-def

atomic-step-ev-wait-one-def

by(*auto split add: int-point-t.splits ipc-stage-t.splits ev-wait-stage-t.splits*)

end

3.9 Link implementation to CISK: the specific separation kernel is an interpretation of the generic model.

theory *link-separation-kernel-model-to-CISK*

imports *separation-kernel-model*

begin

We show that the separation kernel instantiation satisfies the specification of CISK.

theorem *CISK-proof-obligations-satisfied*:

shows

Controllable-Interruptible-Separation-Kernel

rstep

routput-f

($\uparrow s0$)

rcurrent
rcswitch
rkinvolved
rifp
rvpeq
rAS-set
rinvariant
rprecondition
raborting
rwaiting
rset-error-code

proof (*unfold-locales*)

- show that *rvpeq* is equivalence relation
- show** $\forall a b c u. (rvpeq u a b \wedge rvpeq u b c) \longrightarrow rvpeq u a c$
- and** $\forall a b u. rvpeq u a b \longrightarrow rvpeq u b a$
- and** $\forall a u. rvpeq u a a$
- using** *inst-vpeq-rel* **by** *metis+*
- show output consistency
- show** $\forall a s t. rvpeq (rcurrent s) s t \wedge rcurrent s = rcurrent t \longrightarrow routput-f s a = routput-f t a$
- using** *inst-output-consistency* **by** *metis*
- show reflexivity of *ifp*
- show** $\forall u. rifp u u$
- using** *inst-ifp-refl* **by** *metis*
- show step consistency
- show** $\forall s t u a. rvpeq u s t \wedge rvpeq (rcurrent s) s t \wedge True \wedge rprecondition s (rcurrent s) a \wedge True \wedge rprecondition t (rcurrent t) a \wedge rcurrent s = rcurrent t \longrightarrow rvpeq u (rstep s a) (rstep t a)$
- using** *inst-weakly-step-consistent* **by** *blast*
- show step atomicity
- show** $\forall s a. rcurrent (rstep s a) = rcurrent s$
- using** *inst-step-atomicity* **by** *metis*
- show** $\forall a s u. \neg rifp (rcurrent s) u \wedge True \wedge rprecondition s (rcurrent s) a \longrightarrow rvpeq u s (rstep s a)$
- using** *inst-local-respect* **by** *blast*
- show *cswitch* is independent of state
- show** $\forall n s t. rcurrent s = rcurrent t \longrightarrow rcurrent (rcswitch n s) = rcurrent (rcswitch n t)$
- using** *inst-cswitch-independent-of-state* **by** *metis*
- show *cswitch* consistency
- show** $\forall u s t n. rvpeq u s t \longrightarrow rvpeq u (rcswitch n s) (rcswitch n t)$
- using** *inst-cswitch-consistency* **by** *metis*
- Show the *empt* action sequence is in *AS-set*
- show** $[] \in rAS-set$
- unfolding** *rAS-set-def*
- by** *auto*
- The invariant for the initial state, already encoded in *rstate-t*
- show** *True*
- by** *auto*
- Step function of the invariant, already encoded in *rstate-t*
- show** $\forall s n. True \longrightarrow True$
- by** *auto*
- The precondition does not change with a context switch
- show** $\forall s d n a. rprecondition s d a \longrightarrow rprecondition (rcswitch n s) d a$
- using** *precondition-after-cswitch* **by** *blast*
- The precondition holds for the first action of each action sequence
- show** $\forall s d aseq. True \wedge aseq \in rAS-set \wedge aseq \neq [] \longrightarrow rprecondition s d (hd aseq)$
- using** *prec-first-IPC-action prec-first-EV-WAIT-action prec-first-EV-SIGNAL-action*
- unfolding** *rAS-set-def is-sub-seq-def*
- by** *auto*

— The precondition holds for the next action in an action sequence, assuming the sequence is not aborted or delayed

show $\forall s a a'. (\exists aseq \in rAS\text{-set}. is\text{-sub-}seq\ a\ a'\ aseq) \wedge True \wedge rprecondition\ s\ (rcurrent\ s)\ a \wedge \neg raborting\ s\ (rcurrent\ s)\ a \wedge \neg rwaiting\ s\ (rcurrent\ s)\ a \longrightarrow$
 $rprecondition\ (rstep\ s\ a)\ (rcurrent\ s)\ a'$

using *prec-after-IPC-step prec-after-EV-SIGNAL-step prec-after-EV-WAIT-step*

unfolding *rAS-set-def is-sub-seq-def*

by *auto*

— Steps of other domains do not influence the precondition

show $\forall s d a a'. rcurrent\ s \neq d \wedge rprecondition\ s\ d\ a \longrightarrow rprecondition\ (rstep\ s\ a')\ d\ a$

using *prec-dom-independent* **by** *blast*

— The invariant

show $\forall s a. True \longrightarrow True$

by *auto*

— Aborting does not depend on a context switch

show $\forall n s. raborting\ (rcswitch\ n\ s) = raborting\ s$

using *aborting-switch-independent* **by** *auto*

— Aborting does not depend on actions of other domains

show $\forall s a d. rcurrent\ s \neq d \longrightarrow raborting\ (rstep\ s\ a)\ d = raborting\ s\ d$

using *aborting-dom-independent* **by** *auto*

— Aborting is consistent

show $\forall s t u. rypeq\ u\ s\ t \longrightarrow raborting\ s\ u = raborting\ t\ u$

using *raborting-consistent* **by** *auto*

— Waiting does not depend on a context switch

show $\forall n s. rwaiting\ (rcswitch\ n\ s) = rwaiting\ s$

using *waiting-switch-independent* **by** *auto*

— Waiting is consistent

show $\forall s t u a. rypeq\ (rcurrent\ s)\ s\ t \wedge (\forall d \in rkinvolved\ a. rypeq\ d\ s\ t) \wedge rypeq\ u\ s\ t$
 $\longrightarrow rwaiting\ s\ u\ a = rwaiting\ t\ u\ a$

unfolding *Kernel.involved-def*

using *waiting-consistent* **by** *auto*

— Domains that are involved in an action may influence the domain of the action

show $\forall s a. \forall d \in rkinvolved\ a. rprecondition\ s\ (rcurrent\ s)\ a \longrightarrow rjfp\ d\ (rcurrent\ s)$

using *involved-ifp* **by** *blast*

— An action that is waiting does not change the state

show $\forall s a. rwaiting\ s\ (rcurrent\ s)\ a \longrightarrow rstep\ s\ a = s$

using *spec-of-waiting* **by** *blast*

— Proof obligations for *set-error-code*. Right now, they are all trivial

show $\forall s d a' a. rcurrent\ s \neq d \wedge raborting\ s\ d\ a \longrightarrow raborting\ (rset\text{-error-code}\ s\ a')\ d\ a$

unfolding *rset-error-code-def*

by *auto*

show $\forall s t u a. rypeq\ u\ s\ t \longrightarrow rypeq\ u\ (rset\text{-error-code}\ s\ a)\ (rset\text{-error-code}\ t\ a)$

unfolding *rset-error-code-def*

by *auto*

show $\forall s u a. \neg rjfp\ (rcurrent\ s)\ u \longrightarrow rypeq\ u\ s\ (rset\text{-error-code}\ s\ a)$

unfolding *rset-error-code-def*

by *(metis $\langle \forall a u. rypeq\ u\ a \ a \rangle$)*

show $\forall s a. rcurrent\ (rset\text{-error-code}\ s\ a) = rcurrent\ s$

unfolding *rset-error-code-def*

by *auto*

show $\forall s d a a'. rprecondition\ s\ d\ a \wedge raborting\ s\ (rcurrent\ s)\ a' \longrightarrow rprecondition\ (rset\text{-error-code}\ s\ a')\ d\ a$

unfolding *rset-error-code-def*

by *auto*

show $\forall s d a' a. rcurrent\ s \neq d \wedge rwaiting\ s\ d\ a \longrightarrow rwaiting\ (rset\text{-error-code}\ s\ a')\ d\ a$

unfolding *rset-error-code-def*

by *auto*

qed

Now we can instantiate CISK with some initial state, interrupt function, etc.

interpretation *Inst:*

Controllable-Interruptible-Separation-Kernel

rstep — step function, without program stack
routput-f — output function
 $\uparrow s0$ — initial state
rcurrent — returns the currently active domain
rcswitch — switches the currently active domain
(op =) 42 — interrupt function (yet unspecified)
rkinvolved — returns a set of threads involved in the give action
rifp — information flow policy
rvpeq — view partitioning
rAS-set — the set of valid action sequences
rinvariant — the state invariant
rprecondition — the precondition for doing an action
raborting — condition under which an action is aborted
rwaiting — condition under which an action is delayed
rset-error-code — updates the state. Has no meaning in the current model.

using *CISK-proof-obligations-satisfied by auto*

The main theorem: the instantiation implements the information flow policy *ifp*.

theorem *risecure:*

Inst.isecure

using *Inst.unwinding-implies-isecure-CISK*

by *blast*

end

4 Conclusion

We have introduced a theory of intransitive non-interference for separation kernels with control. We have shown that it can be instantiated for a simple API consisting of IPC and events.

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A New Theory of Intransitive Noninterference for Separation Kernels with Control

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Abstract. Intransitive noninterference has been a widely studied topic in the last few decades. Several well-established methodologies apply interactive theorem proving to formulate a noninterference theorem over abstract academic models. In joint work with several industrial and academic partners throughout Europe, we are helping in the certification process of PikeOS, an industrial separation kernel developed at SYSGO. In this process, established theories could not be applied. We present a new generic model of separation kernels and a new theory of intransitive noninterference. The model is rich in detail, making it suitable for formal verification of realistic and industrial systems such as PikeOS. Using a refinement-based theorem proving approach, we ensure that proofs remain manageable.

Keywords: Separation Kernel, Intransitive Noninterference, Information Flow, Formal Methods

1 Introduction

Separation kernels are at the heart of many modern security-critical systems [1]. With next generation technology in cars, aircrafts and medical devices becoming more and more interconnected, a platform that offers secure decomposition of embedded systems becomes crucial for safe and secure performance. PikeOS, a separation kernel developed at SYSGO, is an operating system providing such an environment [2,3]. A consortium of several European partners from industry and academia works on certification of PikeOS up to at least EAL5+. Our aim is to derive a precise model of PikeOS and a precise formulation of the PikeOS security policy, to be used for the Common Criteria evaluation of PikeOS.

A crucial security property of separation kernels is *intransitive noninterference*. This property is typically required for systems with multiple independent levels of security (MILS) such as PikeOS. It ensures that a given security policy over different subjects of the system is obeyed. Such a security policy dictates which subjects may flow information to which other subjects.

Intransitive noninterference has been an active research field for the last three decades. Several papers have been published on defining intransitive noninterference and on unwinding methodologies that enable the proof of intransitive noninterference from local proof obligations. However, in the certification process of PikeOS these existing methodologies could not be directly applied. Generally, the methodologies are based on highly abstract generic models of computation. The gap between such an abstract model and the reality of PikeOS is large, making application of the methodologies tedious and cumbersome.

This paper presents a new generic model for separation kernels called CISK (for: Controlled Interruptible Separation Kernel). This model is rich in detail and contains several facets present in all separation kernels, such as *interrupts*, *context switches* between domains and a notion of *control*. Regarding the latter, this concerns the fact that the kernel exercises control over the executions as performed by the domains. The kernel can, e.g., decide to skip actions of the domains, or abort them halfway.

We have adopted and reformulated Rushby’s definition of intransitive noninterference [4]. Our definition improves on Rushby’s ipurge-based definition in two ways. First, we do not assume a static mapping of actions to domains, since for an OS kernel such a mapping does not necessarily exist [5]. Secondly, we prove more directly that domains perform securely in presence of attackers. Instead of removing actions, we replace the program code of an attacking domain by arbitrary other program code from the attack surface.

Overview Generally, there are two conflicting interests when using a generic model. On the one hand the model must be sufficiently abstract to ensure that theorems and proofs remain manageable. On the other hand, the model must be rich enough and must contain sufficient domain-knowledge to allow easy instantiation. Rushby’s model, for example, is on one end of the spectrum: it is basically a Mealy machine, which is a highly abstract notion of computation, consisting only of state, input and output [4]. The model and its proofs are manageable, but making a realistic instantiation is tedious, requires complicated proofs and quickly becomes infeasible.

We propose a solution to this conflicting trade-off, by providing a refinable model and a new theorem of intransitive noninterference. Starting with a highly generic and abstract model of a separation kernel, we define and prove security for this model. Then, the model is enriched step-by-step. As each step is a refinement of the previous step, all the proofs can be automatically reused. This methodology ensures manageable proofs. The result of these refinement-based proofs is a rich generic model that can be instantiated easily.

Figure 1 shows an overview. The initial model “Kernel” is close to a Mealy machine, but has several facets added, including interrupts, context switches and control. This model is refined in such a way that each refinement basically inserts an adjective before “Kernel”.

The first refinement adds separation, yielding a model of a Separation Kernel (SK). A security policy is added that dictates which domains may flow infor-

Fig. 1. Overview of refinements

mation to each other. Local proof obligations (PO's) are added from which a global theorem of noninterference is proven. In terminology of Rushby, this global theorem is the *unwinding* of the local proof obligations.

In the second refinement calls to the kernel are no longer considered atomic, yielding an Interruptible Separation Kernel (ISK). In this model, one call to the kernel is represented by an *action sequence*. Consider, for example, an IPC call. From the point of view of the programmer this is one kernel call. From the point of view of the kernel it is an action sequence consisting of three stages IPC_PREP, IPC_WAIT, and IPC_SEND. After each stage, an interrupt may occur that switches the current context. A consequence of allowing interruptible action sequences is that it is no longer the case that any execution, i.e., any combination of atomic kernel actions, is realistic. We formulate a definition of *realistic execution* and weaken the proof obligations of the model to apply only to realistic executions.

The final refinement provides an interpretation of control that allows atomic kernel actions to be aborted or delayed. Additional PO's are required to ensure that noninterference is still provided. This yields a Controlled Interruptible Separation Kernel (CISK). When sequences of kernel actions are aborted, error codes can be transmitted to other domains. Consider, for example, an IPC call. After the PREP stage, the kernel can decide to abort the action. The IPC action sequence will not be continued and error codes may be sent out. At the WAIT stage, the kernel can delay the action sequence until the communication partner of the IPC call is ready to receive.

2 CISK

This section presents a generic model of a Controlled Interruptible Separation Kernel. In this model, the entire system consists of several subjects running on top of the kernel. Each subject has its own program code. The program code

is modelled as a list of kernel calls. Each kernel call can trigger a sequence of atomic kernel actions.

First, we present the execution semantics of the model in an informal way. We proceed by explaining a new definition of intransitive noninterference and then detail the assumptions behind this model used to prove security.

2.1 Execution Semantics

The model makes use of the following types. Between brackets are the variable names used to refer to objects of these types.

- '**dom_t** (d, u, v, w, \dots) A domain is an entity executing actions and making calls to the kernel. Later on, we define security at the level of domains.
- '**action_t** (a_0, a_1, \dots) Actions represent atomic instructions that are executed by the kernel. As kernel actions are assumed to be atomic, an interrupt may occur after each kernel action.
- '**action_t execution** ($\alpha_0, \alpha_1, \dots$) An execution of some domain is the code or the program that is executed by the domain. One call from a domain to the kernel will typically trigger a succession of one or more kernel actions. Therefore, an execution is represented as a list of *sequences* of kernel actions. Non-kernel actions are not take into account.
- '**state_t** (s, t, \dots) The state is assumed to contain information about the resources of the system, as well as which domain is currently active. A state does *not* need to include a program stack, as in our model the actions that are executed are modelled separately.
- '**output_t** Given the current state and the program stack the observable output can be determined.
- '**time_t** (n, n', \dots) Time is modelled using natural numbers. Each atomic kernel action can be executed within one time unit.

A *system execution* is a mapping of executions to domains, i.e., it assigns to each domain an execution. We use variables x_0, x_1, \dots to refer to system executions. Figure 2 presents an overview of the types used for modelling the program code of the system.

Fig. 2. Overview of types

Algorithm 1 presents pseudo code of CISK. Repeatedly the kernel executes sequences of kernel actions. In each repetition, the current time is updated. An interrupt can occur, raising a context switch. Otherwise, the kernel executes code according to the execution of the currently active domain. Variable A represents the action sequence that is currently being executed by the currently active domain. If the currently active domain is executing program code, or is idling, A is the empty list. In this case, the kernel fetches the next action sequence from the execution. If this is a kernel action (i.e., if $|A| > 0$), three cases can occur. First, based on the current state and the current action, the action sequence can be aborted. The kernel updates A and may send error codes to other domains. Secondly, based on the current state, the current action can be in a waiting state. No state change occurs. Thirdly, the action can be executed and A is updated accordingly.

Algorithm 1 Pseudo Code for CISK

```

1: loop
2:   update clock
3:   if interrupt occurs then
4:     perform context switch
5:   else
6:     if  $|A| == 0$  then
7:        $A :=$  fetch action sequence from execution
8:     end if
9:     if  $|A| > 0$  then
10:      if  $A[0]$  is aborting then
11:         $A := []$ 
12:        send error codes to involved domains
13:      else if  $A[0]$  is waiting then
14:        skip
15:      else
16:        execute  $A[0]$ 
17:         $A := tl(A)$ 
18:      end if
19:    end if
20:  end if
21: end loop

```

Each loop in Algorithm 1 is considered as one unit of time. Note that we do not assume that each unit of time is the same size. We do assume that one atomic kernel action is done within one time unit. At each time slot, function *output* returns the observable behavior from the system. Function \mathbb{D} returns the currently active domain. At all times, only one domain can be active. Function *run* embodies Algorithm 1. Function *realistic* is a predicate over executions and returns true if and only if an execution can realistically be executed by some domain. This function is overloaded so that it applies to system executions as

well: in that cases it returns true if and only if for all domains their executions are realistic.

A *security policy* (denoted \rightsquigarrow) is a relation over domains. It dictates which domains may flow information to which other domains. We assume an intransitive security policy that allows, e.g, a configuration in which $w \rightsquigarrow v \rightsquigarrow u$, but $w \not\rightsquigarrow u$. In such a configuration, domain w may flow information to u but *only* through v . The following classification is introduced to reason about intransitive noninterference.

unrelated Domain d is unrelated to domain u if and only if the security policy dictates that there is no path from domain d to u .

intermediary An intermediary for u is defined as a domain v for which there exists an information flow from some domain w to u via v , but no direct information flow from w to u is allowed. Intermediaries are also called gateways.

indirect source An indirect source for u is defined as a domain w that may indirectly flow information to u , but not directly.

Any domain other than u is always one of the above, i.e., either unrelated to u , an intermediary for u or an indirect source of u . Domain u is none of the above.

2.2 Noninterference for CISK

For any domain u , two types of domains have restricted access to that domain: unrelated domains have no right to influence domain u at all, and indirect sources can only influence u through an intermediary. We therefore define two notions of noninterference.

The first one deals with unrelated domains. It is a small adaptation of Rushby's conventional purging. For sake of readability we have adopted that term. Function *purge* takes as input the system execution and the domain u for which the system execution is purged. For any domain unrelated to u , the program stack is replaced by any arbitrary other execution that could be realistically executed by that domain. All other domains are left unchanged.

definition *purge* ::

$$\begin{aligned}
 & ('dom-t \Rightarrow 'action-t \text{ execution}) \Rightarrow 'dom-t \Rightarrow ('dom-t \Rightarrow 'action-t \text{ execution}) \\
 \mathbf{where} \text{ } \mathit{purge} \ x \ u \equiv & \lambda \ d \ . \ \text{if unrelated } d \ u \ \text{then} \\
 & \quad \text{SOME } \alpha \ . \ \text{realistic } \alpha \\
 & \quad \text{else} \\
 & \quad \quad x \ d
 \end{aligned}$$

Figure 3 expresses the intuition behind noninterference for unrelated domains. Let d be a domain unrelated to u . For any execution x of the system, and at any time slot n , the observable output of two states is compared. The first state s_f is the state after a run of the system as it is. The second state is the state after doing a purged run. In this run, the execution of d has been

Fig. 3. Noninterference for unrelated domains. The prime indicates any arbitrary execution of the given domain.

replaced by some arbitrary other execution d' , which is possibly an attacker. The observable output of the two states must always be equivalent, indicating that the attacker has no influence on domain u .

definition NI-unrelated :: bool

where NI-unrelated $\equiv \forall x n .$

realistic $x \longrightarrow$

(let s-f = run n s0 x in

output s-f = output (run n s0 (purge x (\mathbb{D} s-f))))

The second notion of noninterference deals with indirect sources. Consider a system with three domains u, v, w and assume that w is an indirect source of u and v is an intermediary, i.e., $w \rightsquigarrow v \rightsquigarrow u$, but $w \not\rightsquigarrow u$. We show that information flow from w to u occurs through v *only*, by showing that if v would be inactive there is no information flow from w to u (see Figure 4). In other words, if the intermediary is inactive, the execution of domain w can be replaced by any arbitrary other execution (possibly an attacker) without influencing domain u .

Fig. 4. Noninterference for indirect sources. The prime indicates any arbitrary execution of the given domain. The crossed domains are inactive.

We argue that any system that has this property is secure with respect to the security policy. Assume that domain w is able to violate the security policy by influencing domain u directly, i.e., without intermediary v . A certain sequence α_A of actions of w performs this security breach, indicating that all actions in α_A are in the attack surface of w . We show that this violates the property as described in Figure 4.

Consider the same system where domain w performs some execution α that does not influence u in any way (e.g., it is idle). Since w' represents *any* possible execution from the attack surface, we can choose the policy violating execution α_A for the execution of w' . By assumption, execution α_A does not in-

clude actions concerning domain v . Therefore, the system $[w, \not{v}, u]$ is not equal to $[w', \not{v}, u]$. This violates the property as expressed in Figure 4.

The definition of noninterference for indirect sources requires two purging functions, denoted $ipurge_l$ and $ipurge_r$. This stands for intransitive purge left and right with respect to Figure 4. The first removes all possible influence of intermediary v in u . It removes the execution of v , ensuring that v cannot send any data to u . It also removes certain actions within domain u itself. Domain u might perform action sequences whose execution depends on the state of domain v . When domain u performs such actions, intermediary v can influence u even without performing actions. By removing those actions as well as all actions executed by intermediary v , the result of $ipurge_l$ is a system execution in which intermediary v does not influence u in any way (see the left hand side of Figure 4).

definition $ipurge_l$::

$(\text{'dom-t} \Rightarrow \text{'action-t execution}) \Rightarrow \text{'dom-t} \Rightarrow (\text{'dom-t} \Rightarrow \text{'action-t execution})$

where

$ipurge_l\ x\ u \equiv \lambda\ d . \text{ if intermediary } d\ u\ \text{ then}$
 $\quad \square$
 $\quad \text{else if } d = u\ \text{ then}$
 $\quad \quad \text{remove-gateway-communications } u\ (x\ u)$
 $\quad \text{else}$
 $\quad \quad x\ d$

The second purge function removes all possible influence of intermediary v and replaces the indirect sources by arbitrary executions, as shown in the right hand side of Figure 4.

definition $ipurge_r$::

$(\text{'dom-t} \Rightarrow \text{'action-t execution}) \Rightarrow \text{'dom-t} \Rightarrow (\text{'dom-t} \Rightarrow \text{'action-t execution})$

where

$ipurge_r\ x\ u \equiv \lambda\ d . \text{ if intermediary } d\ u\ \text{ then}$
 $\quad \square$
 $\quad \text{else if ind-source } d\ u\ \text{ then}$
 $\quad \quad \text{SOME } \alpha . \text{ realistic } \alpha$
 $\quad \text{else if } d = u\ \text{ then}$
 $\quad \quad \text{remove-gateway-communications } u\ (x\ u)$
 $\quad \text{else}$
 $\quad \quad x\ d$

Using these two purging functions, we formulate noninterference for indirect sources. State s_f is the state after a run of the system as it is. Again, the observable output of two states at a certain time slot is compared. The two compared states have been obtained by doing runs purged with the two purging functions.

definition NI-indirect-sources :: bool

where NI-indirect-sources
 $\equiv \forall x \text{ n. realistic-executions } x \longrightarrow$
 $(\text{let s-f} = \text{run n s0 } x \text{ in}$
 $\text{output (run n s0 (ipurge-l } x \text{ (}\mathbb{D} \text{ s-f}))} =$
 $\text{output (run n s0 (ipurge-r } x \text{ (}\mathbb{D} \text{ s-f))))}$

Finally, we can define security for controlled, interruptible separation kernels:

definition secure :: bool
where secure \equiv NI-unrelated \wedge NI-indirect-sources

2.3 Proof Obligations

To prove security, we require a total of 32 assumptions. All of these assumptions are proof obligations, i.e., if one wants to make an interpretation of CISK one needs to discharge each one of these 32 assumptions. For that reason, we have taken care to make them as easy and small as possible. Each PO is *local*, i.e., deals with only one facet of the system. These local PO's are unwinded to the global security theorem.

Function *kstep* (for kernel step) computes the next state based on the current state s and a given action a (corresponding to Line 16 in Algorithm 1). We base proof obligations on a *state invariant* and *preconditions*. The state invariant is simply a predicate over states. It should return true for all reachable states. Ideally, but not necessarily, it returns false for unreachable states. If it does not return false for an unreachable state the model is too conservative, which does not harm soundness.

Since at all times the user can assume the state invariant to hold, we do not mention it any further. Function *prec* (for precondition) takes as input the current state and an atomic kernel action. It returns true if the preconditions necessary for executing the given action are met. The step function may assume that it makes sense to perform the given action, i.e., that any precondition that is necessary for execution of action a in state s is met. If not, it may return any result.

The major instrument used for defining local proof obligations is the concept of *view partitioning* [4]. A view partitioning is a per-domain equivalence relation on the set of states, denoted \sim^u . Given domain u , this equivalence relation reflects whether two states are equivalent from the point of view of domain u . It typically compares the contents of the given domain, i.e., the state of its memory locations. We will call two states s and t *u-equivalent* if and only if $s \sim^u t$.

Control is expressed in two functions *aborting* and *waiting*. Both functions take as input the current state s , an action a and the domain d that is executing the action. Function *aborting* returns the conditions under which an action sequence is aborted, corresponding to Line 10 in Algorithm 1. Whenever *aborting* returns true, action a is not executed but instead a state update can be done

sending, e.g., error codes to other domains. The remainder of the current action sequence is skipped. Similarly, function *waiting* returns the conditions under which an action is delayed (Line 13). As long as *waiting* returns true, the next action is delayed. Both control functions base their return values not only on domain d that is executing the given action, but also on other domains. Function *involved* returns, given an action, which other domains are involved in the control of that action.

Each refinement adds new assumptions to the model. We list the assumptions per refinement.

First Refinement: SK

Proof obligations concerning the step functions are modified versions of Rushby’s assumptions [4]. First, weak step consistency ensures that two u -equivalent states s and t remain u -equivalent after executing an action a , i.e., after completion of a call to function *kstep*. Rushby’s version is weakened by adding assumptions that the invariant holds for the current state and that the precondition for doing action a in states s and t holds. Also, the same domain is active in states s and t .

Weak Step Consistency:

$$s \stackrel{u}{\sim} t \wedge s \stackrel{\mathbb{D}}{\sim}^s t \wedge \text{prec } s (\mathbb{D} s) a \wedge \text{prec } t (\mathbb{D} t) a \wedge \mathbb{D} s = \mathbb{D} t \longrightarrow \text{vpeq } u (\text{kstep } s a) (\text{kstep } t a)$$

The system locally respects the security policy \rightsquigarrow if it ensures that whenever the domain currently active in state s cannot influence domain u , state s is u -equivalent to the state obtained by doing an action.

Locally Respects:

$$\mathbb{D} s \not\rightsquigarrow u \wedge \text{prec } s (\mathbb{D} s) a \longrightarrow \text{vpeq } u s (\text{kstep } s a)$$

A regular action cannot influence which domain is currently active. Also, we assume that an action can be executed within one time slot, and therefore within ‘now’ and the next context switch.

Step Atomicity:

$$\mathbb{D} (\text{kstep } s a) = \mathbb{D} s$$

We assume that \sim is an equivalence relation. The most important property of \sim is that equivalent states yield equivalent observable output.

Output Consistency:

$$s \stackrel{\mathbb{D}}{\sim}^s t \wedge \mathbb{D} s = \mathbb{D} t \longrightarrow \text{output } s = \text{output } t$$

A context switch cannot change the contents of any of the domains. At any time-slot n , executing a context switch must therefore preserve view-partitioning.

Context Switch Consistency:

$$s \stackrel{u}{\sim} t \longrightarrow (\text{cswitch } n s) \stackrel{u}{\sim} (\text{cswitch } n t)$$

The result of a context switch can depend on time, but is independent of the current state. This supposes a system with fixed time-partitioning.

Fixed Time Schedule:

$$\mathbb{D} s = \mathbb{D} t \longrightarrow \mathbb{D} (\text{cswitch } n \ s) = \mathbb{D} (\text{cswitch } n \ t)$$

We pose no proof obligations on function interrupt other than its signature: function interrupt takes as input the current time and returns true if and only if an interrupt occurs in that time slot. Finally, a context switch cannot have any influence on the preconditions of the actions.

Preconditions after Context Switch:

$$\text{prec } s \ d \ a \longrightarrow \text{prec } (\text{cswitch } n \ s) \ d \ a$$

Second Refinement: ISK

We assume the existence of function

$$\text{AS-set} :: ('a \text{action-t list}) \text{ set}$$

which returns a set of action sequences. Each action sequence corresponds to one call to the kernel. For example, if the kernel only allows IPC calls, an interpretation of AS-set can be:

$$\text{AS-set} = \{[\text{IPC_PREP}, \text{IPC_WAIT}, \text{IPC_SEND}]\}$$

The precondition function is structured with respect to the action sequences from AS-set. This means that 1.) at all times and for any action sequence the precondition must allow the start of a new action sequence and 2.) each individual action must ensure the precondition for its successor. For example, the action sequence defining an IPC call induces the following proof obligations:

- $\text{prec } s \ (\mathbb{D} \ s) \ \text{IPC_PREP}$
- $\text{prec } s \ (\mathbb{D} \ s) \ \text{IPC_PREP} \longrightarrow \text{prec } (\text{kstep } s \ \text{IPC_PREP}) \ (\mathbb{D} \ s) \ \text{IPC_WAIT}$
if the action sequence is not aborted or delayed
- $\text{prec } s \ (\mathbb{D} \ s) \ \text{IPC_WAIT} \longrightarrow \text{prec } (\text{kstep } s \ \text{IPC_WAIT}) \ (\mathbb{D} \ s) \ \text{IPC_SEND}$
if the action sequence is not aborted or delayed

The kernel can always initiate an IPC action sequence. Once it has passed the PREP stage (i.e., the action sequence has not been aborted or delayed), the precondition for executing the WAIT stage must be met. Once it has passed the WAIT stage, the precondition for executing the SEND stage must be met. First, we formulate a proof obligation for the first actions of the action sequences.

Precondition for starting action sequences:

$$\alpha \in \text{AS-set} \wedge \alpha \neq [] \longrightarrow \text{prec } s \ d \ (\text{hd } \alpha)$$

Secondly, we formulate a proof obligation ensuring that the action sequence holds while executing the action sequence. Function “sub-seq” returns true if and only if the given two actions are a consecutive pair in the given action sequence. For example, “sub-seq IPC_WAIT IPC_SEND” evaluates to True for the IPC action sequence. For any consecutive pair of actions a and a' , the step function must ensure the precondition for a' after execution of action a .

Precondition for executing action sequences:

$$(\exists \alpha \in \text{AS-set} . \text{sub-seq } a \ a' \ \alpha) \wedge \neg \text{aborting } s \ (\mathbb{D} \ s) \ a \wedge \neg \text{waiting } s \ (\mathbb{D} \ s) \ a \wedge$$

$$\text{prec } s \ (\mathbb{D} \ s) \ a \longrightarrow \text{prec } (\text{kstep } s \ a) \ (\mathbb{D} \ s) \ a'$$

Finally, the precondition can be based on local information of the current domain only.

Precondition Locally Respects:

$$\mathbb{D} \ s \neq d \wedge \text{prec } s \ d \ a \longrightarrow \text{prec } (\text{kstep } s \ a') \ d \ a$$

Third Refinement: CISK

The preconditions that determine whether an action can be executed may base that decision on local information of the current domain only. For the control functions, this is too restrictive. For example, the WAIT stage of an IPC call proceeds only when the communication partner has passed its WAIT stage. In this case, the waiting conditions depend on two domains. For this reason, we require consistency of the control functions only when two states s and t are u -equivalent for the current domain *and* for all domains involved in the action. We formulate PO's for function waiting; similar ones exist for function aborting.

Consistency of Waiting:

$$s \stackrel{\mathbb{D} \ s}{\sim} t \wedge \forall d \in \text{involved } a . s \stackrel{d}{\sim} t \longrightarrow \text{waiting } s \ u \ a = \text{waiting } t \ u \ a$$

If some action is declared to be involved with some partner domain d , then this partner can influence the behavior of domain u executing that action. Consider again the IPC call. The communication partner can control whether the IPC call of domain u passes through the WAIT stage. As it can influence u , it must be allowed to do so. The following proof obligation enforces that the security policy allows involved domains to influence the executing domain.

Interaction Allowed Involved Domains:

$$\forall d \in \text{involved } a . \text{prec } s \ (\mathbb{D} \ s) \ a \longrightarrow \text{ia } d \ (\mathbb{D} \ s)$$

Finally, we make an assumption on the attack surface explicit. The attack surface is defined by function *realistic* which takes as input an execution and returns true if and only if the given execution is realistic. We assume that an attacker can perform any set of kernel calls, i.e., any set of action sequences, in any order. It can, however, not tamper with the order in which these action sequences are executed. Whenever it starts, e.g., an IPC call, the kernel proceeds with the PREP, WAIT and SEND stages in that order. The only influence in executing an action sequence is exercised by the control functions. Also, we assume that the attack surface is equal for all domains. These assumptions can be formulated using a subset relation as follows:

Attack Surface:

$$\text{realistic } \alpha \equiv \text{set } \alpha \subseteq \text{AS-set}$$

3 Isabelle Formalization

All definitions and proofs have been formalized in Isabelle/HOL [6]. Isabelle/HOL is a theorem prover with higher order logic and facilities for data types, records,

inductive sets and recursive functions. We shortly introduce two concepts of Isabelle/HOL that are used in this section. First, *locales* provide a namespace in which fixed variables and local assumptions can be used to prove theorems [7]. Locales can be used for modular proofs and for refinements. Secondly, Isabelle/HOL provides an *option type*, which is used to represent that a variable can either be some value x (denoted “Some x ”) or not (denoted “None”).

The following notation is often used in the proofs and definitions of this section. The expression “ $m \rightarrow f$ ” means “First compute m , if it is None then return True, otherwise pass the results to f ”. This can be generalized to multiple inputs: “ $m_1 || m_2 \rightarrow \alpha$ ” represents “First compute m_1 and m_2 , if one of them is None then return True, otherwise pass the result to α ”.

We prove that the PO’s as presented in the previous section are sufficient for intransitive noninterference. This proof is structured using four locales, each corresponding to a refinement in Figure 1. Security is proven for the first refinement (SK) and then transferred to ISK and CISK.

3.1 K

The first locale defines a “Kernel” in a generalized way. No assumptions are made on which actions can be executed and under which conditions, that is, function $kprec_0$ (for: kernel precondition) is left completely generic. The subscript zero is to express that this is a generic function, that is later going to be refined. The control mechanism is kept generic as well, meaning that in this model there is no concept of “waiting” or “aborting”. A generic control mechanism is represented by an unconstrained function *control* that takes as input the current state, the domain that is currently active and the current system execution. It returns three objects:

1. the action that is going to be executed next or “None” when the given domain is idling in the current time-slot. Given a state s and a system execution x , this object is denoted with $control.a\ s\ x$.
2. a system execution that is the updated system execution. The control mechanism can, e.g., disable a domain by emptying its execution, or skip the current action sequence. When executing action a , typically, this action will be removed from the current execution (i.e., updating the program stack). Given a state s and a system execution x , the next system execution is denoted with $control.x\ s\ x$.
3. a state. The control mechanism is allowed to update the state to send out, e.g., error codes. Given a state s and a system execution x , the next system execution is denoted with $control.s\ s\ x$.

locale Kernel =

```

fixes kstep :: 'state-t  $\Rightarrow$  'action-t  $\Rightarrow$  'state-t
and output-f :: 'state-t  $\Rightarrow$  'action-t  $\Rightarrow$  'output-t
and s0 :: 'state-t
and  $\mathbb{D}$  :: 'state-t  $\Rightarrow$  'dom-t

```

```

and cswitch :: time-t ⇒ 'state-t ⇒ 'state-t
and interrupt :: time-t ⇒ bool
and kprec0 :: 'state-t ⇒ 'action-t ⇒ bool
and realistic :: 'action-t execution ⇒ bool
and control :: 'state-t ⇒ 'dom-t ⇒ 'action-t execution ⇒
    (('action-t option) × 'action-t execution × 'state-t)

```

Upon these generic functions, we build a run function that defines the execution semantics. Function *dom-empty* takes as input a domain execution and returns true if and only if the execution is empty. Function *prec₀* is a wrapper over function *kprec₀*: if the given action is None, it returns true. Otherwise, it passes the action as a parameter to function *kprec₀*.

```

definition prec :: state-t ⇒ 'action-t option ⇒ bool
where prec s a ≡ a → kprec0 s

```

Similarly, function *step* is a wrapper over function *kstep*: if the given action is None, it performs no action and returns that state unchanged. Otherwise, it executes the given action.

A run consists of consecutively running sequences of actions. These sequences are interruptible. Function *run* first checks whether an interrupt occurs. When this happens, function *cswitch* may switch the context. Otherwise, generic function *control* is used to determine the next action *a*, which also yields a new state *s'* and the updated system execution. Action *a* is executed by executing (*step s' a*).

Since function *kprec₀* is generic, it is impossible to know whether at a given time and in a given state action *a* can actually be executed. Therefore, the run function is partial. As soon as it would execute (*step s' a*) for some action *a* that cannot be done according to the precondition, function *run* does not return any result.

```

function run ::
time-t ⇒ 'state-t option ⇒ ('dom-t ⇒ 'action-t execution) ⇒ 'state-t option
where
run 0 s x = s
| run (Suc n) None x = None
| interrupt (Suc n) ⇒
run (Suc n) (Some s) x = run n (Some (cswitch (Suc n) s)) x
| dom-empty(x (current s)) ⇒
run (Suc n) (Some s) x = run n (Some s) x
| ¬prec (control.s s x) (control.a s x) ⇒
run (Suc n) (Some s) x = None
| otherwise
run (Suc n) (Some s) x =
run n (Some (step (control.s s x) (control.a s x))) (control.x s x)

```

3.2 SK

Having defined a locale that models a generic kernel, we extend this locale with separation. A security policy is represented by function *ia* (for: interaction allowed). A view-partitioning is introduced by function *vpeq* (for: view-partitioning equivalent). A list of assumptions is added, which have been introduced in Section 2.3. Among others, these include weak step consistency, locally respects, output consistency and context switch related assumptions. Function *vpeq* is assumed to be an equivalence relation, and we assume that security policy *ia* is reflexive (domains are allowed to interact with themselves).

```

locale Separation-Kernel = Kernel
+
fixes ia :: 'dom-t  $\Rightarrow$  'dom-t  $\Rightarrow$  bool
and vpeq :: 'dom-t  $\Rightarrow$  'state-t  $\Rightarrow$  'state-t  $\Rightarrow$  bool
assumes
:

```

As explained in Section 2.2 security consists of two parts: NI-unrelated for unrelated domains and NI-indirect-sources for indirect sources. We provide the structure of the proof of indirect sources. The proofs for unrelated domains are equal in structure, but simpler. For more details, we refer to the Isabelle source code.

The first step is to define noninterference for indirect sources for the partial run function. We formulate the theorem in such a way, that if the run function yields None, the theorem holds vacuously. Function *same-output* takes as input two states and returns true if and only if the states show the same observable behavior.

```

theorem unwinding-implies-NI-indirect-sources-partial:
shows run n (Some s0) x  $\rightarrow$ 
      ( $\lambda$  s-f . run n (Some s0) (ipurge-l x ( $\mathbb{D}$  s-f)) ||
        run n (Some s0) (ipurge-r x ( $\mathbb{D}$  s-f))  $\rightarrow$ 
        same-output)

```

Basically, this theorem is a partial version of function NI-indirect-sources defined in Section 2.2.

We use two lemma's to prove the theorem. The first states that the system is view-partitioned. For any domain *u*, let state *s_l* be the result of a run with left-purging and state *s_r* be the result of a right-purged run. If one of these runs result in None, then we do not prove anything and the theorem will hold vacuously. Otherwise, the two states shall be *u*-equivalent and shall have the same active domain. Function *same- \mathbb{D}* takes as input two states and returns true if and only if the states have the same currently active domain.

lemma view-partitioned:

shows run n (Some s0) (ipurge-l x u) ||
 run n (Some s0) (ipurge-r x u) \rightarrow
 $\lambda s-l s-r. \text{vpeq } u \text{ s-l s-r} \wedge \text{same-}\mathbb{D} \text{ s-l s-r}$

The second lemma shows that switching and interrupts are state-independent. For any run, if two states s and t have the same currently active domain, then after n steps they still have the same currently active domain. Again, if one of the states is None, the theorem becomes vacuously true.

lemma current-independent-of-domain-actions:

assumes $s \parallel t \rightarrow \text{same-}\mathbb{D}$
shows run n s x_0 || run n t $x_1 \rightarrow \text{same-}\mathbb{D}$

These two lemma's can be used to prove the final theorem for indirect sources. Let u be some domain. Let s_f be the state after a run of the system as it is. Let s_l and s_r be the states after a run of the system with left-purging and right-purging respectively. Whenever one of these runs yield None, the theorem holds vacuously. Otherwise, the first lemma shows that:

$$\text{vpeq } u \text{ s}_l \text{ s}_r \wedge \mathbb{D} \text{ s}_l = \mathbb{D} \text{ s}_r$$

That is, the two purged runs are u -equivalent and have the same currently active domain. The second lemma shows that state s_f has the same currently active domain as both states s_l and s_r . In other words, a purged run always has the same active domain at each time-slot.

$$\mathbb{D} \text{ s}_f = \mathbb{D} \text{ s}_r$$

Using these two facts, output consistency can be used to show that for any action, the observable output is equivalent in states s_l and s_r , showing the thesis.

Lemma current-independent-of-domain-actions can be proven by induction over function run. It requires the assumptions "Context Switch Consistency", "Fixed Time Schedule" and "Step Atomicity".

Lemma view-partitioned is more involved. The first step in the proof is to generalize such that it can be proven by structural induction over function *run*. First, instead of reasoning about initial state s_0 and a system execution x , we reason about two states s and t and their corresponding system executions x_0 and x_1 . Secondly, the lemma in its current formulation shows u -equivalence of the two states only. This is insufficient in the proof, as "Weak Step Consistency" not only requires equivalence of domain u , but equivalence of the currently active domain as well. The induction hypothesis must therefore also make claims about other domains than u . We prove equivalence not only for domain u , but for any domain that can interact with u and that is not an intermediary. This is defined in function vpeq-inductive.

definition vpeq-inductive ::

'state-t option \Rightarrow 'state-t option \Rightarrow 'dom-t \Rightarrow bool

where vpeq-inductive s t u \equiv

$s \parallel t \rightarrow \lambda s \text{ t} . (\forall v . \text{ia } v \text{ u} \wedge \neg \text{intermediary } v \text{ u} \rightarrow \text{vpeq } v \text{ s } t) \wedge$

$s \parallel t \rightarrow \text{same-}\mathbb{D}$

The two system executions x_0 and x_1 are the result of left- and right-purging. This is expressed as a relation between the two system executions, that holds if and only if the two system executions agree on all domains that can influence domain u . Also, both executions have purged the intermediaries.

definition ipurged-relation

where ipurged-relation $u \ x_0 \ x_1 \equiv$
 $\forall d . (\text{ia } d \ u \longrightarrow x_0 \ d = x_1 \ d) \wedge (\text{intermediary } d \ u \longrightarrow x_1 \ d = [])$

Using these two definitions, we formulate a generalized version of Lemma view-partitioned. This lemma can be proven by structural induction over the run function. From this lemma, the non-inductive version can easily be proven.

lemma view-partitioned-inductive:

assumes vpeq-inductive $u \ s \ t$
assumes ipurged-relation $u \ x_0 \ x_1$
shows vpeq-inductive $u \ (\text{run } n \ s \ x_0) \ (\text{run } n \ t \ x_1)$

The proof of this lemma requires “Weak Step Consistency”, “Locally Respects”, “Step Atomicity”, and all the assumptions on context switches.

3.3 ISK

The previous locale proves refinement in an unsatisfactory way: run is a partial function and whenever it does not return a result, all the theorems hold vacuously. Consider for example an interpretation where function $kprec_0$ always returns false. Regardless of the interpretation of all other functions, the run function will always return None and therefore the system can be proven secure. For these reasons, the locale is refined. The second refinement adds action sequences, as explained in Section 2.3. Function AS-set is introduced that formulates which action sequences can be executed by the kernel. A state invariant is introduced. Finally, function $kprec_1$ is introduced which is a refined version of the unconstrained function $kprec_0$. Where $kprec_0$ is a system wide precondition function, $kprec_1$ is a per-domain precondition function.

locale Interruptible-Separation-Kernel = Separation-Kernel

+
fixes AS-set :: ('action-t list) set
and invariant :: 'state-t \Rightarrow bool
and $kprec_1$:: 'state-t \Rightarrow 'dom-t \Rightarrow 'action-t \Rightarrow bool
assumes
 \vdots

All assumptions in Section 2.3 that concern action sequences are added. Function $kprec_0$ is refined, by the following assumption:

$$kprec_0\ s\ a \equiv \text{invariant } s \wedge kprec_1\ s\ (\mathbb{D}\ s)\ a$$

Also, unconstrained function *realistic* is refined, by the following assumption:

$$\text{realistic } \alpha \equiv \text{set } \alpha \subseteq \text{AS-set}$$

An execution is realistic if and only if it is a list of action sequences.

We can now formulate a total run function, since based on the new assumptions the case where the precondition does not hold, will never occur. This new run function is equivalent to the old one, with exception that the second-to-last case distinction (when the precondition does not hold) is removed. The second case where the given execution is None is removed as well. The function no longer optionally returns a state, but always return a state.

The main lemma in proving security for ISK, is that this total run function is strictly equivalent to the partial one. This means two things: 1.) under the new assumptions, the partial function never returns None but always produces a state and 2.) this state is equivalent to the result of the total run function. Function *strict-equal* returns true if and only if such an equivalence holds.

definition $\text{strict-equal} :: 'a\ \text{option} \Rightarrow 'a \Rightarrow \text{bool}$

where $\text{strict-equal } m\ a \equiv \text{case } m\ \text{of } \text{None} \Rightarrow \text{False} \mid (\text{Some } a') \Rightarrow a' = a$

We can now formulate the main lemma of locale ISK. Let function *run-total* embody the total run function as described above. Assuming the invariant, and assuming that the given system execution is realistic, function *run* never returns None and is equivalent to the total run function.

lemma $\text{run-total-equals-run}$:

assumes $\text{realistic } x$

and $\text{invariant } s$

shows $\text{strict-equal } (\text{run } n\ (\text{Some } s)\ x)\ (\text{run-total } n\ s\ x)$

In addition to this lemma, we prove lemma's stating that purging yields realistic traces. These lemma's assist in proving noninterference for ISK:

theorem $\text{unwinding-implies-NI-indirect-sources}$:

assumes $\text{realistic } x$

shows $\text{let } s\text{-f} = \text{run-total } n\ s0\ x\ \text{in}$

$\text{output } (\text{run-total } n\ s0\ (\text{ipurge-l } x\ (\mathbb{D}\ s\text{-f}))) =$

$\text{output } (\text{run-total } n\ s0\ (\text{ipurge-r } x\ (\mathbb{D}\ s\text{-f})))$

3.4 CISK

Up to now, function *control* has been left generic. The final refinement provides an interpretation of this function. This interpretation is based on functions *aborting*, *waiting* and *set_error_code*, whose intended semantics have been presented in Section 2.3.

```

locale Controlled-Interruptible-Separation-Kernel =
    Interruptible-Separation-Kernel
+
fixes aborting :: 'state-t  $\Rightarrow$  'dom-t  $\Rightarrow$  'action-t  $\Rightarrow$  bool
and waiting :: 'state-t  $\Rightarrow$  'dom-t  $\Rightarrow$  'action-t  $\Rightarrow$  bool
and set-error-code :: 'state-t  $\Rightarrow$  'action-t  $\Rightarrow$  'state-t
assumes
    :

```

Function *abort-control* is the control mechanism of CISK. It first checks whether the current domain has code to execute (the first two case distinctions). If not, it does not return an action and leaves the program code of the domain empty. If the domain has code to execute, two case can arise: the current action sequence can be empty or not. The first case occurs when the kernel has finished an action sequence. The kernel performs no action. It updates the execution of the current domain to start the next action sequence. If the current action sequence is not empty, the kernel is in the middle of executing an action sequence. The control mechanism first checks whether this action sequence is aborting. If so, it does not return an action. It updates the current system execution by removing the current action sequence. A state update can be done by setting error codes. If the action sequence is not aborting, it might be delayed. If so, no state change occurs. Otherwise, the control mechanism executes the next action given by the system execution.

```

function abort-control ::
  where abort-control s d []           = (None, [], s)
    | abort-control s d ([]#[])       = (None, [], s)
    | abort-control s d ([]#(as'#x')) = (None, as'#x', s)
    | abort-control s d ((a#as)#x') = (if aborting s d a then
      (None, x', set-error-code s a)
    else if waiting s d a then
      (Some a, (a#as)#x', s)
    else
      (Some a, as#x', s))

```

The main lemma in proving noninterference for CISK is that function *abort-control* is a valid interpretation of the generic control mechanism. All assumptions that have been made on generic function *control* are discharged. Since this locale is

an interpretation of the previous one, theorem unwinding-implies-NI-indirect-sources from ISK holds for CISK as well. With it, the final theorem as presented in Section 2.2 is proven.

4 Related Work

The work presented in this paper is heavily indebted to the work done by Rushby and it builds upon his research [1,4]. The concept of an unwinding theorem that proves noninterference from local proof obligations is originally from Goguen and Meseguer [8]. Rushby’s ipurge-based formulations of intransitive noninterference (originally by Haigh and Young [9]) has been subject to heavy scrutiny and a number of variations has been proposed [10,11,12]. Greve et al. propose separation axioms for nonexfiltration and noninfiltration [13,14]. Van der Meyden proposes a spectrum of different definitions of noninterference for intransitive policies, each with different strengths [11]. Gorrieri and Vernali present noninterference with downgraders for both deterministic and nondeterministic systems [15]. Engelhardt et al. transpose the conventional theorem of intransitive noninterference to the domain of nondeterministic systems [16]. The relation between the definition of intransitive noninterference as presented in this paper and the various definitions in the literature still has to be researched. The major difference is that our definition applies to the detailed model CISK, whereas the models considered by the previous works all consider abstract models such as Mealy machines or process algebras.

A notable exception is the work of Murray et al [5], in which a framework is presented for machine-checking unwinding conditions over the implementation of operating system kernels. This framework is applied to the seL4 micro-kernel. Murray et al. prove noninterference over an abstract specification and subsequently transfer that proof to C implementations via refinement [17].

5 Conclusion

We proposed a new formalization of intransitive noninterference. We developed a formal model of a separation kernel with control and interrupts. Kernel calls are composed of atomic actions. An interrupt may arrive after any atomic action. Over this model, we defined a novel formulation of noninterference. This new formulation, instead of purging away actions of non-interfering domains, replaces these actions by arbitrary ones, simulating an attacker. Our model, our formulation of noninterference, and all the proofs have been formalized using the Isabelle/HOL interactive theorem proving system.

Our model has more details than previous ones. Consequently, proofs over this model becomes complicated. Thanks to a refinement-based approach, these proofs are still manageable. On the other hand, thanks for these details, instantiating the model for realistic separation kernel should be easier. Our current future work focuses on showing that the high-level design of PikeOS is an instantiation of our model.

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